

Fluids of light in a nonlinear photorefractive medium

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Fluids of light in a nonlinear photorefractive medium

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Abstract

Abstract This thesis presents an experimental study of hydrodynamical phenomena of a laser propagating nonlinearly. For a medium presenting an intensity-dependent refractive index, and in the frame of the paraxial approximation, the intensity of the laser beam is equivalent to a density of a fluid, the propagation direction is seen as a time evolution of the fluid as well as the phase gradient of the laser beam defines a flow velocity and the nonlinear refractive index change allows defining a sound velocity of the fluid. Under this analogy, we call the propagating laser beam a *fluid of light*. In this thesis, we provide a study of the superfluidity concept of a fluid of light in a self-defocusing regime of the nonlinearity. It is defined as the absence of diffraction when the fluid of light encounters an obstacle. The parameters which control the superfluid transition are: the flow velocity as well as the sound velocity. They are monitored respectively through the wave vector and the intensity of the laser beam. In the frame of this analogy, we also present in this manuscript a study of vortex shedding regime as a result of the interaction between the fluid of light and the obstacle. Here, the obstacle is considered to be strong. When twice the flow velocity at the poles of the obstacle is larger than the sound velocity, pairs of vortex/anti-vortex are emitted demonstrating a hydrodynamical behaviour of the fluid of light. In order to underline the nonlinear refractive index change, we also report in this thesis a study of the photorefractive nonlinearity using the self-phase modulation effect.

Keywords: *Nonlinear optics, photorefractive effect, optical Kerr effect, self-phase modulation, wavefront-shaping, quantum fluids, Bose-Einstein condensates, superfluidity, Landau criterion, quantised vortices.*

Résumé L'objet de cette thèse est l'étude expérimentale des comportements hydrodynamiques d'un faisceau laser se propageant dans un milieu à réponse non-linéaire. Pour un milieu présentant un indice de réfraction qui dépend de l'intensité du laser, ainsi que dans le cadre de l'approximation paraxiale, l'intensité du faisceau est assimilée à une densité de fluide. L'axe de propagation représente le temps d'évolution du fluide, le gradient de phase du faisceau laser définit sa vitesse d'écoulement et la variation de l'indice de réfraction permet de définir une vitesse du son dans le fluide. Dans le cadre de cette analogie, nous appelons la lumière qui se propage, *fluide de lumière*. Dans cette thèse, nous étudions la notion de superfluidité de la lumière dans un régime non-linéaire auto-défocalisant (*self-defocusing*). Cette notion est définie par l'absence de diffraction lorsque le fluide de lumière se propage en présence d'un obstacle. Les paramètres permettant de contrôler la transition superfluide sont: la vitesse du fluide de lumière ainsi que la vitesse du son. La première est pilotée par la direction du vecteur d'onde, ainsi que la deuxième est contrôlée par l'intensité du laser. Nous étudions aussi dans le cadre de cette analogie, le régime d'émission de vortex quantifiés suite à l'interaction entre le fluide de lumière et l'obstacle, considéré dans ce cas comme étant fort. Quand deux fois la vitesse d'écoulement aux pôles de l'obstacle dépasse la vitesse du son, des paires de vortex/anti-vortex sont émises, démontrant ainsi un comportement hydrodynamique de la lumière. Dans le but de comprendre l'effet non-linéaire mis en jeu, nous présentons également dans cette thèse, une étude de l'effet photoréfractif non-linéaire en exploitant l'effet de l'automodulation de phase (*self-phase modulation*).

Mots clés: *Optique non-linéaire, effet photoréfractif, effet Kerr optique, automodulation de phase, mise-en-forme des fronts d'ondes, fluides quantiques, condensats de Bose-Einstein, superfluidité, critère de Landau, vortex quantifiés.*

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Quantum fluids of light	3
2.1	Quantum fluids	3
2.2	Introduction to quantum fluids of light	4
2.2.1	Fluids of light in cavity systems	5
2.2.2	Fluids of light in the propagating geometry	7
2.3	From nonlinear optics to hydrodynamics	11
2.3.1	The Madelung transformation and the hydrodynamical equations of light	11
2.3.2	Amplitude fluctuations on top of a fluid-of-light - the Bogoliubov dispersion relation	14
2.3.3	Landau criterion of superfluidity	18
2.4	Summary	20
3	Characterisation of a photorefractive nonlinear medium	23
3.1	Review of nonlinear optics	23
3.1.1	Introduction	23
3.1.2	The nonlinear polarisation and the equation of propagation	24
3.2	Photorefractive nonlinear effect	31
3.2.1	Introduction to the photorefractive effect	31
3.2.2	Refractive index modulation via the photorefractive effect	33
3.2.3	Description of E_{sc} in the band transport model	38
3.2.4	The isotropic and the anisotropic derivation of \mathbf{E}_{sc}	40
3.2.5	The equation of propagation in the SBN crystal	43
3.3	Characterisation of the medium via sSPM	45
3.3.1	Spatial self-phase modulation	45
3.3.2	Experimental procedure	51
3.3.3	Experimental set-up	52
3.4	Results and discussion	53
3.4.1	Far-field intensity distribution	54
3.4.2	Measurement of the nonlinear refractive index variation Δn	56
3.4.3	Measurement of the SBN's anisotropy	62
3.5	Summary	63
4	Superfluidity and drag-force cancellation in a fluid-of-light	65
4.1	Brief introduction to superfluidity	65
4.2	Probing superfluidity using a weakly perturbative obstacle	66
4.2.1	Probing superfluidity in a quantum fluid	66

4.2.2	Probing superfluidity in a fluid-of-light	68
4.2.3	Diffraction of a fluid-of-light over an obstacle	72
4.2.4	Optical parameters to probe the superfluid transition	74
4.2.5	Experimental set-up	77
4.3	Results and discussion	78
4.3.1	Diffraction suppression in the intensity distribution	79
4.4	Optical drag force	81
4.4.1	Optical drag force - the shape of the fluid-of-light and the displacement of the obstacle	83
4.4.2	Displacement of the obstacle in a Gaussian potential	87
4.4.3	Extraction of the displacement due to the superfluid/frictional regimes	91
4.4.4	Experimental results and discussion	92
4.5	Summary	96
5	Vortex observation in a fluid-of-light	97
5.1	Introduction	97
5.1.1	General techniques of generating optical vortices	98
5.2	Review of optical vortices	98
5.2.1	Optical vortices description	99
5.3	Optical vortex generation in a fluid-of-light and experimental set-up	105
5.3.1	Vortex generation in a fluid-of-light	105
5.3.2	Experimental set-up	106
5.3.3	Physical mechanism of optical vortex pairs nucleation	107
5.4	Preliminary results and discussion	108
5.4.1	Potential induced by a Bessel beam	110
5.4.2	Potential induced by a Gaussian beam	113
5.5	Chapter 4 summary and perspectives	117
6	Conclusion and perspectives	119
A	Fluids-of-light in the propagating geometry	121
A.A	Derivation of the light's hydrodynamical equations	121
A.B	Derivation of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation for a fluid-of-light	123
A.C	The Madelung transformation for a quantum fluid	125
A.D	Bogoliubov dispersion relation in quantum fluids	125
A.D.1	Bogoliubov theory for weakly interacting Bose gas - ground state energy	125
A.D.2	Excitation spectrum - Higher order approximation	126
A.D.3	Small amplitude oscillations - Bogoliubov dispersion relation	128
B	Experiment and techniques	131
B.A	Experimental set-up - experimental control of the parameters	131
B.A.1	Experimental set-up	131
B.A.2	The spatial light modulator (SLM)	134
B.A.3	The digital micromirror device (DMD)	137
B.A.4	Determination of the white light power	140
B.B	Negative velocities measurements artifacts	142

Chapter 1

Introduction

The phenomenological discovery of liquid helium superfluidity^[1,2] has triggered a new field of research in physics related to quantum mechanics and condensed matter physics. The property of the wave-particle duality allows to define a wavelength of the particle λ_{dB} called the de Broglie wavelength^[3] and the average of this wavelength of a gas particles defines the so-called the thermal de Broglie wavelength λ_{th} . When this latter is comparable to the mean interparticle spacing in a gas, the Bose-Einstein and the Fermi-Dirac statistics become decisive in predicting the behaviour of the fluid; in a Fermi gas, the particles are known to obey the Pauli exclusion principle preventing them from occupying simultaneously the lowest state at zero temperature. In contrast, the Bose-Einstein statistics allow particles to gather simultaneously in the lowest energy state giving rise to a single-particle behaviour. That is recognised as the *Bose-Einstein condensate*. When the interactions between the particles (bosons) add up to the single-particle state, a wide range of new physical phenomena are triggered, such as the superfluidity, superconductivity effects^[4,5] and quantum Hall effect. The theory which deals with the collective behaviour of interacting particles is called the *many-body physics* and the systems exhibiting these effects are referred to as *quantum fluids*. The latter has been of interest to numerous systems suchlike, liquid helium,^[6-8] ultracold atoms in trapped gases,^[9-12] electrons in solid matter^[13,14] and other different particle systems. However, these systems consider only matter particles like electrons and atoms. Therefore, the question one might ask is: *can we simulate many-body physics using massless particles like photons? If so, is it possible to consider a light beam as a fluid?*

From the viewpoint of quantum mechanics, light consists of quantum particles called photons, which as well possess wave properties. Adding up to this the bosonic aspect of photons, light seems to be interesting to form a Bose-Einstein condensate of photons. When light particles occupy the same energy state and are close to each other (i.e. coherence), their wave functions can add up to form a single-particle state. Hence, a coherent laser beam can be seen as a condensate of photons. Nevertheless, the photons of a laser beam in vacuum are lacking of essential properties to get a fluid-like behaviour. Particularly, mass and photon-photon interactions. This latter exists in vacuum but it is very weak such that a practical interaction between photons cannot be seen. Therefore, a fluid-like behaviour of light cannot be emphasised in vacuum. Thus, a question arises, *how can we establish interactions between photons?*

The answer to this problematic comes from the theory of nonlinear optics,^[15,16] which predicts the establishment of photon-photon interactions through light matter interaction. In fact, a laser beam shone onto a nonlinear medium induces a transverse local refractive index change, which for its part controls the behaviour of the light beam. Therefore, an effective interaction between photons arises and this effective interaction is controlled through the sign of the refractive index change. Finally, obtaining a fully fluid-like description of a light beam requires giving photons a finite mass. This can be achieved on the one hand by

confining the light beam between two mirrors,^[17] or on the other hand through the paraxial approximation of a propagating light beam^[18]. We call the first apparatus the cavity configuration and the second one the propagating geometry. In this manuscript, we tackle solely the propagating geometry. In the latter configuration, the light beam propagates into a nonlinear self-defocusing medium and the collective behaviour of photons is described by the Gross-Pitaevskii equation, where the axis of propagation plays the role of time, the intensity of the laser beam is equivalent to the density of the fluid of light and the flow velocity of the fluid of light is defined as the gradient of the wave's spatial phase.

Fluids of light open up new perspectives to simulate many-body physics phenomena using a photonic system (i.e. the cavity or the propagating geometry). Thanks to their ability of being fully controlled in density, phase and in nonlinearity, fluids of light allow accessing and studying in detail phenomena of many-body physics, such as superfluidity,^[19] quantised vortical structures,^[20,21] quantum turbulence,^[22,23] analogue gravity^[24,25] and a few other effects. In addition to this, fluid of light systems allow to create new geometries that are unavailable in the quantum fluids counterpart and suggest propitious applications to quantum computing. In this manuscript, we present an experimental investigation of fluids of light in the propagating geometry. This latter presents less technological expenses compared to the cavity geometry.

Broadly speaking, we suggest in this manuscript to tackle the concept of superfluidity in quantum fluids of light also we will present a preliminary observation of quantised vortex shedding in this system. Far from the concept of fluids of light, we suggest an experimental characterisation of the nonlinear medium we used to study fluids of light. To do so the manuscript was organised as follows:

Chapter 2 is devoted to presenting the concept of quantum fluids and quantum fluids of light, stressing the analogies between original system and the fluid of light system. Also, we suggest giving the general framework of fluids of light, the equations that model the flow of a photon fluid and the parameters that control the system. Afterwards, we give briefly the dispersion equation of a small perturbation created on top of the fluid of light, namely the Bogoliubov dispersion relation. Thereafter, a crucial criterion is given to determine the superfluid behaviour of a fluid of light. This criterion is very important to understand because our study of superfluidity relies essentially on this criterion.

Chapter 3 deals with nonlinear optics precisely the photorefractive nonlinearity. We propose in this chapter to briefly remind the theory of nonlinear optics. Thereafter, we give a detailed description of the photorefractive nonlinearity and the mechanisms behind the photorefractive effect. Afterwards, a technique to measure the nonlinear refractive index change as well as the anisotropic characteristic of photorefractive medium is provided. Finally, we present the results of characterisation of the Strontium Barium Niobate crystal.

Chapter 4, which represents the core chapter of this manuscript deals with the concept of superfluidity, which is one of the manifestations of the many-body physics. We first define the notion of superfluidity in the original system (i.e. liquid helium). Thereafter, in analogy with quantum fluids, we give a definition to the concept of superfluidity in fluids of light and we propose a principle to probe this physical phenomena. Finally, in the results section, we give evidences of light superfluidity.

Chapter 5 tackles the concept of optical vortices in the fluid of light framework. In this chapter, we suggest to define an optical vortex, giving as well the theory that describes amplitude of a vortex in a fluid of light. Thereafter, we briefly present the principle and the mechanism that allow to create optical vortices in a fluid of light. Finally, we present the results relative to the observation of optical vortex structures in a fluid of light.

Chapter 2

Quantum fluids of light

2.1 Quantum fluids

A quantum fluid is a system featuring quantum mechanical effects at the macroscopic scale. Quantum mechanical effects becoming significant at the de Broglie wavelength λ_{DB} , they appear when the mean spacing between particles (e.g particles of a bosonic gas) d is smaller than λ_{DB} (figure 2.1). The key parameter that controls this wavelength is the temperature of the system T - We restrict our brief description to only bosonic systems.

When the temperature T of a bosonic gas approaches the absolute zero value, the particles of the system (bosons) become large and occupy the same energy state. This results in a collective wave function denoted by ψ . This is known as the Bose-Einstein condensation (BEC) phenomenon (see figure 2.1.(c)).

Figure 2.1: Bose-Einstein condensation process. λ_{DB} is the de Broglie wavelength of each particle and d is the mean spacing between the particles. Panel (a), far from the condensation temperature, the particles of the fluid are moving arbitrarily with different velocities. Panel (b), near the condensation temperature, the particles start to occupy the ground energy state. Panel (c), at the condensation temperature T_c , all the particles of the fluid occupy the lowest energy state and exhibit a collective wave behaviour.

Quantum fluids differ from classical fluids in many ways. In classical fluids, particles with a definite volume are determined by the position and the momentum quantities. The accessible energies are described by the Boltzmann distribution and the dynamics of the fluid are governed by the Navier-Stokes equations.^[26] In contrast, particles in quantum fluids cannot be distinguished and their collective behaviour has to be considered as statistical in particular, a bosonic gas is described by the Bose-Einstein distribution rather than

the Boltzmann distribution.

At zero temperature, the time evolution of the condensate is governed by the Gross-Pitaevskii equation (GPE)^[12]:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(\mathbf{r}, t)}{\partial t} = \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(\mathbf{r}, t) + g|\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2 \right] \psi(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (2.1)$$

where $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the wave function of the condensate, ∇^2 is the transverse Laplacian operator, m is the mass of atoms and $V(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is an external potential acting on the system (not taken into account in further analysis in this chapter). The nonlinear term $g|\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)|^2$ arises from the interactions between the particles.

If one is able to assign an effective mass to photons and to trigger an effective interaction between them, then a laser beam can be seen as an ensemble of bosonic particles and thus turns out to be an interesting system to probe quantum fluid phenomena in the framework of quantum fluids of light.

We dedicate the whole first chapter to the description of quantum fluids of light. To do so, we suggest in the next paragraph to introduce the general concept of quantum fluids of light and to present thereafter the possible experimental configurations that support quantum fluids of light. Later on, we focus our description on the specific configuration that pertains to our work. In further sections, we give in detail the hydrodynamical description of light, the Bogoliubov theory as well as a key criterion to determine the superfluid behaviour of light, namely, the Landau criterion of superfluidity.

2.2 Introduction to quantum fluids of light

Our interpretation of light has been through different directions, from Newton's interpretation^[27] to Maxwell's theory of electromagnetism. For decades, Maxwell's theory showed a strong consistency by explaining all the experimental phenomena, particularly interference and diffraction. At the beginning of the 20th century the electromagnetic theory was incapable of explaining some physical phenomena such as the black-body radiation^[28] and the photo-electric effect.^[29] Therefore, the first step to a quantum mechanical theory was achieved. Its principle relies on the quantisation of the energy spectrum of anybody. Particularly light can be seen as an ensemble of particles called "photons" carrying a linear momentum $\mathbf{p} = \hbar\mathbf{k}$, where $|\mathbf{k}| = 2\pi/\lambda$ is the wave number of photons and λ being their wavelength.

In the frame of linear optics, photons do not exhibit any interaction with each other. This intuitive picture was soon put back into the study with the advent of the laser. This latter fosters the photon-photon interaction in certain optical devices. The possibility of such interactions creates a collective behaviour of photons, giving birth to a possible fluid-like description. Thereby, we define a fluid of light as follows:

Definition of a fluid of light: *It is a collective behaviour of photons in an effective interaction.*

In the recent few years, many experimental and theoretical works were carried out to study quantum fluids of light, as a reference to most of these works we cite the review of I. Carusotto and C. Ciuti^[17] Among the possible configurations in optics providing effective interactions are the semi-conductor cavity systems. They allow the emergence of a new particle-like concept called "polariton"^[30], that we'll discuss later in the following subsection. This quasi-particle possesses few interesting features of quantum fluids. Another configuration able to exhibit effective photon interactions is the all-optical propagating geometry.

This configuration is the one that concerns this work. Therefore, we focus our description mainly on the propagating geometry.

Naturally, if we cross two lasers in space, they will not exhibit any interaction. Nevertheless, it has been predicted by Heisenberg and co-workers through the use of the quantum electrodynamics approach that a photon-photon interaction exists in vacuum thanks to the virtual electron-positron cloud assumed to be created around the photon.^[31] This prediction is difficult to attain because of the negligible cross-section of photon-photon scattering in vacuum which is of the order of, $\sigma \propto \frac{\hbar^2}{m_e^2 c^2} \left(\frac{\hbar\omega}{m_e c^2}\right)^6 \approx 10^{-26} \text{ cm}^2$, where \hbar is the Planck constant, c is the speed of light in vacuum, m is the mass of the electron and ω is the frequency of the photon.

Now, if we propagate a laser beam in any medium other than vacuum, then light might interact with the material. This interaction induces a variation of the refractive index of the material (see chapter 3). The refractive index variation results in a collective behaviour of photons interacting effectively. Therefore, to get this behaviour, one has to send an optical wave into a semi-conductor medium or a highly nonlinear dielectric one.

To obtain a fully fluid-like behaviour one needs to assign photons an effective mass. This can be ensured on the one hand using a cavity geometry, in which photons are spatially confined between two mirrors and on the other hand using the propagating geometry under the assumption of the paraxial approximation.^[15]

2.2.1 Fluids of light in cavity systems

Let us consider a quantum well embedded in a semi-conductor micro-cavity of a thickness l_z and an index of refraction n_0 in which photons are confined (see figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Sketch of a semi-conductor micro-cavity embedding a quantum well bounded by two Bragg mirrors. The wave vector is quantised along the z -axis. The photons of the micro-cavity are strongly coupled to the excitons in the quantum well. A laser beam of frequency ω excites the micro-cavity with an incidence angle θ . The light escaping from the cavity allows to measure the intensity distribution in the real space and k -space. Adapted from^[32]

The dynamics of the micro-cavity photons along the z -axis are quantised as, $k_z = \pi j/l_z$, j being a positive integer number. The frequency dispersion relation of these photons as a function of the in-plane

wave vector is given by:

$$\omega_c(k) = \frac{c}{n_0} \sqrt{k_z^2 + k^2} \approx \frac{ck_z}{n_0} + \frac{ck^2}{2k_z n_0} = \omega_c^0 + \frac{\hbar k^2}{2m_{\text{eff}}} \quad (2.2)$$

Where ω_c^0 is the cutoff frequency specific to the cavity dimensions, $k^2 = k_x^2 + k_y^2$ is the wave number of laser beam in the (x, y) -plane and $m_{\text{eff}} = \hbar k_z n_0 / c$ is effective mass of photons. One can estimate this latter to, $m_{\text{eff}} \approx 10^{-5} m_e$, for $k_z = 10^6 \text{ m}^{-1}$ and $n_0 = 1$, where m_e is the mass of an electron. The equation (2.2) is a generic form of $\omega(k)$ that shows how photons can be assigned an effective mass.

In figure 2.2, at the quantum well, one sees the emergence of a quasi-particle called the exciton. This latter is considered as a bound state of an electron and a hole. They are bounded by the electrostatic coulomb force. The exciton quasi-particle forms when a material absorbs a photon of higher energy than its bandgap. It is a bosonic quasi-particle since it is formed by two fermionic particles.

In the strong coupling regime, the photon illuminating the micro-cavity couples with the exciton to form a new quasi-particle called the polariton.^[33,34] This quasi-particle is as well a boson, since it is made up of two bosons. Thanks to their interacting part ensured by the excitons, polaritons have revealed plenty of interesting features like the Bose-Einstein condensation^[32] and superfluidity.^[35]

Figure 2.3: Figure of the dispersion relations versus the wave number k . Solid line curve represents the dispersion relation of the polariton which has an upper and a lower part. The colors of the curve are chosen as a function of the fraction photon-exciton. The dashed red curve represents the energy dispersion of the exciton. It has a parabolic behaviour but due to its heavy mass, the exciton quasi-particle is assumed constant in this interval of k . The dispersion energy of the photon cavity is represented by the dashed blue curve. Adapted from^[36].

We present in figure 2.3 the dispersion relations of the polariton (solid lines) and the exciton (red dotted line) quasi-particles as well as the dispersion relation of the micro-cavity photons (blue dotted line). The figure shows the parabolic form of the dispersion relation relative to the photons micro-cavity. The energy dispersion of the exciton has also a parabolic form. However, in the figure, it appears to be constant. This is

because the mass of the electron is much larger than the effective mass of the photon. These two dispersion relations mix in the strong coupling regime and yield to the dispersion relation associated to the polariton quasi-particle represented by the solid lines. One observes on the figure the existence of two polariton types called the upper and the lower polariton. Note on this figure that the in-plane wave vector \mathbf{k} monitors the dispersion relation of the polariton quasi-particle.

To describe the physics behind the polaritonic system, we have to deal with the quantum field description of photons, excitons and their interactions inside the cavity. This is not the goal of this manuscript. However, It is worth mentioning that this system obeys to an equation similar to the Gross-Pitaevskii equation (2.1) besides the additional terms of the driven-dissipative behaviour. For whom who are interested in learning more about the dynamics of polaritons, please refer to the articles.^[17,34] The fact that this system is being driven-dissipative makes it easy to visualize the field inside the microcavity because the light escaping from this latter is essentially a copy of the light inside. Therefore, visualizing the near-field photons escaping from the cavity allows to access the spatial intensity distribution of the field inside the cavity. While the far-field photons allow to measure its momentum distribution.

The micro-cavity systems have shown a great capability for simulating many-body physics, such as the Bose-Einstein condensation BECs of excitons^[37], and later on BECs of polaritons was reported.^[32] Recently, a room temperature BEC was achieved by Lerario et al.^[35], thanks to the small effective mass of photons and to organic micro-cavities instead of semi-conductor ones. The first suggestion of a superfluid study of polaritonic system was proposed^[38,39], and verified experimentally^[40], further studies were performed reporting the hydrodynamic nucleation of vortex dipole^[21,41], and dark solitons.^[42,43]

To summarize, polaritons represent a suitable system to probe many-body physics phenomena, and fluid-like behaviour which allows us to characterize the dispersion relation. Also these systems allow to have a good control of the nonlinearity. However, they present some weaknesses such as the short lifetime of the polariton quasi-particle, which is of the order 100 ps.

In the past section, we have presented a brief description of the cavity systems. In the following of the manuscript, we will focus on the second system, namely, the propagating geometry.

2.2.2 Fluids of light in the propagating geometry

Introduction to the propagating geometry From another perspective, we can study fluids of light using a different configuration called the propagating geometry. This constitutes another way to trigger effective interaction by exploiting the nonlinear response of an optical medium.

In the linear regime, light propagates in media and undergoes effects of linear absorption and linear refraction. Conversely, in the nonlinear regime, light interacts with matter. This interaction gives birth to plenty of interesting phenomena given briefly in Chapter3. The most important property brought by the nonlinearity is the possibility to control the nonlinear refractive index of the material by the propagating light.

Historically, the first suggestion of a fluid of light in the propagating geometry was made by Frisch and co-workers^[44], where they simulated the flow around a disk of a system governed by the nonlinear Schrödinger equation, demonstrating the existence of a drag force applied on the disk and the emission of vortices. Later on, an important theoretical work was carried out to highlight the hydrodynamical proper-

ties of light in a self-focusing and a self-defocusing media. This work has covered the liquid-like solitonic structure^[45], vortex emission^[46,47], dispersive shock waves^[48], scattering of light in a material defect^[49], superfluid motion^[50] and the generation of acoustic black holes.^[51] Despite all this theoretical work, not many have experimentally investigated the hydrodynamical behaviour of light in the propagating geometry. Among the few activities, we refer to the work done in the self-focusing environments on the one hand, such as soliton observation in fibers and crystals^[52,53], the modulational instability in optical fibers^[54], the observation of optical rogue waves^[55] as well as the achievement of wave condensation in waveguides and in optical fibers.^[56,57] In the self-defocusing medium on the other hand, with the experimental study of vortices, solitons stability and interactions^[58,59], the observation of dispersive shock waves^[60] as well as the classical wave condensation^[61] and recently the measurement of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of a fluid of light.^[62,63]

We illustrate in figure 2.4 the principle of a fluid of light in the propagating geometry. In this configuration, a laser beam is sent through a nonlinear medium along the z -direction, where the nonlinearity ensures the effective interactions of photons. Note on figure 2.4 that the axis of propagation z of the optical wave is mapped to a certain time t . This property will be clarified later. However, here we illustrate the propagation of a laser beam as an evolution of a fluid density.

Figure 2.4: A sketch of a fluid of light in the propagating geometry. A laser beam is sent through a nonlinear medium along the z -axis. The space time mapping is shown in the figure, where z is equivalent to time t . Each image measured at a distance z corresponds to a snapshot at time t . We illustrate on the image the propagation of the fluid of light as the time evolution of a certain fluid.

As we pointed out earlier, to attain the complete hydrodynamical approach of light, we need also to assign photons a certain mass. In the propagating geometry, this is ensured by considering the paraxial propagation of the light beam (also called the slowly varying envelop approximation see chapter 3). Under this approximation photons acquire an effective mass proportional to the wave number of the laser beam $n_0 k_0 = 2\pi n_0 / \lambda_0$, where λ_0 is the wavelength of the light beam in vacuum.

Under these considerations (i.e. effective photons interactions and the paraxial approximation), we qualify the propagating laser beam as the *fluid-of-light*.

In the next paragraph, although described in detail in chapter 3, we give the equation that models the propagation of a light beam in a nonlinear medium under the paraxial approximation and also, we give a brief description of the nonlinearity used for the hydrodynamical approach.

The propagation equation and the analogy with GPE The equation that describes the propagation of a laser beam in a bulk nonlinear medium under the paraxial approximation is given as follows:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, z) + k_0 \Delta n(I) \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, z), \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, z)$ is the amplitude of the laser beam, $I = |\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, z)|^2$ is its intensity, \mathbf{r} is the radial coordinate in the transverse plane and z being the direction of propagation of the laser beam.

In a nonlinear medium the propagating light induces a variation of the refractive index denoted by $\Delta n(I)$. This refractive index change is essentially controlled by the intensity of the light beam. The derivation of the above equation is given in detail in chapter 3. Here, we use it to derive the hydrodynamical approach of light. In the case of a Kerr-type nonlinearity (i.e. $\Delta n(I) \propto I$), equation (2.3) can be considered as an analogue to the nonlinear Schrödinger equations. The latter is similar to the Gross-Pitaevskii equation (2.1) which models the time evolution of a Bose-Einstein condensate, where the time axis is equivalent to the propagation axis z of eq. (2.3). Therefore, a measurement of the fluid-of-light at a certain distance z_n would be equivalent to a snapshot of the fluid-of-light at a time $t_n = (n_0 z_n / c)$ in the hydrodynamical framework (see figure 2.4).

Fluid-of-light systems can have different signs of the nonlinearity Δn . Therefore, different regimes of the light propagation arise. In the case of the self-focusing regime $\Delta n(I) > 0$, the light beam self-focuses (see figure 2.5.(a)). This can be interpreted in terms of fluids-of-light as an attractive force between photons. Within this regime the laser beam can exhibit many interesting effects analogous to some effects in hydrodynamical physics. Nevertheless, in the study of the superfluid behaviour of light, we consider the self-defocusing regime of nonlinearity $\Delta n(I) < 0$ because it provides an effective repulsive-type interaction between the photons (see figure 2.5.(b)).

Figure 2.5: Illustration of the behaviour of a laser beam propagating through a self-focusing nonlinear medium (a) and a self-defocusing nonlinear medium (b).

The form of the refractive index change is specific to each medium, but generally it depends on the intensity of the propagating beam.^[29] It also depends on the intrinsic properties of the medium, namely, its permittivity. The most common nonlinearity used to study fluids-of-light is the Kerr-type nonlinearity. In Chapter 3, we give the principle of this nonlinear effect. The refractive index variation due to optical Kerr effect is given as follows:

$$\Delta n(I) = n_2 I \quad (2.4)$$

Where n_2 is the optical Kerr coefficient that can be positive or negative. It is given as a function of the nonlinear susceptibility $\chi^{(3)}$ of the material by (see Chapter 3):

$$n_2 = -\frac{3\chi^{(3)}}{8n_0} \quad (2.5)$$

Substituting the expression of the nonlinear refractive index change in the equation of propagation (2.3) yields:

$$i\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r},z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0n_0}\nabla_{\perp}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r},z) + k_0n_2I\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r},z), \quad (2.6)$$

The above equation is the nonlinear wave equation under the paraxial approximation in a Kerr-type nonlinear medium. Compared to equation (2.1), equation (2.6) is very similar to the Gross-Pitaevskii equation without the external potential $V(\mathbf{r},t)$. Where:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial z}A(\mathbf{r},z) &\leftrightarrow \frac{\partial\psi(\mathbf{r},t)}{\partial t}, \\ \frac{1}{2k_0n_0}\nabla_{\perp}^2A(\mathbf{r},z) &\leftrightarrow \frac{\hbar}{2m}\nabla^2\psi(\mathbf{r},t) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$k_0n_2I \leftrightarrow g|\psi(\mathbf{r},t)|^2$$

Therefore, under the analogy with the Gross-Pitaevskii equation we can deduce the analogous terms between this latter and the nonlinear wave equation eq. (2.6):

$$A(\mathbf{r},z) \equiv \psi(\mathbf{r},t), \quad n_2I(\mathbf{r},z) \equiv g|\psi(\mathbf{r},t)|^2, \quad \text{and} \quad n_0k_0 \equiv \frac{m}{\hbar} \quad (2.7)$$

The amplitude of the laser beam $A(\mathbf{r},z)$ is equivalent to the wave function of the condensate $\psi(\mathbf{r},t)$, the nonlinear term in optics is equivalent to the interactions between bosons of the condensate and the wave number n_0k_0 is equivalent to the mass of the condensate m .

In our study, we use a photorefractive medium instead of a Kerr-type nonlinear medium. The model that describes the photorefractive nonlinearity is detailed in chapter 3. However, here, we would like to point out that the photorefractive nonlinearity can be considered as a Kerr-type nonlinearity with a saturable behaviour. The refractive index change induced through the photorefractive effect is given as follows:

$$\Delta n(I) = \Delta n_{\max} \frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{I} + 1}, \quad (2.8)$$

where \tilde{I} comprises the intensity of the laser beam divided by a certain intensity intrinsic to the photorefractive medium denoted I_{sat} and Δn_{\max} is the maximum refractive index variation possible to reach. In the following paragraphs of this chapter, we use a generic form of the refractive index change denoted $\Delta n(I)$. As mentioned earlier, in our work, we focus on the self-defocusing nonlinear regime. The procedure to obtain a negative refractive index change $\Delta n(I) < 0$ is specific to each medium. In our system (i.e. photorefractive SBN crystal), we exploit the possibility of inverting the voltage applied on the photorefractive medium.

Unlike the micro-cavity system where fluids-of-light (polaritons) have a limited lifetime, the current system does not present any limited lifetime of fluids-of-light (photons). Also regarding the experimental complexity of the polaritonic system, the propagating geometry presents simpler experimental set-up. Before we dive into the details of the hydrodynamical description of light, we propose to give some clarifications about the saturable nonlinearity and how it can be seen as a Kerr-type nonlinear effect in a definite interval of the light beam intensity.

Adaptation of the saturable nonlinearity to the hydrodynamical description of light The goal of this paragraph is to clarify few ideas concerning the saturable photorefractive nonlinearity and its adaptation to the hydrodynamical description of light. To explain this, we will firstly stress an important point about the saturable nonlinearity, namely, the refractive index change. As pointed out by eqn (2.8), when the normalized intensity \tilde{I} is high enough (i.e. $\tilde{I} \rightarrow +\infty \Leftrightarrow I \gg I_{\text{sat}}$), the medium does not exhibit any interaction with light. Hence, no effective interaction between photons takes place. Particularly, $\frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{I}+1} \rightarrow 1$:

$$\Delta n(I \gg I_{\text{sat}}) = \Delta n_{\text{max}}, \quad (2.9)$$

from eqn (2.9), one sees that the nonlinearity does not depend anymore on the intensity of the light beam (see chapter 3). Therefore, in the illuminated region, the medium behaves like a linear medium with a new constant refractive index. In this case, we cannot speak about an analogy between nonlinear optics and quantum fluids. Hence, we cannot define hydrodynamical quantities of a light beam. Therefore, in our study of fluids-of-light, typically in chapters 2, 4 and 5, we shall not consider the case when the refractive index saturates. Thus, in our description and experiments we consider solely the case when $I \ll I_{\text{sat}}$.

Subsequently, in this approximation, the nonlinear refractive index change follows a Kerr-like type nonlinearity. In fact, when $I \ll I_{\text{sat}}$ (i.e. $\tilde{I} \rightarrow 0$), the refractive index change is expressed as follows (we expanded $1/(\tilde{I}+1)$ into a 0th order Taylor series):

$$\Delta n(I \ll I_{\text{sat}}) \approx \Delta n_{\text{max}} \tilde{I} \approx \frac{\Delta n_{\text{max}}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I, \quad (2.10)$$

where I_{sat} is called the saturation intensity, which has nothing to do the intensity of the light beam. The saturation intensity is described in chapter 3. In the following of our study, to have a valid hydrodynamical description of light, we will consider only this case (i.e. Kerr-like type nonlinearity). Finally, by considering this approximation, the calculus to define the hydrodynamical quantities of light shall be similar to the Kerr-type nonlinearity. That is what we present in the following section.

2.3 From nonlinear optics to hydrodynamics

In the last section we have briefly given some experimental and theoretical activities in the fluids-of-light framework and we have highlighted the analogy between the nonlinear wave equation and the GPE, without going into the details of the analogy. Therefore, the goal of this section is to derive the hydrodynamics equations of a light beam propagating into a nonlinear medium.

2.3.1 The Madelung transformation and the hydrodynamical equations of light

The similarities between equation (2.6) that describes the propagation of a laser beam in a nonlinear Kerr-type medium and the Gross-Pitaevskii equation for atomic Bose gases give an idea to use approaches of quantum hydrodynamics, particularly, the Madelung transformation. This method was used to understand the physical meaning of the Schrödinger equation that describes the wave function of one particle. It was assumed that the wave function of a particle can be written in the form of an amplitude times the exponential of a phase $\psi = \alpha e^{i\beta}$. The result of this assumption, was retrieving the hydrodynamical equations, namely, the continuity and the momentum conservation equations with the wave-particle parameters.^[64]

In the following we show that using the same procedure on the nonlinear wave equation leads to finding the hydrodynamical description of light. To simplify, let us consider that the wave envelop in equation (2.3)

is a scalar quantity. Also, we assume the absence of linear absorption. Using the Madelung transformation we can assume that the wave envelop of the laser beam can be written as follow:

$$A(\mathbf{r}, z) = \sqrt{\rho(\mathbf{r}, z)} e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{r}, z)} \quad (2.11)$$

Where $\rho(\mathbf{r}, z)$ is the light intensity and $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, z)$ is its phase. Notice that in the case of quantum fluids the z coordinate in the Madelung transformation is replaced by time t . However, to get the space time mapping we substitute in the wave equation (2.3) the z coordinate by ct/n_0 , where, c is the speed of light in vacuum and t is a fictitious time coordinate. Therefore, in the case of a Kerr-type nonlinearity, we recall the propagation equation:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} A(\mathbf{r}, z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 A(\mathbf{r}, z) + k_0 n_2 I A(\mathbf{r}, z), \quad (2.12)$$

Injecting equation (2.11) in the nonlinear wave equation (2.12) results in the hydrodynamical equations of a laser beam propagating in a nonlinear medium:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \rho(\mathbf{r}, t) + \nabla_{\perp} \cdot [\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)] = 0 \quad (2.13)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{v} + \rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla_{\perp}) \mathbf{v} + \nabla_{\perp} P - \rho \frac{c^2}{2k_0^2 4n_0^2} \nabla_{\perp} \left(\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}} \right) = 0 \quad (2.14)$$

The full derivation of these equations is given in the appendix A.A. The above equations are very similar to the Euler equations that describe the motion of an ideal fluid. Equation (2.13) is known as the continuity equation in hydrodynamic physics and equation (2.14) is the equation of momentum conservation of an ideal fluid flow. However, here all the parameters are defined by optical quantities. In fact, the quantity $\rho(\mathbf{r}, z)$ is the fluid (fluid-of-light) density and it is equal to the intensity of the laser beam propagating into the nonlinear medium.

$$\rho(\mathbf{r}, z) = I(\mathbf{r}, z), \quad (2.15)$$

The term $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)^1$ is the velocity of the fluid-of-light. It represents the transverse velocity of the propagating laser beam:

$$\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \frac{1}{k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, z) \quad (2.16)$$

We will see in chapter 4 that this velocity simplifies to the angle of incidence of the laser beam in the case of a plane wave. Note that the form of the velocity \mathbf{v} of the fluid-of-light (i.e. eq.(2.16)) is similar to the velocity defined for an ideal fluid^[26] as well as to the velocity of the condensate (A.32).

The quantity P is the term of pressure that we find in Euler's equations. In terms of optical parameters, P is defined by the nonlinearity of the medium. For the sake of simplicity we express it for a Kerr-type nonlinear medium:

$$P = k_0 \frac{n_2 I^2}{2n_0} \quad (2.17)$$

In quantum fluids, the term of pressure is given as function of the nonlinear interactions between the particles by, $P = gn^2/2$, where n is the density of the condensate.

From the expression of the pressure in the fluid-of-light (i.e. eq.(2.17)) we can deduce the expression of the sound velocity in the fluid-of-light using the analogy with quantum fluids. According to^[12] the square of the sound velocity in the fluid-of-light can be defined as the derivative of the pressure term P with respect to the intensity of the fluid-of-light divided by the wavenumber k_0 and we write:

$$c_s^2 = \frac{1}{k_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial I} P \quad (2.18)$$

Therefore, using the above equation. We can derive the expression of the sound velocity c_s ¹ in a fluid-of-light in the case of a Kerr-type nonlinearity:

$$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{n_2 I}{n_0}} \quad (2.19)$$

Note that for a photorefractive medium and in the case of Kerr-like type nonlinearity, the sound velocity reads, $c_s = \sqrt{\Delta n(I)/n_0}$, where $\Delta n(I) = \frac{\Delta n_{\max}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I$ is defined by equation (2.10).

In the equation of the momentum conservation we notice the presence of a extra term (R.H.S term of the equation (2.14)). This term does not exist in Euler's equations, but it is present in the hydrodynamical equations of quantum fluids. It is called the quantum pressure term. It reveals the quantum origin of quantum fluid systems. It can be neglected if it is larger than a certain characteristic length of the system.^[12] Analogously, in nonlinear optics the quantum pressure term can be neglected if:

$$\left(\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}} \right)^{-1/2} \gg \xi, \quad (2.20)$$

where ξ is a characteristic length of the system called the healing length. It is defined as a function of the optical parameters as follows:

$$\xi = \frac{1}{n_0 k_0 c_s} = \frac{1}{n_0 k_0} \sqrt{\frac{n_0 I_{\text{sat}}}{\Delta n_{\max}}} \frac{1}{I} \quad (2.21)$$

When the condition (2.20) is satisfied, equation (2.14) takes the form of the Euler's equation in hydrodynamics

$$\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v} + \rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla_{\perp}) \mathbf{v} + \nabla_{\perp} P = 0 \quad (2.22)$$

To sum up, we have established in this section the hydrodynamical description of light in a nonlinear medium. We have to keep in mind that when a light beam propagates into a nonlinear medium, then its spatial intensity distribution evolving along z can be seen as a fluid flow evolving in time, where the time is the axis of propagation of the light beam (see figure 2.4). The flow velocity of that fluid is determined by the phase gradient of the light beam. In table 2.1, we give a summary of the main physical quantities of the fluid-of-light and their counterparts in quantum fluids.

¹Notice by definition that the fluid-of-light velocity v as well as the sound velocity in a fluid-of-light are dimensionless quantities

Table 2.1: A summary table of the physical quantities of the fluid-of-light and their counterparts in quantum fluids

Physical quantity	Fluids-of-light	Quantum fluids
Space/time	$z = (ct/n_0)$	t
wavenumber/mass	$n_0 k_0$	\hbar/m
Intensity/fluid density	$I(\mathbf{r}, z) = A(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) ^2$	$ \psi(\mathbf{r}, t) ^2$
velocity	$v(\mathbf{r}, z) = (1/n_0 k_0) \nabla_{\perp} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, z)$	$v(\mathbf{r}, t) = (\hbar/m) \nabla_{\perp} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$
Speed of sound	$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta n_{\max} I}{n_0 I_{\text{sat}}}}$	$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{gn}{m}}$
Healing length	$\xi = (1/n_0 k_0) \sqrt{n_0 / \Delta n(I)}$	$\xi = \hbar \sqrt{1/mgn}$

To underline the hydrodynamical approach, we suggest in the next subsection to derive the Bogoliubov energy spectrum of the fluid-of-light.

2.3.2 Amplitude fluctuations on top of a fluid-of-light - the Bogoliubov dispersion relation

The Bogoliubov dispersion relation expresses the energy E distribution as a function of the linear momentum p of the elementary excitations of an atomic Bose gas. It was derived by N. Bogoliubov in 1947.^[65] In this section, we briefly present the Bogoliubov theory applied to fluid-of-light systems.

To derive the Bogoliubov dispersion relation, we consider a small amplitude perturbation evolving on top of a uniform fluid-of-light. Figure 2.6 illustrates a fluid-of-light beam on top of which a small perturba-

Figure 2.6: The intensity distribution of a fluid-of-light beam on top of which a perturbation was introduced. Panel (a) shows the 2D intensity distribution of the fluid of light and the disturbance. Panel (b) displays the x -cut intensity distribution. Adapted from.^[66]

tion is introduced. We display respectively in figures 2.6.(a) and 2.6.(b) the 2D intensity distribution and a cut along the x -axis of the fluid-of-light.

The principle here is to study the behaviour of the small perturbation created on top of the fluid-of-light

during its propagation into the nonlinear medium. The fluid-of-light propagates along the z -axis and the amplitude of the background beam can be expressed as follows:

$$A_0(\mathbf{r}, z) = \sqrt{I_0} e^{-i\phi_{\text{nl}} z}, \quad (2.23)$$

where I_0 is the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam and $\phi_{\text{nl}} = k_0 n_2 I_0$ is the nonlinear phase accumulated by the fluid-of-light along its propagation. Notice that the expression (2.23) can be found through solving equation (2.6) by neglecting the effect of diffraction (i.e. $\nabla^2 A(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = 0$).

The amplitude of the perturbation denoted $\delta A(\mathbf{r}, z)$ can be put in the following form:

$$\delta A(\mathbf{r}, z) = [u(r)e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r)e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi_{\text{nl}} z}, \quad (2.24)$$

where $u(\mathbf{r})$ and $v(\mathbf{r})$ are the complex amplitudes of the perturbation and k_z is the wave number of the perturbation. Therefore, the total amplitude of the wave propagating in the nonlinear medium is expressed by:

$$A(\mathbf{r}, z) = A_0(\mathbf{r}, z) + \delta A(\mathbf{r}, z) = [\sqrt{I_0} + u(r)e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r)e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi_{\text{nl}} z} \quad (2.25)$$

To retrieve the energy spectrum of the perturbation, one should inject eq. (2.25) into the equation of propagation of the fluid-of-light (2.3). However, for the sake of simplicity, we assume that we possess a Kerr-type nonlinear medium (i.e. $\Delta n(I) = n_2 I$). Therefore, injecting (2.25) in equation (2.6) yields a set of differential equations of $u(r)$ and $v(r)$:

$$k_z u(r) = \left[\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} - k_0 n_2 I_0 + 2k_0 n_2 I_0 \right] u(r) + k_0 n_2 I_0 v(r) \quad (2.26)$$

$$k_z v(r) = \left[\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} - k_0 n_2 I_0 + 2k_0 n_2 I_0 \right] v(r) + k_0 n_2 I_0 u(r) \quad (2.27)$$

Equations (2.26) and (2.27) are known as the Bogoliubov equations. They can be solved numerically. However, an analytical solution to this system can be considered by assuming that the intensity I_0 is independent of the radial coordinates r and the perturbation has a plane wave form. It is expressed as follows:

$$u(\mathbf{r}) = u_0 e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{r}}, \quad \text{and} \quad v(\mathbf{r}) = v_0 e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{r}} \quad (2.28)$$

Now, substituting in the Bogoliubov equations the expression of $u(\mathbf{r})$ and $v(\mathbf{r})$ (i.e.(2.28)) gives the following set of equations:

$$k_z u_0 = -\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} u_0 + k_0 n_2 I_0 (u_0 + v_0) \quad (2.29)$$

$$-k_z v_0 = -\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} v_0 + k_0 n_2 I_0 (u_0 + v_0) \quad (2.30)$$

Therefore, from equations (2.29) and (2.30) one finds easily the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of a fluid-of-light:

$$k_z(k_{\perp}) = \sqrt{\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0} \left(\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0^2} - 2k_0 \frac{n_2 I_0}{n_0} \right)} \quad (2.31)$$

This equation predicts the behaviour of the perturbation wave number k_z as a function of transverse wavenumber k_\perp of the perturbation. A full derivation of this equation is presented in appendix A.B. This equation is important for understanding the behaviour of the fluid-of-light propagation in a nonlinear medium. Note that the counterpart expression of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation in quantum fluids has a similar form but with quantum fluid parameters. According to^[12], it is given by:

$$\hbar\omega = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m} \left(\frac{\hbar^2 k^2}{2m} + 2\hbar gn \right)}, \quad (2.32)$$

where ω is the frequency of the perturbation and k is the wave number of the perturbation. This equation expresses the dispersion of the energy as a function of the wavenumber k . One easily recognises the similarities between equations (2.31) and (2.32) by taking into account the analogous terms defined in table 2.1.

Notice that for the photorefractive medium and in the case of Kerr-like type nonlinearity the Bogoliubov dispersion relation for a fluid-of-light is expressed as follows:

$$k_z(k_\perp) = \sqrt{\frac{k_\perp^2}{2k_0} \left(\frac{k_\perp^2}{2k_0 n_0^2} - 2k_0 \frac{\Delta n_{\max} I}{n_0 I_{\text{sat}}} \right)} \quad (2.33)$$

It is worth mentioning that from the above equation, we can find the expression of the healing length ξ defined in the previous subsection. By considering the Bogoliubov dispersion relation one observes that two possible regimes of the fluid-of-light arise. We call these regimes the phonon-like regime and the particle-like regime.

Figure 2.7: Figure of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of a fluid-of-light. The grey box represents the region where the fluid-of-light exhibits a superfluid behaviour. The white region displays the predominance of the quadratic of k_z as a function of the k_\perp . The fluid-of-light in this region exhibits a frictional behaviour.

The particle-like regime occurs when $k_\perp \xi \gg 1$, where ξ is the healing length of the system $\xi =$

$(1/k_0 n_0) \sqrt{(\Delta n_{\max} I)/(n_0 I_{\text{sat}})}$. In this regime the Bogoliubov dispersion relation simplifies to a free particle-like form:

$$k_z(k_\perp) \approx k_\perp^2 / 2k_0 n_0 \quad (2.34)$$

We shall see later that in this regime the fluid-of-light exhibits a frictional behaviour and behaves like a normal fluid.

When $k_\perp \xi \ll 1$, the Bogoliubov dispersion relation takes the phonon-like expression

$$k_z(k_\perp) = c_s k_\perp, \quad (2.35)$$

where $c_s = (k_0 n_0 \xi)^{-1}$ is the optical analogue of the sound velocity defined previously. In this regime, the fluid-of-light is characterised by a superfluid behaviour.

We display in figure 2.7 the plot of the dispersion relation (2.33). One observes in the grey region a clear linear dependence of k_z on the transverse wave number k_\perp . That is for $k_\perp \xi \ll 1$. In the white area, the curve evolves with a quadratic behaviour corresponding to the particle-like regime.

As mentioned earlier, to experimentally characterize the Bogoliubov dispersion relation in fluids-of-light, one has to send through a nonlinear medium a uniform laser pump with frequency ω_0 , playing the role of the background fluid of density $I(\mathbf{r}, z)$ and to create a weak perturbation on top of this background fluid using another laser beam having the same frequency. The control parameters in this case are the transverse wave vector k_\perp and the intensity of the laser beam controlling the sound velocity c_s (i.e. ξ). The first characterization of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation in the propagating geometry was reported^[62], where they measured the phase velocity of the fluid-of-light by the help of an adapted oceanographic technique.^[67] As a nonlinear medium they used a liquid with a thermo-optical nonlinearity.

Recently, a more precise technique for characterising the Bogoliubov dispersion relation was reported.^[63] It relies on the direct measurement of the group velocity of the perturbation. The Bogoliubov dispersion relation is deduced from the group velocity using the following relation $k_z(k_\perp) = \omega(k_\perp) = \int_0^{k_\perp} v_g(k) dk$, where k is the wavenumber in the transverse plane the photon fluid, k_\perp is the maximum wavenumber in the transverse plane and v_g is the group velocity of the perturbation created on top of the fluid.

The measured Bogoliubov frequency $\Omega_B(k_\perp)$ is represented in figure 2.8. It represents a signature of a superfluidity exhibited by this system characterised by a spectrum of a phonon-like regime. So far, we have established the Bogoliubov dispersion relation in the context of fluids-of-light and we have seen that ξ represents the limit between two different states of the fluid-of-light, particularly a superfluid and a frictional state. In the next section, we will shed light on a more intuitive criterion for determining the superfluid behaviour of a fluid-of-light.

Figure 2.8: Panel (a) Figure of the group velocity versus the k_{\perp} . The solid line represents the simulation of the theoretical model and the circles represent the experimental measurement. The dashed line is the asymptotic behaviour. Panel (b) represents the curve of the dispersion relation after the integration of the group velocity v_g . From.^[63]

2.3.3 Landau criterion of superfluidity

We dedicate this section to defining the phenomenological criterion of superfluidity in quantum fluids and in fluids-of-light, the Landau criterion.

A fluid is said to be superfluid if it flows along capillaries without dissipating energy.^[7] This is true if the spectrum of the elementary excitations satisfies a certain condition. This criterion was derived by the physicist Lev Landau in 1941^[68] after the discovery of superfluidity in liquid helium in 1938.^[1,2]

Let us consider a quantum fluid flowing along a capillary with a velocity v_s . Unlike a normal fluid, the flowing velocity distribution is uniform inside the capillary. This is because of the absence of frictions with the capillary. Here, the dissipation of the energy process is only considered through elementary excitations creation. Therefore, Landau's idea was to study the spectrum of elementary excitations as a function of the fluid velocity. We illustrate in figure 2.9 the process of an elementary excitation generated in the quantum fluid.

To derive the Landau criterion let us consider a particle traveling at a velocity v_s on top of the quantum fluid and having a linear momentum \mathbf{P} (see figure 2.9). The excitation is generated if the particle loses energy. Let us denote by $\varepsilon(\mathbf{p})$ the amount of the energy lost by the particle and by \mathbf{P}' the momentum of the particle after the generation of the elementary excitation. This latter has for its part a momentum \mathbf{p} (see figure 2.9).

Figure 2.9: Sketch of a particle flowing at a velocity v_s on top of a quantum fluid. The superfluid is represented by the grey box and the quantum fluid particle is represented by the grey circle. Panel (a) shows the flow of the particle before the generation of the elementary excitation. Panel (b) shows the change of the flow velocity of the particle due to the elementary excitation. m is the mass of the particle. The quantities \mathbf{P} , \mathbf{P}' are respectively the momenta of the particle before and after losing energy. And \mathbf{p} is the momentum of the elementary excitation.

The energy and momentum conservation conditions lead us to write the following equations:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{p} + \mathbf{P}', \quad (2.36)$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{P}^2}{2m} = \varepsilon(\mathbf{p}) + \frac{\mathbf{P}'^2}{2m}, \quad (2.37)$$

where m is the mass of the particle. Substituting the expression \mathbf{P}' in the energy conservation equation (eq.(2.37)) gives the expression of the energy excitation as a function of \mathbf{P} and \mathbf{p} , and we write:

$$\varepsilon(\mathbf{p}) = \frac{\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{m} - \frac{\mathbf{p}^2}{2m} \quad (2.38)$$

Therefore, the energy of the created excitation fulfils the following condition:

$$\varepsilon(\mathbf{p}) \leq \frac{\mathbf{P} \cdot \mathbf{p}}{m} \quad (2.39)$$

Hence, if we assume that the direction of \mathbf{p} is parallel to \mathbf{v}_s then, the condition of existence of the elementary excitation can be put in the following form:

$$v_s \geq \min \left(\frac{\varepsilon(\mathbf{p})}{p} \right) = v_c \quad (2.40)$$

Where v_c is called the critical velocity. This condition is of a crucial importance for the study of superfluidity. In fact, it establishes a condition for the generation of an elementary excitation in a quantum fluid. In other words, if the flow velocity v_s of the quantum fluid is greater than the critical velocity v_c then the quantum fluid exhibits a frictional regime.

Therefore, recalling the expression of the Bogoliubov for quantum fluids eq.(2.32) allows to find the expression of the critical velocity v_c :

$$v_c = \min \left(\frac{\varepsilon(\mathbf{p})}{p} \right) = \min \left(\frac{\sqrt{\left(\frac{1}{4m^2}P^4 + \frac{gn}{m}P^2\right)}}{p} \right) = \sqrt{\frac{gn}{m}} = c_s^{\text{QF}}. \quad (2.41)$$

Where c_s^{QF} is the speed of sound in quantum fluids. By analogy with quantum fluids, one can establish a similar inequality (i.e. (2.40)) to fluids-of-light. Denoting by v the transverse velocity of the fluid-of-light defined previously, one writes in analogy with quantum fluids the condition of generating an excitation in a fluid-of-light as follows:

$$v \geq \min \left(\frac{k_z(k_\perp)}{k_\perp} \right) = c_s = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta n_{\text{max}}}{n_0 I_{\text{sat}}}} I, \quad (2.42)$$

where k_z is determined by the Bogoliubov dispersion relation (2.33) and k_\perp is the transverse wavenumber of the fluid-of-light. The critical velocity in this case equals as well the speed of sound in fluids-of-light.

The above inequality allows us to determine the behaviour of the fluid-of-light. To sum up this part, we should keep in mind the following statements:

- when $v < c_s$, then the fluid-of-light is said to be superfluid
- when $v > c_s$, then the fluid-of-light exhibits a frictional regime

Many experiments were carried out to investigate the concept of superfluidity, from gas helium^[1,69] cooled to $T \approx 0 \text{ K}$ to cold atoms.^[9] Few years ago, superfluidity was as well found in polaritonic fluids-of-light.^[40]

We show in figure 2.10 a measurement of the superfluidity signature in gas $^2\text{Helium}$ cooled to a temperature of 0.35 K. The experiment was carried by Allum and co-workers in 1977, it consists in introducing an obstacle in the quantum liquid and thus measuring the drag force applied by the liquid on the obstacle. According to^[69], it was reported for the quantum fluid (i.e. ^2He at $T = 0.35 \text{ K}$) that the drag force cancels for a flow velocity less than a critical velocity v_1 . In contrast, Allum and co-workers performed the same measurement for the ^2He above the condensation temperature. In this case, they reported the presence of the drag force for any value of the fluid velocity. This result confirms the prediction of Landau about the existence of the critical velocity for the breakdown of superfluidity.

In chapter 4 we present a detailed study of the superfluidity concept in the context of fluids-of-light based on the Landau criterion.

2.4 Summary

To sum up, in this chapter, we have presented the two possible configurations that support fluids-of-light, focusing our attention on the propagating geometry. We have derived the hydrodynamical equations of a fluid-of-light, pointing out the analogous terms between nonlinear optics and hydrodynamics. Thereafter, we have established the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of a small perturbation evolving on top of a fluid-of-light. Finally, we showed through the Landau criterion that in order to get a superfluid regime of a fluid-of-light, its velocity should be less than the speed of sound of the system c_s . To characterise this parameter, we suggest in chapter 3 to characterise the nonlinearity of the medium, since c_s is proportional to the square root of the nonlinear refractive index change Δn . Therefore, chapter 3 is devoted to the measurement of the nonlinear refractive index change $\Delta n(I)$ of a photorefractive medium.

Figure 2.10: Drag force measured on ion moving on top of superfluid Helium at 0.35 K and on a non-superfluid Helium at 4 K temperature versus the average velocity. The two curves show that for a superfluid Helium the drag force does not appear for a velocity smaller than the critical velocity $v_l = v_c$, while for a normal fluid the drag force is present as long as the velocity of the fluid $v > 0$ from. ^[69]

Chapter 3

Characterisation of a photorefractive nonlinear medium

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We dedicate this chapter entirely to the study and to the experimental characterisation of the nonlinear photorefractive effect. The latter can be viewed as the Kerr effect^[70] with a saturable behaviour. To do so, we suggest in the first section introducing briefly the theory of nonlinear optics, the concept of the medium's polarisation (response to an electromagnetic radiation) and the equation that describes the propagation into a nonlinear medium. Thereafter, in the second section, we propose to focus our attention on the photorefractive nonlinear effect, which represents the core subject of this chapter particularly of the Strontium Barium Niobate (SBN) crystal. The third section deals with the characterisation and the measurement of the SBN's optical properties through the effect of Self-Phase Modulation (SPM).^[71] Within this section, we present the results of the measurement of the SBN's nonlinear refractive index.

3.1 Short introduction to nonlinear optics²

3.1.1 Introduction

The theory of ray optics teaches us that laser beams propagate always in straight lines with a velocity $v = c/n$, where c is the speed of light in vacuum and n is the refractive index of the medium. It was known that the refractive index of a medium n depends only on the frequency of the propagating light (e.g. linear chromatic dispersion). This is because the sources of light used before the 1960s do not allow reaching the intra-atomic field of the medium in question. Thus, only a linear response of the material was exhibited. In linear optics, a laser beam shone onto a medium induces the motion of the medium's charges. These charges oscillate and radiate another electric field proportional to the incident field. The generated wave is phase-shifted compared to the incident field and the linear refractive index of the medium does not depend on the intensity of the laser.^[73]

When the intensity provided by a source of light is comparable to the intra-atomic field of a medium, a

²Many monographs describe perfectly the theory of nonlinear optics. In this thesis, we only give a brief reminder about the discipline. For more details about the theory of nonlinear optics we refer the reader to^[18,72].

nonlinear response to the optical radiation occurs. This regime is called the nonlinear optical regime. Nonlinear optics is a branch of physics that studies the propagation of a radiation capable of changing the properties of the material. In particular, its index of refraction. This latter may vary as a function of the laser's intensity. This is because of the changed electron distribution of the medium. Since the propagation of a laser beam is determined by the refractive index of the medium, then one can *control the propagation of light by light itself*.

The first theoretical prediction of a nonlinear optical process was done by M. G. Mayer in her PhD thesis in which she proposed a possible two-photon absorption by atoms.^[74] Years after, the first experimental manifestation of a nonlinear optical process was observed by Franken and coworkers.^[75] They frequency doubled a red laser at 694 nm generated from a solid-state ruby crystal getting the first blue laser of that time. Simultaneously, at Bell labs, Kaiser and Garrett discovered the effect of two-photon absorption^[76] in $\text{CaF}_2:\text{Eu}^{2+}$. Bloembergen developed the description of many nonlinear optical processes published in his monograph "Nonlinear optics".^[72]

Generally, the theory used to describe most of nonlinear optical processes is the Maxwell theory of electromagnetism.

3.1.2 The nonlinear polarisation and the equation of propagation

To describe the wave-matter interaction, the classical theory of electromagnetism is usually used. Within the frame of this theory, one needs to introduce the notions of the material's polarisation and susceptibility.^[18,77] This latter is a physical quantity of the material relating its response to an incident electromagnetic field. In the linear optical regime, the polarisation vector is proportional to the incident field. On the contrary, in the nonlinear optical frame, the polarisation vector depends on quadratic and cubic terms of the incident field.

Brief reminder on the concept of the polarisation The polarisation, commonly denoted by \mathbf{P} , represents the electric response of a material to an applied electric field. Physically, it is the dipole moment of the medium's charged particles per unit volume V induced through an applied electric field.^[78] Mathematically, it is generally represented by a vector.

The standard picture used to describe the polarisation \mathbf{P} vector is given by considering the medium as an ensemble of bounded charged particles (i.e. Drude's model). According to this model, the bounding is assumed to have a certain elasticity that allows the particles to move under the action of an applied electromagnetic field. We illustrate in figure 3.1 the electrons' motion in a dielectric medium under the application of an electric field.

$$E(\omega, t) \propto \cos(\omega t)$$

Figure 3.1: An illustration of the motion of bound charges in a dielectric medium which is subject to an electric field $\mathbf{E}(\omega, t)$.

The induced slight movement of the charged particles is an oscillatory motion that generates a collection of electric-dipole moments leading to the creation of the polarisation of the material.

Here, we consider only the impact of the electric field, because the influence of the magnetic field can be neglected.^[78]

The displacement of the bound electrons induced by the electric field $\mathbf{E}(\boldsymbol{\omega}, t)$ can be described by the equation of motion of an oscillator. When the displacement of these electrons is weak enough we usually consider a linearised version of the electron's motion equation.^[18,79] Hence, the response of the material is proportional to the incident field. The polarisation field within this regime is expressed by the following equation:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(1)}(t) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t), \quad (3.1)$$

where $\mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is called the linear polarisation vector, $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{(1)}$ is the linear susceptibility tensor, $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is the incident electric field and ε_0 is the dielectric constant of vacuum. In this expression, we considered that the response of the material is local and instantaneous. By taking the Fourier transform of equation (3.1) we express the linear polarisation as a function of the frequency of the incident wave:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) = \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(1)}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) \quad (3.2)$$

In the linear regime, the charged particles oscillate at the same frequency $\boldsymbol{\omega}$ of the incident electric field allowing to radiate a wave which undergoes purely linear effects. Particularly, the incident wave undergoes a refraction effect determined by the real part of the susceptibility $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{(1)}$ (refractive index) and an absorption effect defined by its imaginary part (absorption coefficient). Therefore, assuming that the field is polarised along the x -axis $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) = \frac{1}{2}[E(\mathbf{r})e^{-i\boldsymbol{\omega}t} + \text{c.c.}]e_x$, the refractive index of the medium as well as the absorption coefficient are given as follows:

$$n_0 = \text{Re} \left(\sqrt{1 + \chi_{xx}^{(1)}(\boldsymbol{\omega})} \right), \quad \alpha_0 = \text{Im} \left(\sqrt{1 + \chi_{xx}^{(1)}(\boldsymbol{\omega})} \right) \frac{\boldsymbol{\omega}}{c}, \quad (3.3)$$

where $\chi_{xx}^{(1)}$ is the xx component of the susceptibility tensor.

When the displacement of the electrons induced by the electric field is large enough, the linear approximation is no longer appropriate to describe the motion of the electrons. Therefore, one needs to take into account the anharmonic terms in the electron's motion equation. Consequently we should write the polarisation vector \mathbf{P} in the form of a Taylor series expansion of the applied electric field $\mathbf{E}(r, t)$:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, t) &= \mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(2)} \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \\ &+ \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(3)} \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

Taking the Fourier transform of equation (3.4) we express the polarisation vector as a function of the frequency of the incident field:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}, 2\boldsymbol{\omega}, 3\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(2)}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) \\ &+ \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(3)}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

Where $\mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega})$ is the linear polarisation vector given by equation (3.2), $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{(2)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\chi}^{(3)}$ are respectively the 2nd and 3rd order nonlinear susceptibility tensors. $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r})$ is the incident electric field vector. From Equation (3.5) we write the nonlinear polarisation vector $\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r})^3$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}, 2\boldsymbol{\omega}, 3\boldsymbol{\omega}) &= \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(2)}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) \\ &+ \varepsilon_0 \boldsymbol{\chi}^{(3)}(\boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) * \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega}) + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

³ $\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r})$ should be thought of as a perturbation compared to $\mathbf{P}^{(1)}(\mathbf{r}, \boldsymbol{\omega})$. Otherwise, the Taylor series expansion cannot be valid.

Unlike in the linear case, here the nonlinear part makes it possible to radiate a field of a certain frequency ω_n different from the initial frequency. This happens when the charged particles oscillate at the frequency ω_n and radiate constructively a wave at ω_n . This is known as the "phase matching condition".^[80,81] We illustrate this on figure 3.2.

Let us consider two waves of frequencies ω_1 and ω_2 propagating into a nonlinear medium. If we calculate the polarisation induced in the medium, we can show that depending on the type of the nonlinearity a variety of interesting phenomena arise (see figure 3.2).

Figure 3.2: Schematic representation of a few possible effects that may occur as a result to the propagation of two waves in $\chi^{(2)}$ nonlinear medium (figure (a)) and in a $\chi^{(3)}$ medium (figure (b))

The second-order term $\chi^{(2)}$, allows to achieve the second harmonic generation (SHG) (generation of a frequency of $2\omega_1$)^[75], the sum and the difference harmonic generations^[16], as well as the parametric amplification and oscillation.^[82,83]

Similarly to the $\chi^{(2)}$, the third-order term $\chi^{(3)}$ is responsible for phenomena such as, the third harmonic generation (THG)^[84], the optical Kerr effect^[70,85] which we detail in the next paragraph. It allows as well to achieve the cross phase modulation effect (XPM)^[86,87], the four-wave mixing^[88,89] and many other effects.

Optical Kerr effect The optical Kerr effect is a nonlinear optical phenomenon that induces a change of the refractive index of a material in response to an applied electric field (e.g. optical radiation). This effect is present only in media exhibiting a $\chi^{(3)}$ nonlinearity type. Let us assume a wave propagating in a $\chi^{(3)}$ nonlinear medium (see figure 3.3):

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \frac{1}{2} [E(\mathbf{r})e^{-i\omega t} + \text{c.c.}] \mathbf{e}_x \quad (3.7)$$

In this case, the possible frequencies excited along the propagation into the nonlinear medium are 3ω , $2\omega + \omega = 3\omega$, $2\omega - \omega = \omega$ and ω . In the case where 3ω is not generated, the only wave that survives at the output of the medium possesses the same frequency of the incident wave ω (see figure 3.3) and a refractive index change is being induced in the medium.

Figure 3.3: Illustration of the optical Kerr effect in $\chi^{(3)}$ -type nonlinear medium. A wave of frequency ω is sent into the nonlinear medium.

This refractive index variation is proportional to the intensity of the laser illuminating the medium. To derive it, let us consider a $\chi^{(3)}$ medium shone by an electric field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \omega)$. Writing the polarisation $\mathbf{P}(\omega)$

induced by the optical radiation yields to^[16]:

$$\begin{aligned} P(\omega) &= P^{(1)} + P^{(nl)} \approx \varepsilon_0 \chi_{xx}^{(1)} E(\omega) + \chi_{xxxx}^{(3)} E^3(\omega) \\ &\approx \varepsilon_0 \left(\chi_{xx}^{(1)} + \frac{3}{4} \chi_{xxxx}^{(3)} |E(\omega)|^2 \right) E(\omega) \\ &\approx \varepsilon_0 \chi E(\omega) \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

where χ is the total susceptibility induced in the medium. Such that $\chi = \chi_{xx}^{(1)} + \frac{3}{4} \chi_{xxxx}^{(3)} |E(\omega)|^2$. Generally, susceptibilities are complex valued quantities. So we can write χ in the form of a real and an imaginary part denoted respectively by χ' and χ'' :

$$\chi = \chi' + i\chi'' \quad (3.9)$$

In a similar way to the linear refractive index and the linear absorption coefficient of equation (3.3), we define the nonlinear refractive index n and the nonlinear absorption coefficient α induced by the optical Kerr-effect as follows:

$$n = (1 + \chi')^{1/2} = \left[\text{Re} \left(1 + \chi_{xx}^{(1)} + \frac{3}{4} \chi_{xxxx}^{(3)} |E(\omega)|^2 \right) \right] = n_0 \left[1 + \frac{3}{4n_0^2} \text{Re}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) I \right]^{1/2} \quad (3.10)$$

$$\alpha = (\chi'')^{1/2} = \left[\text{Im} \left(1 + \chi_{xx}^{(1)} + \frac{3}{4} \chi_{xxxx}^{(3)} |E(\omega)|^2 \right) \right] \frac{\omega}{c} = \alpha_0 \left[1 + \frac{3\omega}{4\alpha_0^2 c} \text{Im}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) I \right]^{1/2} \quad (3.11)$$

where $I = |E(\omega)|$ is the intensity of the wave. Making use of a Taylor series expansion since $\left| \frac{3\text{Re}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) I}{4n_0^2} \right| \ll 1$ and $\left| \frac{3\omega \text{Im}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) I}{4\alpha_0^2 c} \right| \ll 1$, we give the expressions of the nonlinear refractive index and the absorption coefficient:

$$n \approx n_0 + \frac{3}{8n_0} \text{Re}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) |E(\omega)|^2 = n_0 + n_2 I \quad (3.12a)$$

$$\alpha \approx \alpha_0 + \frac{3\omega}{8\alpha_0 c} \text{Im}(\chi_{xxxx}^{(3)}) |E(\omega)|^2 = \alpha_0 + \alpha_2 I, \quad (3.12b)$$

where n_2 and α_2 are respectively called the nonlinear (Kerr) coefficient and the two-photons absorption coefficient. The order of magnitude of the nonlinear coefficient n_2 is very small (e.g. $n_2 = 10^{-20} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{W}^{-1}$ in fused silica). Therefore, to get significant values of the refractive index variation $n_2 I$, one shall use pulsed lasers allowing to provide intensities of the order of $10^{16} \text{ W} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$.

Thanks to the intensity-dependent refractive index, the optical Kerr effect manifests itself temporally in the self-phase modulation effect (SPM) and spatially in the self-focusing effect. In the next paragraph, we provide a brief description of the self-phase modulation effect and its impact on the wave propagation.

Self-phase modulation Self-phase modulation (SPM) is a nonlinear optical phenomenon that results from light-matter interaction. This effect is considered as one manifestation of the intensity-dependent refractive index, suchlike the Kerr effect. The phenomenon was discovered within the frame of ultrashort pulses propagating in nonlinear media.^[90,91]

A pulse propagating in a nonlinear $\chi^{(3)}$ -type medium induces a variation of the refractive index Δn . This latter yields a phase shift in the propagating pulse which in turn induces a change in the pulse's spectrum. In

Self-phase modulation

Figure 3.4: Illustration of the self-phase modulation (SPM) effect. A Gaussian temporal pulse is sent through a $\chi^{(3)}$ nonlinear medium along the z -axis. Experiencing the SPM, the temporal pulse shrinks during the propagation, while the frequency spectrum broadens.

figure 3.4 we illustrate a pulse propagating into a $\chi^{(3)}$ nonlinear medium and experiencing the SPM effect.

The first observation of the SPM effect dates back to 1967, found by Shimizu^[71], in his article, he reported the broadening of the frequency spectrum of a short light pulse propagating in CS_2 -filled cell. Few years after, SPM was observed in solid media and glasses with the use of picosecond laser type.^[92] The spectral broadening of the picosecond pulse was observed in calcite, sodium chloride and several glasses. Later on, Ippen and co-workers reported the first observation of SPM in a CS_2 -filled fibre. This work was thereafter succeeded in a systematic study of the SPM in silica-core fibre.^[91]

To understand the SPM effect, let us assume a Gaussian pulse with a central frequency ω_0 propagating in a Kerr-type nonlinear medium along the z -axis (see Fig. 3.4):

$$I(t) = I_0 e^{-t^2/\tau^2}, \quad (3.13)$$

where I_0 is the intensity at $t = 0$ and τ is the width of the pulse. The propagation of the pulse (eq. (3.13)) produces a time varying refractive index:

$$n(I) = n_0 + n_2 I_0 e^{-t^2/\tau^2} \quad (3.14)$$

Thus, since the phase of the propagating pulse depends on the refractive index, it can be expressed as follows:

$$\varphi(t) = \omega_0 t - kz = \omega_0 t - k_0 n(I(t)) z \quad (3.15)$$

where k_0 is the wave number in vacuum. This equation shows that the variation of the refractive index induces a shift in the instantaneous phase of the pulse. Thus a frequency shift occurs along the propagation of the pulse. It is given by:

$$\omega(t) = \omega_0 + \frac{2k_0 n_2 z I_0}{\tau^2} e^{-t^2/\tau^2} \quad (3.16)$$

The SPM effect acts on the pulse by generating extra frequencies along the propagation into the nonlinear medium. This effect induces the broadening of the frequency spectrum of the pulse. In the field of ultra-short pulses, SPM finds many applications suchlike, the supercontinuum generation^[93], the temporal pulse

compression^[94] and the spectral pulse compression^[95], to cite a few.

In this paragraph we have given a description of the self-phase modulation in the temporal frame, in our experiment, we will use the self-phase modulation effect but in the spatial frame. Therefore, instead of a Gaussian pulse, we will use a Gaussian beam to characterise the nonlinear medium. This is described in section 3.3.

To complete the short introduction to nonlinear optics, we suggest in the next paragraph to derive the equation that describes the propagation of wave in a nonlinear medium.

Figure 3.5: illustration of a wave propagating into a nonlinear medium along the z -axis

Propagation of a wave in a nonlinear isotropic medium Let us consider a wave propagating into a nonlinear dielectric medium of permittivity ϵ and a permeability $\mu = 1$ (non-magnetic medium) in which there is no charge and current (see figure 3.5). The propagation is described by Maxwell's equations of electromagnetism:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = 0, \quad (3.17a)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0, \quad (3.17b)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t}, \quad (3.17c)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t}. \quad (3.17d)$$

Where \mathbf{E} is the electric field vector. \mathbf{B} and \mathbf{H} represent the magnetic field vectors. They are related by the following expression $\mathbf{H} = \mu_0 \mathbf{B}$. The displacement vector \mathbf{D} can be expressed as a function of the incident field \mathbf{E} and the polarisation \mathbf{P} vectors by:

$$\mathbf{D} = \epsilon \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P} \quad (3.18)$$

The wave equation of the electric field is found by applying the curl operator on the equation (3.17c):

$$\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{P}}{\partial t^2} \quad (3.19)$$

Knowing from vector analysis that $\nabla \times \nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \nabla(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}) - \nabla^2 \mathbf{E}$, the wave equation for a source-free medium reads:

$$\nabla^2 \mathbf{E} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{E}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{P}}{\partial t^2} \quad (3.20)$$

The polarisation field \mathbf{P} comprises the linear \mathbf{P}^l and the nonlinear part \mathbf{P}^{nl} .

Knowing that the z -axis is the propagation direction (see figure 3.5), we know that the equation of propagation (eq. (3.20)) admits a particular solution having the form of a monochromatic plane wave:

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}, t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})e^{i(\omega t - \mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{z})}, \quad (3.21)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})$ is the complex amplitude of the wave. $\mathbf{r} = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}\hat{\mathbf{e}}_r$ is the transverse (radial) coordinate and $\mathbf{k} = k\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z = (2\pi/\lambda)\hat{\mathbf{e}}_z$ is the wave vector, where λ is its wavelength.

Injecting this particular solution (eq. (3.21)) in the propagation equation (3.20) results in the following equation of the complex amplitude $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})$:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) + 2ik\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) + \nabla_{x,y}^2\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = -\frac{\omega^2}{\epsilon_0 c^2}\mathbf{P}^{nl}(\mathbf{r}, t) \quad (3.22)$$

Equation (3.22) is the wave equation with an additional nonlinear source term $\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}$. We can simplify this equation by assuming that the complex amplitude varies slowly as a function of z over scales in the order of the wavelength λ (paraxial approximation). Therefore, we can neglect the second derivative of the complex amplitude $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})$ compared to its first derivative with respect to the distance of propagation z and we write:

$$\left| \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) \right| \ll \left| k\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) \right| \quad (3.23)$$

This inequality is known as the "slowly varying envelop approximation". Within the frame of this approximation and assuming that the nonlinear source term $\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}$ is expressed by:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r})e^{-i\omega t} + \text{c.c.}, \quad (3.24)$$

the equation (3.22) simplifies to:

$$2ik\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) + \nabla_{x,y}^2\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = -\frac{\omega^2}{\epsilon_0 c^2}\mathbf{P}^{nl}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) \quad (3.25)$$

The above equation is known as the nonlinear propagation equation under the paraxial approximation (slowly varying envelop approximation). It describes the variation of the wave's complex amplitude regarding the transverse coordinate \mathbf{r} along with its propagation in the z direction. The first term $\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})$ represents the evolution of the wave envelope, the term $\nabla_{x,y}^2\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})$ represents the term of the diffraction effect of the complex amplitude and the R.H.S term is the nonlinear one. Knowing that the nonlinear polarisation \mathbf{P}^{nl} in a Kerr-type medium can be calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{P}^{(nl)}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = 2n_0\frac{3}{8n_0}\text{Re}(\chi^{(3)})|\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z})|^2\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = 2n_0n_2I\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) \quad (3.26)$$

Thus substituting equation 3.26 in the nonlinear propagation equation 3.25 yields to:

$$i\frac{\partial}{\partial z}\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) + \frac{1}{2k}\nabla_{x,y}^2\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) = -kn_2I\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{z}) \quad (3.27)$$

Eq. 3.27 is the nonlinear propagation equation in a nonlinear Kerr medium.

To sum up, in the past section, we provided a short introduction to nonlinear optics, stressing few phenomena that concern our work (optical Kerr effect and SPM). Also we gave a description of a wave propagating in a nonlinear medium. We suggest in the next section to describe the photorefractive nonlinearity.

3.2 Photorefractive nonlinear effect

3.2.1 Introduction to the photorefractive effect

The photorefractive effect is a nonlinear optical phenomenon that consists in the spatial variation of the refractive index of a medium through the intensity distribution of a laser beam. Firstly discovered in 1966 by Ashkin and co-workers^[96], the photorefractive effect was found through the observation of the wavefront distortion of a laser beam propagating into an electro-optic medium⁴. Since then, the photorefractive effect was found in almost all electro-optic crystals, namely, Strontium Barium Niobate (SBN), Lithium Niobate (LiNbO₃), Potassium Tantalate Niobate (KTN), Barium Titanate (BaTiO₃), Potassium Niobate (KNbO₃), Bismuth Germanate Oxide (BGO), Gallium Arsenide (GaAs), etc.^[97]

Photorefractive media⁵ were used mainly in applications related to volume holographic data storage.^[98] Afterwards the technique was enhanced using multiplexing and encoding.^[99] The photorefractive effect was also used to achieve optical images convolutions and correlations^[100] as well as in applications like associative memories allowing to rebuild a stored optical image from a partial input.^[101] In addition to the holographic effect, a two-wave mixing phenomenon can take place when two coherent beams propagate and interfere into a photorefractive medium giving birth to the formation of a refractive index grating. This grating might be shifted with respect to the intensity pattern which gives rise to the property of nonreciprocal energy transfer. The latter property can be exploited in many applications such as photorefractive resonators^[102], laser beam clean-up^[103], in image processing context, suchlike, self-pumped phase conjugators^[104], optical neural networks^[99,105] and image amplification.^[106] In a more recent literature, photorefractive media were used for the observation of optical discrete solitons^[107,108], for the study of quasicrystals^[109] and in graphene-like structures.^[110,111] Also, the photorefractive nonlinearity was employed to show weak or transverse localisation in disordered lattices^[112,113] as well as to study the quantum hydrodynamical aspects of light.^[60,61] For more details about photorefractive applications we provide the reader with some interesting references.^[97,114,115] Let us now take a look on the principle of the photorefractive effect.

Principle of photorefractive effect In this paragraph we give briefly the mechanisms responsible for the occurrence of the photorefractive effect. In later subsections, we will provide the theory that describes the photorefractive effect focusing our analysis on the Strontium Barium Niobate SBN crystal.^[115]

Generally, crystals contain impurities that form an energy level localised between the valence and conduction bands. A laser beam shone onto a photorefractive medium induces the excitation of electrons (or holes) to the conduction band depending on the energy provided by the laser source. These excited charge carriers are displaced because of three factors:

- First because of diffusion, which occurs through the *thermal mobility* of charges in which the displacement is oriented from the regions of higher density charges to regions of lower density.
- The second factor is the action of an applied *external electric field*, giving rise to a drift action experienced by the charge carriers.

⁴An electro-optic medium refers to any material that exhibits the Pockels (electro-optic) effect. The latter represents the change of the refractive index of a material through the application of a dc or a low-frequency electric fields.

⁵Note that nowadays photorefractive media are not used that much in applied physics. Nevertheless, in fundamental physics research activities are still conducted in few photorefractive media.

- The third factor is the displacement of charges because of the photovoltaic effect; the spatial intensity of light illuminating the medium creates an internal electric field. The latter induces a drift of electrons (or holes). The peculiarity about the photovoltaic effect is that the excited particles migrate in a specific direction determined by the polar axis of the crystal.

These excited electrons (or holes) can recombine with the empty donors (or acceptors) resulting in the creation of a charge distribution inside the medium inducing a modulation of the spatial electric charge density. Hence, an internal electric field is created in the bulk of the photorefractive medium called the "space charge electric field", usually denoted by \mathbf{E}_{sc} (see Figure 3.6). The latter induces through the Pockels effect a variation of the refractive index of the medium.

It is worth mentioning that the induced refractive index modulation might (or not) be shifted regarding the intensity distribution of the laser beam. This depends on the leading phenomenon that induces the migration of charge carriers, namely, diffusion or drift (see figure 3.6). Notice that we neglect the photovoltaic effect because drift and diffusion effects are generally larger than the photovoltaic effect.

Figure 3.6 displays the variation of the refractive index Δn in a 1-dimensional space that occurs in a photorefractive medium in the case of a drift dominating process presented in the left column of the figure and in the case where the diffusion process dominates displayed on the right column of the figure.

We start from a Gaussian profile beam represented in 1-D space in Fig.3.6(a) and (b). The drift-ruled process represents the situation when an external static electric field \mathbf{E}_{ext} is being applied on the medium. In this case electrons or holes are photo-excited into the conduction band through absorption of photons. Experiencing an external electric field charge carriers are displaced in a well-defined direction yielding an asymmetric density of charges $\rho(x)$ (Fig.3.6.(c)). Integrating the obtained density of charges $\rho(x)$ allows to retrieve the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} that is created in the photorefractive medium. We display \mathbf{E}_{sc} for the drift dominated process in Fig.3.6.(e). Finally, thanks to the Pockels effect a spatial modulation of the refractive Δn index arises in the medium. It is displayed in Fig.3.6.(g). Here, we present a positive variation of the refractive index (self-focusing regime) $\Delta n > 0$ which is defined by the orientation of the applied static field. Redirecting the external field in the opposite direction shall give the opposite effect which is negative variation of the refractive index (self-defocusing regime).

In the diffusion-ruled process (displayed on the right column of Fig.3.6), the excited electrons or holes are symmetrically diffused to regions of low intensity distributions because of the thermal effect. This diffusion gives birth to a symmetric distribution of the charge density $\rho(x)$ Fig.3.6.(d). Performing an integration of the charge density gives an asymmetric distribution of the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} Fig.3.6.(f). Hence, the refractive index change occurring through the Pockels effect has either an asymmetric distribution.

In a real physical system, both processes (drift, diffusion) cannot be separated from one another. However, depending on the external conditions, we can foster individually one of the effects. Applying an external static electric field allows a higher contribution of the drift process such that diffusion can be neglected. In contrast, an increase in the temperature of the photorefractive medium allows the diffusion process to dominate.

Figure 3.6: Figure of the refractive index change Δn taking place because of the charge carrier displacement in the cases of drift and diffusion dominated processes. Panels (a) and (b) represent the intensity distribution of the laser beam illuminating the photorefractive medium. (c) and (d) are the densities of charges ρ . (e) and (f) display the induced space charge field. (g) and (h) are the spatial variation of the refractive index. Adapted from.^[115]

3.2.2 Refractive index modulation via the photorefractive effect

In this subsection we give the physical model commonly used to describe the refractive index change due to the photorefractive nonlinearity. We start from the electro-optic effect (Pockels effect) since it is the one responsible for the refractive index variation in photorefractive media.

Electro-optic (Pockels) effect The electro-optic effect is a phenomenon that induces a change in the refractive index of a material as a response to an applied static (or low-frequency) electric field.^[116] Many authors generalise the phenomenon and regard it as the change of the material's optical properties including the change of the absorption coefficient (Stark effect).^[117] However, in this manuscript, we only mean the first definition.

A medium that exhibits the Pockels effect is called an electro-optic material. This phenomenon exists only in materials that are noncentrosymmetric.⁶ ^[114] Therefore, some authors interpret and describe it using the second-order nonlinear susceptibility term.^[16] However, a particular description was devoted to the electro-optic effect based on the definition of the so-called electro-optic tensor. Let us consider a laser

⁶A centrosymmetric crystal is a medium that possesses inversion symmetry, which means the possibility of moving an atom from a position r to a position $-r$ regarding the center of inversion. This property implies that $\chi^{(2)} = 0$

beam propagating along the z -axis into an electro-optic crystal in which we introduce a static external field \mathbf{E}_{ext} oriented along the x -axis (see figure 3.7).

Figure 3.7: Illustration of a beam propagating in an electro-optic medium of a thickness d along the z direction. An external electric field is being applied along the x -axis to render the electro-optic effect.

To describe the electro-optic effect, we usually consider the impermeability tensor denoted by η which by definition, is the inverse of the permeability tensor ε . We assume that the impermeability coefficients can be expressed as a power series in the strength of the applied static electric field and we write:

$$\delta\eta_{ij} = \delta\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right)_{ij} = \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \mathbf{r}_{ijk} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{k}} + \sum_{\mathbf{k}} \sum_{\mathbf{m}} \mathbf{s}_{ijkm} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{k}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{m}} + \dots \quad (3.28)$$

where $\mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{k}}$, $\mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{m}}$ are the components of the applied static electric field. The tensors \mathbf{r}_{ijk} , \mathbf{s}_{ijkm} are respectively the linear and the quadratic electro-optic tensors and n is the refractive index of the medium. It is worth reminding that the tensors \mathbf{r}_{ijk} is not zero because all the electro-optic media are noncentrosymmetric. In the following, we neglect the quadratic contribution \mathbf{s}_{ijkm} , because only the linear part \mathbf{r}_{ijk} is responsible for the Pockels effect. We should note in the case of a photorefractive medium that we will have the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} defined earlier instead of only the external static electric field $\mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{k}}$.

From the definition of the impermeability $\eta = 1/\varepsilon$, one can write the variation of the dielectric tensor $\delta\varepsilon$ as a function of the impermeability variation tensor $\delta\eta$ ^[114]:

$$\delta\varepsilon = -\varepsilon\delta\eta\varepsilon \quad (3.29)$$

The electro-optic tensor \mathbf{r}_{ijk} is a tensor of rank 3 that comprises 27 elements. For a lossless non-active medium the permeability ε and the impermeability η tensors are real and symmetric. Subsequently, the electro-optic tensor must be symmetric and real valued either. Therefore, the first 2 indices of the electro-optic tensor are interchangeable. This property allows to reduce the number of elements of the electro-optic tensor to 18 elements. And we can write:

$$r_{ijk} = r_{jik} \quad (3.30)$$

Thus, one can use the so-called contracted indices^[16,114] allowing to abbreviate the notations of the electro-optic coefficients. We represent indices (i, j) by one index l as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} r_{1k} &= r_{11k}, & r_{2k} &= r_{22k}, & r_{3k} &= r_{33k}, \\ r_{4k} &= r_{23k} = r_{32k}, & r_{5k} &= r_{13k} = r_{31k}, \\ r_{6k} &= r_{12k} = r_{21k}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

The indices (i, j, k) take values from 1 to 3 to refer to the coordinates axis (x, y, z) and the contracted index l takes values from 1 to 6. Finally, after considering the contracted notation, we express the variation of $(1/n^2)$ and the impermeability tensor η (eq. (3.28)) as follows:

$$\delta\eta_l = \delta\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right)_l = \sum_k r_{lk} \mathbf{E}_k \quad (3.32)$$

The last equation allows us to derive the expression of the refractive index variation in a photorefractive medium. Particularly the one of the SBN crystal. Before doing so, we suggest in the next paragraph to introduce the SBN crystal and its characteristics.

Properties of the SBN crystal The Strontium Barium Niobate is the chemical compound referred by: $\text{Sr}_x\text{Ba}_{1-x}\text{Nb}_2\text{O}_6$, where x is the quantity of the Strontium present in the compound. Usually denoted by SBN, it is a ferroelectric material with tetragonal tungsten bronze compounds without volatile elements. This material is commonly used in single crystal form in electro-optics, acousto-optics applications and in photorefractive optics field.

There are three techniques used to grow the SBN crystal, known as Bridgman^[118], Stepanov^[119] and the Czochralski^[120] techniques. The latter technique is the most common one. For whom might be interested to know more about these techniques, a detailed report is given by Ulex and co-workers.^[121] We display in Fig. 3.8 the crystalline structure of the SBN crystal at room temperature for the compositions $x = 0.61$ ^[122] and $x = 0.75$.^[123]

Figure 3.8: Scheme of the crystalline structure of the SBN crystal in room temperature conditions. a and b represent the basis of the reciprocal lattice vectors.

Both Sr and Br atoms can occupy the A_2 sites while the A_1 positions can only be occupied by the Sr atom. The green octahedrons in the figure represent the atoms of Nb_2O_6 .

At room temperature, the SBN crystal is uniaxial. It has two indices of refraction along two different directions, ordinary index n_o and the extraordinary index n_e . The birefringence $\Delta n = n_e - n_o$ of the SBN has a negative value ($\Delta n < 0$). The SBN crystal belongs to the point symmetry group $4mm$. This allows to reduce the number of the independent elements of the electro-optic tensor. Therefore the electro-optic

Table 3.1: Summary table of the characteristics of the SBN:61 crystal

Physical quantity	Value	Ref.
Refractive indices	$n_e = 2.36$	[114]
(Measured at $\lambda = 633$ nm)	$n_o = 2.4$	[114]
Electro-optic coefficients	$r_{33} = 235$ pm/V	[125]
	$r_{13} = 47$ pm/V	[125]
Dielectric constant	$\epsilon_{33} = 800$	[114]
Phase transition temperature	$T_c = 81$ °C	[126]

tensor $(\mathbf{r}_{lk})_{\text{SBN}}$ of the SBN is expressed as follows:

$$(\mathbf{r}_{lk})_{\text{SBN}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & r_{13} \\ 0 & 0 & r_{13} \\ 0 & 0 & r_{33} \\ 0 & r_{42} & 0 \\ r_{42} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.33)$$

We give in table 3.1 few characteristics of the crystal we used in the experiments. It is an SBN:61 crystal doped with Cerium (Ce) rare-earth (0.02%) to enhance its photoconductivity, thus, its photorefractive sensitivity.^[124]

The reasons for which we have chosen the SBN photorefractive crystal are:

- This medium offers the possibility to get nonlinear effects at lower laser's intensity values of the order $I \approx 10^2$ mW.cm⁻². This makes it possible to use only continuous (CW) laser sources.
- Its high electro-optic coefficient r_{33} allows to reach nonlinear refractive index change of the order of $\Delta n \approx 10^{-4}$.
- The possibility to induce an erasable refractive index pattern into this photorefractive medium is a great advantage of this crystal type.

Effective electro-optic coefficient of the SBN To derive the expression of the refractive index change Δn , let us consider an SBN crystal oriented as follows: the optical axis (*c*-axis) is directed along the *z*-axis, along which a static electric field \mathbf{E}_{ext} is being applied. Besides this, we send through the photorefractive crystal along the *y*-axis an optical wave having a polarisation unit vector \mathbf{p} within the (*x, z*)-plan (see Fig.3.9).

We have already pointed out that the electric field responsible for the refractive index variation in a photorefractive crystal is the so-called \mathbf{E}_{sc} . It is induced on the one hand through the intensity distribution

Figure 3.9: Scheme of the propagation of a laser beam into the SBN crystal. The y -axis is the propagation direction. An external field is applied on the crystal along the z -axis which is the direction of the c -axis.

of the laser beam and on the other hand through the applied static field \mathbf{E}_{ext} . We assume that the space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} is oriented along the z -axis as well and we give:

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ E_{\text{sc}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.34)$$

The expression of the refractive index variation Δn in a photorefractive medium can be calculated using the following formula:

$$\Delta n = \mathbf{p}^T \delta(1/n^2) \mathbf{p}, \quad (3.35)$$

where \mathbf{p} and \mathbf{p}^T are respectively the light polarisation unit vector and its transpose. We assume that the wave is polarised linearly with an angle θ with respect to the x -axis (see Fig. 3.9). Therefore the polarisation vector is given by:

$$\mathbf{p} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta) \\ 0 \\ \sin(\theta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.36)$$

According to equation (3.32) we can calculate the tensor of the variation of $1/n^2$ by multiplying the electro-optic tensor $(\mathbf{r}_{\text{lk}})_{\text{SBN}}$ (eq (3.33)) by the space charge field vector \mathbf{E}_{sc} (eq. (3.34)). The result to this operation $\delta(\frac{1}{n^2})$ is given as follows:

$$\delta\left(\frac{1}{n^2}\right) = \delta\eta = \begin{bmatrix} r_{13}E_{\text{sc}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r_{13}E_{\text{sc}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & r_{33}E_{\text{sc}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.37)$$

Therefore, making use of equation (3.35) we find the variation of the refractive index Δn of the SBN crystal:

$$\Delta n_{\text{SBN}} = -\frac{1}{2}n_e^3 [r_{13} \cos^2(\theta) + r_{33} \sin^2(\theta)] E_{\text{sc}}, \quad (3.38)$$

which can be expressed as a function of an effective electro-optic coefficient denoted by r_{eff} :

$$\Delta n_{\text{SBN}} = -\frac{1}{2}n_e^3 r_{\text{eff}} E_{\text{sc}}, \quad (3.39)$$

with r_{eff} equals to:

$$r_{\text{eff}} = r_{13} \cos^2(\theta) + r_{33} \sin^2(\theta) \quad (3.40)$$

To maximise the variation of the refractive index Δn_{SBN} , we need to maximise the effective electro-optic coefficient r_{eff} . To do so, we set the polarisation direction parallel to the c -axis of the crystal $\theta = \pi/2$. This is because the electro-optic coefficient r_{33} is very large regarding r_{13} ^[127] ($r_{33} \gg r_{13}$) (see table 3.1).

In order not to be confused, we remind in this paragraph, that the c -axis of the crystal was oriented along the z direction. However, in Section 3.3 we consider a crystal such that its c -axis is parallel to the x -axis and the external static field is applied along the x -axis, while the propagation direction becomes the z -axis.

So far, the expression of the refractive index variation eq. (3.39) is still not determined completely because \mathbf{E}_{sc} is not defined yet. Therefore, to fully establish the expression of the nonlinear refractive index variation in a photorefractive medium, we suggest in the next subsections to give in detail the model that describes the expression of the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} .

3.2.3 Description of E_{sc} in the band transport model

The description of the mechanisms responsible for the photorefractive effect considers the band transport theory. The commonly used model to describe most of photorefractive phenomena was developed by Kukhtarev and co-workers.^[128] In this model, it is assumed that photorefractive crystals contain impurities (e.g. Ce^{3+} for a Cerium doped crystal). To simplify the description, we suppose that the impurities donor occupy the same energy level localised in the band gap of the material and are identical.

The excited particles undergo a migration process until they recombine with the empty donors (see Fig. 3.10). This charge separation results in the creation of the space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} .

Figure 3.10: Illustration of the energy band model for the photorefractive effect suggested by Kukhtarev et al. N_d and N_d^+ are respectively the density of unionised and ionised donors. A photon $\hbar\omega$ is being absorbed by an electron. G and R denotes respectively the excitation and the recombination rates. n_{e-} is the density of electron that is displaced within the crystal.

There is another model developed by Hall and co-workers^[129–131] called the "hopping" model. This latter can be considered as a special case of the band transport model. It suggests that carrier migration occurs through light induced hopping from a filled donor site to an empty trap. This model becomes valid when free charges density n_{e^-} has a short lifetime. In this case, the band transport theory supposes that the density of free charges n_{e^-} is negligible regarding the density of ionised donors N_d^+ . Therefore, only the redistribution of charges between traps (hopping charges) contributes to the creation of the space charge field. This model can be appropriate sometimes, (e.g. the case of a large energy band gap). Even though this model has a statistical basis^[132] it provides the same expression of the space charge field regarding Kukhtarev's model.

The Kukhtarev and the hopping models have explained the mechanisms behind the photorefractive effect. However, both of which assume that traps have simple distributions, which is not the case in reality. Since we possess a Cerium doped SBN crystal then the energy gap in the band transport model is reduced. Therefore, it is more appropriate to consider Kukhtarev's model for describing the formation of the space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} . In this manuscript, we will restrict our description to only the model of Kukhtarev.

Kukhtarev's description of the photorefractive effect We would like to point out that in this paragraph as well as in the next subsection 3.2.4, we use the description developed by Denz and co-workers^[115] to determine the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} .

As we explained before, the creation of the space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} in a photorefractive medium is due to the migration of both charge carriers (electrons and holes). However, for the sake of simplicity, the model of Kukhtarev assumes that only one type of charge carriers creates the space charge field supposed to be the electron. Let us consider a photorefractive medium containing N_d^0 donors per unit volume. We know from the model that an impurity (dopant) is excited from the donor level to the conduction band through illumination and/or through temperature. We denote by n_{e^-} the electron density in the conduction band, N_d^+ and N_d the densities of ionised donors and unionised donors (see Fig. 3.10). So, the total density of donors N_d^0 equals to the sum of densities of ionised and unionised donors $N_d^+ + N_d = N_d^0$. However, the density of electrons n_{e^-} is not equal to the density of ionised donors N_d^+ , this is because few number of excited electron may go to the acceptor level or they may be led to regions not electrically neutral.

The variation of the density of ionised donors N_d^+ as a function of time t is expressed through the difference of two competing effects. The first effect is the generation of electron-hole pairs and the second is their recombination. G denotes the rate of electron generation, it is proportional to the density of unionised donors and to the probabilities of photoexcitation and thermal excitation. As for the recombination rate R , it is proportional to the density of electrons of the conduction band and to the density of ionised donors. We express these rates by the following formula:

$$G = (sI + \beta_{th})(N_d^0 - N_d^+) = \beta_{th}(I/I_{sat} + 1)(N_d^0 - N_d^+), \quad (3.41a)$$

$$R = \zeta N_d^+ n_{e^-} \quad (3.41b)$$

where β_{th} , s and ζ are respectively coefficients of the thermal excitation, the photoinduced excitation, and the linear recombination. I is the intensity of the electromagnetic radiation; I_{sat} is called the saturation intensity, it represents the ratio of the thermal excitation coefficient to the photoinduced excitation coefficient β_{th}/s . This crucial quantity contributes in the control of the photorefractive nonlinear effect. We can experimentally achieve this by illuminating the crystal with an incoherent light, allowing an amplification of the thermal coefficient β_{th} .

In the literature of photorefractive optics, we can find also another notation called the "dark intensity". This latter refers to the ratio of the saturation intensity to the peak intensity of the laser beam, $I_d = I_{\text{sat}}/I_0$. In the following of this manuscript, we will be using only the saturation intensity designation and we denote by $\tilde{I} = I/I_{\text{sat}}$.

Expressing the change of the ionised donor density as a function of time gives:

$$\frac{\partial N_d^+}{\partial t} = G - R = \beta_{\text{th}}(\tilde{I} + 1)(N_d^0 - N_d^+) - \zeta N_d^+ n_{e^-} \quad (3.42)$$

Knowing that the density of electrons n_{e^-} increases because of the ionisation and/or because of the electron flow into neutral regions, one expresses the variation of the electron density with respect to time as:

$$\frac{\partial n_{e^-}}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial N_d^+}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{e} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}, \quad (3.43)$$

where e is the electron charge and \mathbf{j} is the vector density of current owing to the migration of electrons in the conduction band. It is related to the density of charges by the continuity equation $\partial \rho / \partial t = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}$. Assuming that all acceptors are ionised, we give the density of charges as a function of densities of ionised donors N_d^+ , acceptors N_a and the density of electrons n_{e^-} . Therefore, $\rho = e(N_d^+ - N_a - n_{e^-})$. The current flow \mathbf{j} is described by the following equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{j} &= \mathbf{j}_{\text{diffusion}} + \mathbf{j}_{\text{drift}} + \mathbf{j}_{\text{photovoltaic}} \\ &= e\mu n_{e^-} \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} + eD \nabla n_{e^-} + \mathbf{j}_{\text{photovoltaic}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.44)$$

where $D = \mu k_B T / e$ and μ are respectively Einstein's diffusion coefficient and the charge mobility, T is the absolute temperature, k_B is the Boltzmann constant and $\mathbf{j}_{\text{photovoltaic}}$ is the current density induced by the photovoltaic effect.

According to Maxwell's electrodynamics equations, the resulting internal field (space charge electric field) \mathbf{E}_{sc} shall satisfy Poisson's equation:

$$\epsilon_0 \epsilon \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = e(N_d^+ - N_a - n_{e^-}), \quad (3.45)$$

where ϵ is the dielectric constant of the crystal and ϵ_0 is the permittivity of vacuum.

The above equation expresses the variation of the space charge electric field as a function of the densities of the charge carriers. This equation (eq. (3.45)) combined with equations (3.42) and (3.44) represent the basis equations of Kukhtarev's model. This system of equations describes the propagation of an electromagnetic wave in a photorefractive medium and takes into account all the mechanisms behind the occurrence of the photorefractive effect.

3.2.4 The isotropic and the anisotropic derivation of \mathbf{E}_{sc}

In this section, we derive the expression of the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} using two different approaches. The first approach suggested by Christodoulides and co-workers^[133] is called the isotropic approach. This one assumes that the space charge electric field is isotropic within the bulk of the crystal, while the second one known as the anisotropic approach^[134] deals with an anisotropic space charge electric field.

We assume for both approaches that the system is time-independent (steady-state $\partial/\partial t = 0$). This condition is valid as long as we send a continuous laser beam into the photorefractive medium (or the width of the pulse should be greater than the recombination time of the charge carriers in the order of few μs ^[132]). We neglect as well the photovoltaic effect ($\mathbf{j}_{\text{photovoltaic}} = \mathbf{0}$) because the drift and the diffusion effects are much larger than the photovoltaic one.

We assume a wave propagating into a photorefractive medium along the z direction and an external electric field is being applied along the x -axis parallel to the optical axis of the crystal (c -axis).

Isotropic approximation To simplify the situation we consider a geometry of $(1 + 1)$ -dimension, since we assumed an isotropic space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} . And the laser beam is quasi-homogeneous which means that the width of the beam is very large regarding the characteristic scale of the electric field determined by the Debye wavenumber.^[115] Besides this, we assume that the density of electrons n_{e^-} is negligible regarding the densities of acceptors N_a and ionised donors N_d^+ . Therefore, in these conditions, we find from equation (3.45) an expression of ionised donors N_d^+ :

$$\epsilon_0 \epsilon \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = e(N_d^+ - N_a - n_{e^-}) \quad \Rightarrow \quad N_d^+ \approx N_a \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{e N_a} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} \right) \quad (3.46)$$

Using equation (3.42) and by employing the previous formula (eq. (3.46)) one can establish an expression of the electron density n_{e^-} . The steady-state assumption implies a zero variation of the ionised donors as a function of time. Hence, the expression of n_{e^-} reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial N_d^+}{\partial t} &= \beta_{\text{th}}(\tilde{I} + 1)(N_d^0 - N_d^+) - \zeta N_d^+ n_{e^-} = 0 \\ \Rightarrow n_{e^-} &= \frac{\beta_{\text{th}}}{\zeta N_d^+} (\tilde{I} + 1)(N_d^0 - N_d^+) \end{aligned} \quad (3.47)$$

Replacing in the expression of n_{e^-} of the equation (3.47) the density of ionised donors N_d^+ yields to an expression of the free charge n_{e^-} :

$$n_{e^-} = \frac{\beta_{\text{th}}(N_d^0 - N_a)}{\zeta N_a} (\tilde{I} + 1) \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{e N_a} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.48)$$

Let us now assume that the intensity of the laser beam \tilde{I} in asymptotic regions is constant $\tilde{I}((x, y) \rightarrow \infty, z) = \tilde{I}_\infty$. This assumption is valid because the diameter of the laser beam is very small compared to the transverse dimensions of the nonlinear medium. Therefore, the induced space charge electric field \mathbf{E}_{sc} in these regions depends only on the applied static electric field \mathbf{E}_{ext} and we write $\mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}}(x \rightarrow \infty) = \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}} = (V/d)\mathbf{e}_x$, where V is the applied voltage and d is the width of the photorefractive crystal.

The free electron density in asymptotic regions n_∞ is found by taking the limits of the spatial coordinates $(x, y) \rightarrow \infty$ of equation (3.48). Since in asymptotic regions the space charge electric field is constant, then its spatial derivative is zero $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = 0$. This yields:

$$n_e((x, y) \rightarrow \infty) = n_\infty = \beta_{\text{th}}(1 + \tilde{I}_\infty)(N_d^0 - N_a)/\zeta N_a \quad (3.49)$$

Therefore, using the steady-state assumption and the equation (3.43) one finds a simplified expression of the space charge field \mathbf{E}_{sc} . Since $\frac{\partial n_{e^-}}{\partial t} = 0$ and $\frac{\partial N_d^+}{\partial t} = 0$, then eq. (3.43) allows to deduce that $\nabla \mathbf{j} = 0$. Therefore, integrating $\nabla \mathbf{j} = 0$ from 0 to ∞ ($\int_0^\infty \nabla \mathbf{j} = 0$) of the equation (3.44) we give \mathbf{E}_{sc} :

$$\mathbf{E}_{\text{sc}} = \frac{n_\infty \mathbf{E}_{\text{ext}}}{n_{e^-}} - \frac{k_B T}{e n_{e^-}} \nabla n_{e^-} \quad (3.50)$$

Replacing n_{e^-} and n_∞ in equation (3.50) gives the expression of \mathbf{E}_{sc} as a function of the external static electric field \mathbf{E}_{ext} , the intensity of the laser illuminating the medium I and also as a function of the second and first order spatial derivatives ($\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{sc}$, $\nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_{sc}$).

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{E}_{sc} = & \mathbf{E}_{ext} \frac{I_\infty + 1}{I + 1} \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{e N_a} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{sc} \right) - \frac{k_B T}{e} \frac{\nabla \tilde{I}}{\tilde{I} + 1} \\ & + \frac{k_B T}{e} \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{e N_a} \left(1 + \frac{\epsilon_0 \epsilon}{e N_a} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{sc} \right)^{-1} \nabla^2 \mathbf{E}_{sc} \end{aligned} \quad (3.51)$$

Assuming that the intensity of the laser beam varies slowly with respect to the spatial coordinates $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_{sc} \approx 0$ and that the application of the external electric field \mathbf{E}_{ext} makes the drift process dominant over the diffusion one, then we can neglect the diffusion parameter $k_B T/e$. Therefore, the expression of the space charge field can be simplified as follows:

$$\mathbf{E}_{sc} \approx \mathbf{E}_{ext} \frac{\tilde{I}_\infty + 1}{\tilde{I} + 1} \quad (3.52)$$

Thus, replacing the expression of \mathbf{E}_{sc} eq. (3.52) in the equation of the refractive index variation (3.39) and considering a zero intensity in the asymptotic region $I_\infty \approx 0$, we give the variation of the refractive index in a photorefractive medium under the isotropic approach by:

$$\Delta n(\tilde{I}) = -\frac{1}{2} n_0^3 r_{eff} |\mathbf{E}_{ext}| \frac{1}{1 + \tilde{I}} = -\frac{1}{2} n_0^3 r_{eff} |\mathbf{E}_{ext}| \frac{1}{1 + I/I_{sat}} \quad (3.53)$$

Equation (3.53) shows that a photorefractive nonlinearity has a saturable character.

To illustrate this, we plot in Fig.3.11.(a) the evolution of $\Delta n(I)$ for a fixed value of the external electric field $E_{ext} = 1500 \text{ V.cm}^{-1}$ and different I_{sat} . One observes on the figure that $\Delta n(I)$ saturates always at a certain value of $\Delta n(I)$ with different I_{sat} . Figure 3.11.(b) presents the evolution of $\Delta n(I)$ for a fixed value of I_{sat} and various values of E_{ext} . Here, we observe that Δn at $I \rightarrow +\infty$ is different depending on the external electric field.

Figure 3.11: Figure of the nonlinear refractive index variation of the photorefractive nonlinearity in the isotropic approximation. Panel (a) presents $\Delta n(I)$ for various values of the saturation intensity and a fixed external electric field. Panel (b) displays $\Delta n(I)$ for various external field and a fixed I_{sat} .

The isotropic description remains a good approximation to study the variation of the refractive index in a photorefractive medium in the (1+1)D. However, for a (1+2)D study, one has to use the anisotropic approach.

Anisotropic approximation Developed by Zozulya and Anderson^[134], the anisotropic approach suggests that the space charge field is expressed as a function of an electrostatic potential denoted by ϕ .

$$\mathbf{E}_{sc} = \nabla\phi \quad (3.54)$$

The expression of the current density (3.44) without the photovoltaic term reads:

$$\mathbf{j} = e\mu n_{e-} \nabla\phi + eD\nabla n_{e-} \quad (3.55)$$

Since we have a single beam propagating into the photorefractive medium, we also can assume that the space charge electric field varies slowly regarding the spatial coordinates $\nabla\mathbf{E}_{sc} \approx 0$. If we substitute the expression of n_{e-} in equation (3.55) we get an equation of first and second order derivatives of the potential as a function of the first and the second order derivative of the beam's intensity \tilde{I} .

$$\nabla\tilde{I} \cdot \nabla\phi + (\tilde{I} + 1)\nabla \cdot (\nabla\phi) - \frac{k_B T}{e} \nabla^2(\tilde{I} + 1) = 0 \quad (3.56)$$

The application of a static electric field along the x -axis allows us to write the electrostatic potential as a difference between the biased electric field $|\mathbf{E}_{ext}|_x$ and ϕ_0 the potential induced solely by the light beam intensity $\phi = \phi_0 - |\mathbf{E}_{ext}|_x$. Therefore, the final equation that describes the photoinduced potential takes the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla^2\phi_0 = & -\nabla\ln(1 + \tilde{I})\nabla\phi_0 + |\mathbf{E}_{ext}| \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \ln(1 + \tilde{I}) \\ & - \frac{k_B T}{e} \left[\nabla^2 \ln(1 + \tilde{I}) + (\nabla \ln(1 + \tilde{I}))^2 \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3.57)$$

The latter equation shows that the potential comprises two main effects, the diffusion effect expressed by the coefficient $k_B T/e$ and the drift effect manifested in the first two terms of the R.H.S of equation (3.57). Both effects create an anisotropic variation of the refractive index affecting the spatial intensity distribution of the laser beam. Hence, a circular laser beam will be elliptical at the output of the photorefractive medium.

So far, the expression of the nonlinear refractive index variation in a photorefractive medium is finally determined. In the next paragraph, we suggest to describe the propagation of a light beam into the SBN crystal.

3.2.5 The equation of propagation in the SBN crystal

As discussed in section 3.2.2, a laser beam propagating in a biased photorefractive medium induces a local transverse refractive index variation. This variation impacts the propagation of the beam. Consequently, to model its propagation in the photorefractive medium, one has to take into account this variation within the wave equation. We therefore give in analogy with the Kerr-type nonlinearity (i.e. eq. (3.27)) the propagation equation along the z -axis of a light beam into a photorefractive medium assumed to be the SBN:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \mathbf{A}(x, y, z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_e} \nabla_{\perp} \mathbf{A}(x, y, z) - i\alpha \mathbf{A}(x, y, z) + k_0 \Delta n(I) \mathbf{A}(x, y, z) \quad (3.58)$$

Where $\mathbf{A}(x, y, z)$ is the amplitude of the laser beam, I is its intensity $I = |\mathbf{A}(x, y, z)|^2$, $k_0 = 2\pi/\lambda_0$ is the wave vector in the vacuum, n_e represents the linear refractive index along the extraordinary axis of the crystal (x -axis), $\Delta n(I)$ is the variation of the refractive index induced by the intensity of the beam and α is the

Figure 3.12: Illustration of the propagation of a laser beam into the SBN crystal. The polarisation of the wave is oriented along the x -axis (c -axis of the crystal). A static electric field is being applied along the x -axis and a white light (incoherent light) is shone on the medium to control the nonlinearity of the medium.

linear absorption coefficient of the material. For the SBN:61 crystal, we estimated the linear absorption coefficient of the medium at $\alpha = 1.319 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at a wavelength $\lambda = 532 \text{ nm}$. Note that in the following, we consider the isotropic description for the characterisation of the medium even though it is not strictly valid in $(1+2)$ -dimensional geometry. Therefore, for a crystal oriented as follows (see Fig. 3.12):

- The c -axis of the crystal is parallel to x -axis (the direction of the applied external field E_{ext}).
- The polarisation of the laser beam is parallel to the c -axis of the crystal in order to get a maximum refractive index change.
- An incoherent light shone on the crystal to monitor the saturation intensity I_{sat}

The nonlinear refractive index change $\Delta n(I)$ is expressed using equation (3.53) in the photorefractive nonlinearity, we usually make use of the following change of variable $A(x, y, z) \rightarrow A_1(x, y, z)e^{-ik_0\Delta n_{\text{max}}z}$ to change the reference for the bulk refractive index and to simplify the expression of the $\Delta n(I)$ in Equation (3.58). Therefore, the nonlinear propagation equation reads:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} A_1(x, y, z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_e} \nabla_{\perp}^2 A_1(x, y, z) - i\alpha A_1(x, y, z) + k_0 \Delta n_{\text{max}} \left[\frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{I} + 1} \right] A_1(x, y, z). \quad (3.59)$$

Where $\Delta n_{\text{max}} = \frac{-1}{2} n_e^3 r_{33} E_{\text{ext}}$ corresponds to the maximum variation of the refractive index. After the variable change, the refractive index variation in the SBN takes the following form:

$$\Delta n(I) = \Delta n_{\text{max}} \frac{\tilde{I}}{\tilde{I} + 1} \quad (3.60)$$

We plot in figure 3.13 the variation of the refractive index $\Delta n(I)$ as a function of the intensity of the laser beam I (i.e. eq. (3.13)) for various values of E_{ext} and I_{sat} . We observe on Fig. 3.13.(a) that the curves saturate at the same value Δn_{max} defined by E_{ext} but with different saturation intensities defined by the tangent at the origin of the curves. On Fig. 3.13.(b), one sees that Δn_{max} is different, while the saturation intensity is

Figure 3.13: Figure of the refractive index change $\Delta n(I)$ evolution versus the intensity of the light beam of the SBN crystal in the self-defocusing regime. Δn_{\max} is the maximum value of the refractive index.

similar for both curves. Here, we considered a negative variation of the refractive index (the self-defocusing regime). However, theoretically the same behaviour takes place in the case of the self-focusing regime. The next section is devoted to the characterisation of the SBN crystal by taking advantage of the self-phase modulation effect seen in paragraph 3.1.2.

3.3 Characterisation of the photorefractive media using the spatial self-phase modulation (sSPM)

In the first part of this section, we explain the principle of the spatial self-phase modulation in a photorefractive crystal. We further discuss the technique that allows us to measure the change of the refractive index through the spatial self-phase modulation effect. Thereafter, we present the experimental set-up we used for the characterisation of the nonlinear medium. Finally, we discuss the results of the experiment.

3.3.1 Spatial self-phase modulation

The principle of the spatial self-phase modulation The spatial self-phase modulation (sSPM) consists in the phase modulation of the laser beam through the local transverse variation of the refractive index that arises from the nonlinearity. This effect is considered as one manifestation of the intensity-dependent refractive index. In comparison to the self-phase modulation (see paragraph 3.1.2), the sSPM effect acts on the spatial distribution of the laser beam through the generation of new spatial frequencies leading to the broadening of the spatial spectrum of the wave in the transverse plane (k_x, k_y) .

The accumulated nonlinear phase of a laser beam propagating into a nonlinear medium denoted by $\Delta\phi_{\text{nl}}$ is proportional to the refractive index change $\Delta n(I)$:

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{nl}}(x, y) = k_0 \int_0^L \Delta n(\mathbf{r}, z) dz \quad (3.61)$$

Where L is the distance of propagation of the beam along the nonlinear crystal. The nonlinear phase change $\Delta\phi_{\text{nl}}$ varies also as a function of the transverse coordinates (x, y) because it is proportional to the intensity

of the laser beam $I(x,y)$.

Let us consider the propagation of a Gaussian profile beam into a photorefractive medium.

$$I(x,y) = I_0 e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2}, \quad (3.62)$$

where $I(x,y)$ is the intensity of the Gaussian beam and ω_0 is the radius of the Gaussian beam at $1/e^2$. Within the frame of a *non-saturated*⁷ regime of nonlinearity i.e. $\Delta n(I) = n_2 I(x,y)$, the induced phase change $\Delta\varphi_{nl}$ can be put in the form of a Gaussian profile as follows:

$$\Delta\varphi_{nl}(r) = \Delta\varphi_0 e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2}. \quad (3.63)$$

Where $\Delta\varphi_0$ represents the phase variation at the maximum of the Gaussian beam intensity $r = 0$. Assuming that the absorption coefficient is negligible $\alpha = 0$, we give $\Delta\varphi_0$ of the photorefractive nonlinearity as follows:

$$\Delta\varphi_0 = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{k_0 L n_e^3 r_{33} E_{\text{ext}}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I_0 = \Delta n_{\text{max}} \frac{k_0 L}{I_{\text{sat}}} I_0, \quad (3.64)$$

where E_{ext} , I_{sat} and r_{33} are respectively the external electric field, the saturation intensity and the electro-optic coefficient, they were given previously. In the case of the photorefractive nonlinearity with a Gaussian profile beam, the phase variation $\Delta\varphi_{nl}$ reads:

$$\Delta\varphi_{nl} = \Delta n_{\text{max}} \frac{I_0 e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2}}{I_0 e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2} + I_{\text{sat}}} \quad (3.65)$$

In figure 3.14, we represent the refractive index variation profiles when a Gaussian beam propagates on the one hand into a Kerr-type nonlinear (Fig. 3.14.(a)) and on the other hand into a photorefractive saturated medium (Fig. 3.14.(b)). In the first case, we get a clear Gaussian profile of the refractive index variation, while in the second case, the refractive index change has a Gaussian profile with a saturating behaviour.

Figure 3.14: Refractive index variation profile in the case of the saturated and non-saturated photorefractive medium

⁷The non-saturated regime in the photorefractive nonlinearity can be considered as the optical Kerr-type nonlinearity $\Delta n(I) = n_2 I$. In fact, in the expression $\Delta n(I) = \Delta n_{\text{max}} \frac{I}{I+1}$, taking $I \rightarrow 0$, gives a similar expression to a Kerr-type nonlinearity $\Delta n(I) = \frac{\Delta n_{\text{max}}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I$.

According to equation (3.61), the phase of the laser beam changes because of the nonlinear refractive index variation $\Delta n(I)$. This phase change allows the appearance of new spatial frequencies (k_x, k_y) leading to the broadening of the spatial spectrum. In the 1-dimensional far-field intensity distribution, one observes the appearance of secondary lobes corresponding to the new spatial frequencies created. In the 2-dimensional spatial spectrum, these lobes transform into rings, yielding a structure of concentric rings. We call this effect "diffraction through a nonlinear medium".^[135] We illustrate in figure 3.15 the diffraction through the SBN crystal thanks to the sSPM effect. In the next paragraph we suggest giving a detailed explanation of this diffraction phenomenon.

Figure 3.15: An illustration of the diffraction pattern taking place at the far-field region due to the propagation into the SBN.

Origin of the diffraction effect through the nonlinear medium We attribute the occurrence of the diffraction pattern through the nonlinear medium to the interference phenomenon between two waves or more. To understand the origin of this interference, one shall calculate the transverse spatial frequency $k_{\perp}(r)$. It is given by:

$$k_{\perp}^{(nl)} = \frac{d}{dr} \Delta \varphi_{nl}(r), \quad (3.66)$$

where $k_{\perp}^{(nl)}$ is the localised spatial frequency induced through the nonlinearity. We assume here that we have a Kerr-type nonlinearity and a Gaussian profile beam. Therefore $k_{\perp}^{(nl)}$ reads:

$$k_{\perp}^{(nl)}(r) = -4\Delta\varphi_0 \frac{r}{\omega_0^2} e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2} \quad (3.67)$$

Expression (3.16) tells that for one value of k_{\perp}^{nl} , two spatial solutions exist. Let us denote them by r_1 and r_2 (see Figure 3.16). These two solutions have the same wavenumber $k_{\perp}^{nl}(r_1) = k_{\perp}^{nl}(r_2)$, therefore, a two-wave interference is expected to take place between these waves. We present in the Fig. 3.16.(a) the phase change profile $\Delta\varphi_{nl}$ that occurs in a Kerr-type nonlinear medium and in Fig. 3.16.(b) the corresponding spatial frequency k_{\perp}^{nl} .

The nonlinear phase difference between the points r_1 and r_2 can be calculated using:

$$\Delta\varphi_{nl}|_{r_1-r_2} = \Delta\varphi_{nl}(r_1) - \Delta\varphi_{nl}(r_2) \quad (3.68)$$

Figure 3.16: Figure of the spatial phase variation $\Delta\varphi_{nl}$ (Panel (a)) and the corresponding spatial frequency k_{\perp}^{nl} (Panel (b)) of Gaussian beam after the sSPM

And the intensity distribution that arises from points r_1 and r_2 can be expressed as follows:

$$I_{r_1-r_2} = I(r_1) + I(r_2) + 2\sqrt{I(r_1)I(r_2)} \cos(\Delta\varphi_{nl}|_{r_1-r_2}) \quad (3.69)$$

The third term in the R.H.S of eq. (3.69) represents the interference term between two waves with the same wave number $k_{\perp}^{(nl)}$. In the 2D space, the interference pattern takes the form of a ring structure (see figure 3.15).

Actually, the phase variation of the propagating laser beam into the nonlinear medium does not come only from the nonlinear medium, but in reality the phase accumulated during the propagation can have another contribution related to the wavefront of the propagating wave. In the next paragraph, we propose to investigate the impact of the Gaussian profile on the accumulated phase of the propagating beam.

Impact of the Gaussian profile on the accumulated phase According to the report of Deng and co-workers^[136], the profile of the laser beam has as well an impact on its phase. We denote this phase change by $\Delta\varphi_G$. Since we deal with a Gaussian, then we can write the phase variation because of the beam's wavefront as follows:

$$\Delta\varphi_G = k_0 \frac{n_e r^2}{2R(z)}, \quad (3.70)$$

where r is the radial coordinate and R is the curvature radius of the Gaussian beam. We represent in figure 3.17 the propagation of a Gaussian beam in free space. The quantities ω_0 , $\omega(z) = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 + (z/Z_R)^2}$ and $Z_R = (\pi\omega_0^2/\lambda)$ are respectively the waist, the radius at a distance z and the Rayleigh range of the Gaussian beam. We placed in the figure 3.17 the nonlinear medium arbitrarily on the right side and we hereby discuss the optimal position of the nonlinear crystal regarding the Gaussian beam propagation to have a minimum impact of the wavefront on the total accumulated phase.

Figure 3.17: Illustration of the Gaussian profile expansion. The nonlinear medium of thickness L was placed out of the Rayleigh region.

The curvature radius $R(z)$ in equation (3.70) is given by the following expression. Its plot is depicted in figure 3.18:

$$R(z) = z \left[1 + \left(\frac{Z_R}{z} \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.71)$$

Let us now explain the impact of the Gaussian profile on the phase of the wave propagating into the nonlinear medium. The total phase accumulated by the wave in a Kerr-type medium can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta\varphi_T = \Delta\varphi_{nl} + \Delta\varphi_G = \Delta\varphi_0 e^{-r^2/\omega_0^2} + k_0 \frac{ne r^2}{2R(z)} \quad (3.72)$$

The above equation shows the contribution of the beam profile manifested in the term of the curvature radius $R(z)$ and playing the role of an initial chirp. Therefore, if the term of the curvature radius is very small ($R(z) \rightarrow 0$) then the contribution of the Gaussian wavefront is very high and we can say that the phase accumulated by the wave comes only from the Gaussian shape. In contrast, if $R(z) \rightarrow \infty$ (collimated beam), the contribution of the beam's wavefront to the phase is negligible. Consequently, for a precise characterisation of our nonlinear medium we need to ensure the collimation condition. Besides this, from figure 3.18, one can see that within the Rayleigh region Z_R the radius of curvature goes to infinity $R(z) \rightarrow \infty$. However, it undergoes a radical sign change. This sign variation impacts significantly the diffraction pattern that forms in the far-field making it impossible to measure the phase variation induced only by the sSPM effect.

To illustrate the impact of the curvature radius let us recall the description of the previous paragraph but this time we include the term of the curvature radius.

Calculating the total localised spatial frequency $k_{\perp}^{(T)}$ of the totally induced phase variation $\Delta\varphi_T$ yields:

$$k_{\perp}^{(T)} = \frac{d}{dr} \Delta\varphi_T = k_{\perp}^{(nl)}(r) + k_0 \frac{ne r}{R(z)} \quad (3.73)$$

We display in figure 3.19 the variation of the total spatial frequency $k_{\perp}^{(T)}$ of a Gaussian beam profile for various values of the curvature radius R .

Figure 3.19 demonstrates the impact of the curvature radius of the Gaussian beam on the spatial frequency $k_{\perp}^{(T)}$. We can see on Fig 3.19.(a) that, when the $R \rightarrow \infty$ (i.e. collimated beam) the impact of the Gaussian shape on the accumulated total phase is negligible. Therefore, the diffraction pattern occurring

Figure 3.18: Plot of the radius of curvature evolution of a Gaussian profile beam versus the distance of propagation z

Figure 3.19: Figure of the spatial frequency $k_{\perp}^{(T)}(r)$ of a Gaussian beam profile for various values of the curvature radius R .

in the far-field is only induced from the nonlinear refractive index variation and only a two-wave process creates the diffraction pattern. While for a well-defined value of R (e.g. Fig. 3.19.(c) and (d)), we observe that the curve of the spatial frequency is distorted and for a single value $k_{\perp}^{(T)}(r)$ we can find three spatial solution denoted r_1 , r_2 and r_3 . Therefore, the diffraction pattern of the far-field can also be generated from a three-wave interference process. Decreasing more and more the radius of curvature R (e.g. Fig. 3.19.(e) and (f)) yields a monotonous variation of the spatial frequency $k_{\perp}^{(T)}$ as a function of r . Hence, no diffraction pattern is expected to form in the far-field.

Let us now calculate the spatial spectrum of a non-collimated Gaussian beam ($R \neq \infty$) propagating into a nonlinear medium (e.g. Kerr-type medium). We access the spatial spectrum by taking the Fourier transform of the intensity distribution of the propagating beam^[137]. One writes:

$$S(k) = \left| \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} I_0 e^{-2r^2/\omega_0^2} e^{(-i\Delta\phi_T)} e^{-ikr} dr \right|^2 \quad (3.74)$$

In figure 3.20 we present the evolution of the spectrum $S(k)$ of a non-collimated Gaussian beam. Each horizontal unit cut of the figure represents the obtained 1D spatial spectrum after the propagation into the nonlinear medium of length L for various values of ρ . Here, the nonlinear accumulated phase is constant and the quantity $\rho = \omega_0^2 / (2n_2 I_0 R(z))$ is controlled solely by the radius of curvature $R(z)$.

Figure 3.20: Figure of the spectrum $S(k)$ evolution of a Gaussian shape beam in a nonlinear Kerr-type medium with a fixed $\Delta\phi_0 = 7$ rad as a function of the radius of curvature R

When $R(z) > 0$ a self-defocusing effect takes place because of the Gaussian wavefront giving birth to new spatial frequencies and when $R(z) < 0$ a self-focusing effect occurs. This figure shows the formation of the diffraction pattern even though the nonlinearity has a fixed value.

After this analysis, we are convinced that for a precise characterisation of the nonlinearity of the medium, we need to minimise the impact of the Gaussian shape of the laser beam on the accumulated phase. Therefore, in our experiments we placed the nonlinear medium outside of the Rayleigh range (as shown in Fig. 3.17). In this region, we know that $R(z)$ has only one sign and also varies linearly with the distance of propagation z . Besides this, knowing that the length of the medium is negligible regarding the length at which the radius of curvature changes significantly. Therefore, the variation of the curvature radius $R(z)$ along the crystal's length L is considered as constant. Hence, $\Delta\phi_G$ is constant.

3.3.2 Experimental procedure

We have discussed previously the origin of the diffraction pattern which takes place through the propagation into a nonlinear medium and we have already demonstrated that it emanates from a two (or more)-wave interference process. Therefore, one can calculate the interference intensity distribution that arises from two points of the same spatial frequency (e.g. r_1 and r_2) as follows:

$$I|_{r_1-r_2} = I(r_1) + I(r_2) + 2\sqrt{I(r_1)I(r_2)} \cos(\Delta\phi_T) \quad (3.75)$$

where $I(r_1)$ and $I(r_2)$ are respectively the intensities emitted from r_1 and r_2 spots. According to eq. (3.75), the constructive interference occurs when $\Delta\phi_T = 2m\pi$. The latter in the 2-dimensional space corresponds to a bright ring. In contrast, a destructive interference corresponding to a dark ring in the 2D space occurs when $\Delta\phi_T = (2m - 1)\pi$, where $m \geq 1$ is an integer number.

For a non-varying radius of curvature as a function of z , the Gaussian contribution to the total phase is assumed to be constant $\Delta\varphi_G \approx \text{constant}$. This suggests that the occurrence of the ring structure is due only to the nonlinear effect (sSPM). Therefore, the two upper conditions can be written only in terms of the nonlinear phase variation and we give:

$$\Delta\varphi_0 = l\pi \quad (3.76)$$

Where l takes an even value (resp. odd) for bright rings (resp. dark rings). The latter expression is an important formula which allows to relate the phase variation due to the nonlinear effect to the number of rings in the spatial spectrum. Thus the number of rings is given as follows:

$$N_{\text{rings}} \simeq \frac{\Delta\varphi_0}{\pi} \quad (3.77)$$

For $\Delta\varphi_0 \gg 2\pi$ one observes multiple diffraction ring pattern. Finally, using equation (3.77) and (3.64), we give the expression relating the nonlinear refractive index Δn to the number of rings N_{rings} :

$$\Delta n \simeq \frac{2\pi N_{\text{rings}}}{k_0 L} \quad (3.78)$$

Using the above equation one can experimentally access the nonlinear refractive index of the SBN crystal through *counting the number of rings having formed in the far-field intensity distribution*. We illustrate in figure 3.21 the procedure to measure the nonlinear refractive index through sSPM.

Procedure of measuring $\Delta n(I)$

Figure 3.21: Illustration of the procedure of measuring the nonlinear refractive index change through the sSPM. Starting from the diffraction pattern we count the number of rings to measure the nonlinear phase accumulated, hence, the nonlinear refractive index is deduced.

3.3.3 Experimental set-up

The experiment depicted in figure 3.22 consists in a laser beam propagating through an SBN crystal. A solid-state laser provides a green beam $\lambda = 532$ nm with an initial diameter of 2 mm. Using a telescope, we reduce the diameter of the laser beam to subsequently couple it into a single mode fibre. At the output of the fibre we regain the laser beam with a diameter $D = 145$ μm , we added a $\lambda/2$ to control the polarisation of light before propagating into the crystal. To maximise the nonlinear effect in the medium we fix the polarisation of the laser beam parallel to the optical axis of the crystal c -axis here oriented along the x -axis. After the $\lambda/2$ the beam passes through a converging lens to get a radius at $1/e^2$ of 220 μm at the input of

Figure 3.22: Figure of the experimental set-up in 2D space used for the characterisation of the SBN. A Gaussian beam shape propagates into the SBN and detected through a sCMOS camera placed at the far-field. The external electric field (resp. the white light) controls the maximum variation of the refractive index Δn_{\max} (resp. the saturation intensity I_{sat})

the crystal and $230 \mu\text{m}$ at its output. The principal role of the last lens is to ensure a well-defined radius of curvature R with a constant sign along the propagation onto the crystal. We estimated the radius of curvature of the beam in the middle of the crystal at $R = 21 \text{ cm}$. The reason for which we didn't place the crystal in the Rayleigh range $Z_R = \pi\omega_0^2/\lambda$ was discussed before. Afterwards, the beam propagates into the SBN crystal and gets captured by an sCMOS camera placed in the far-field region localised at 1 m from the output of the crystal.

The nonlinear medium is a $5 \times 5 \times 20 \text{ mm}^3$ SBN:61 crystal doped with cerium (0.02%). To control the nonlinear refractive index change $\Delta n(I)$, we apply an external field \mathbf{E}_{ext} along the c -axis by means of two electrodes allowing to reach Δn_{\max} . As pointed out earlier we can control the dynamics of the saturation intensity I_{sat} through the application of an incoherent illumination which enhances the thermal effects within the photorefractive crystal. It is worth mentioning that during the characterisation process, one should keep the white light source and the crystal unmoved to ensure a constant value of I_{sat} .

3.4 Results and discussion

We present here the obtained results. In our analysis, we only considered the case of the self-defocusing photorefractive nonlinearity $\Delta n < 0$. This is because in the self-focusing case, the beam undergoes the modulational instability effect. This phenomenon makes it difficult to get a useful diffraction pattern for characterising the medium.

We would like to mention that after getting the diffraction pattern, we start to count manually the number of rings having formed in the spatial spectrum. When a ring appears, we directly acknowledge that the

Figure 3.23: Illustration of the 1D (resp. 2D) spatial spectrum as a function of the accumulated phase

nonlinear phase $\Delta\varphi_0$ has gained a value of π or 2π depending on the previous intensity distribution of the spatial spectrum (see figure 3.23). This procedure is explained in detail in later paragraphs with concrete examples. However, we give in figure 3.23 an illustration of the nonlinear phase with the corresponding 1-dimensional far-field intensity profiles to show the evolution of the accumulated nonlinear phase as a function of these profiles.

To understand the saturable behaviour of the photorefractive nonlinearity, as well as to characterise the anisotropic aspect of the SBN crystal, we carried out the measurement of the Δn for different values of the external electric field $E_{\text{ext}} = [0.5, 1.0, 1.5] \times 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ and different values of the saturation intensity I_{sat} . The value of I_{sat} is not directly measurable using an instrument. However, to control it, we define a measurable physical quantity (the white light power) denoted by P_{WL} ⁸ to refer to a fixed value of I_{sat} . We vary this power as follows $P_{\text{WL}} = [0.36, 0.96, 1.92] \text{ W}$.

We finally have chosen 5 set of measurements resumed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_1 : \{E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}, P_{\text{WL}} = 0.36\}, & \quad S_2 : \{E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}, P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96\}, \\
 S_3 : \{E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}, P_{\text{WL}} = 1.92\} & \\
 S_4 : \{E_{\text{ext}} = 0.5 \cdot 10^{-5}, P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96\}, & \quad S_5 : \{E_{\text{ext}} = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-5}, P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96\}
 \end{aligned}$$

S_1, S_2 and S_3 were carried out for the same value of the external field and different values of the white light power. As for S_4 and S_5 represent measurements for a fixed value of the white light and different values of the external electric field.

3.4.1 Far-field intensity distribution

We present in figure 3.24 the spatial intensity distribution of the laser beam measured in the far-field (k_x, k_y) for various values of the input intensity. This set of measurement represents the group S_2 where $E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ and $P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96 \text{ W}$.

One observes clearly the appearance of the diffraction pattern. The increase of the beam's intensity induces the broadening of the spatial spectrum and the appearance of new spatial frequencies as explained

⁸A description of the measurement technique of the white light is presented in appendix B.A.4

previously. The intensity was increased gradually to intentionally observe the threshold intensity for the appearance of each ring. It was varied from $I = 0.5 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ to $I = 700 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ for this set of measurement.

Also from figure 3.24 one immediately sees that the shape of the diffraction pattern is elliptical. This comes from the intrinsic anisotropy of the SBN crystal as well as from the induced anisotropy through the application of the external static electric field E_{ext} . Always on the same figure, we can see qualitatively on pictures (g) to (h) that the number of rings does not increase. That is recognised as the saturable behaviour of the photorefractive nonlinearity.

Figure 3.24: Intensity distribution of the spatial spectrum measured in the far-field, i.e. (k_x, k_y) plane, for various input laser intensities. The size of the total image is $17 \times 14 \text{ mm}^2$

To precisely count the number of rings having formed in the far-field we use the profiles of the intensity distribution of the spatial spectrum. To do so, we suggest proceeding as follows. First we develop the procedure in detail for the cuts along the k_x direction and we give the corresponding results. Thereafter, we deduce from this procedure the results along the k_y direction.

3.4.2 Measurement of the nonlinear refractive index variation Δn

Measurement of the Δn along the x -axis As annotated by the stripe in pictures 3.24.(c) and 3.24.(f), we perform an integration of k_x -cut profile over 40 pixels along the k_y axis in order to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. We present in figure 3.25 the cuts along k_x for various values of the beam's intensity, for a fixed external electric field and a fixed white light power at ($E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ V.m}^{-1}$, $P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96 \text{ W}$).

Figure 3.25: The spatial intensity distribution profiles cuts along the x -axis for various values of the input beam intensity

We start from a Gaussian profile displayed in figure 3.25.(a). Because of the increase of the laser's intensity, the phase of the propagating wave changes and induces the appearance of extra spatial frequencies in the spectrum. The number of rings in the picture 3.25.(a) is 0. Therefore, according to equation (3.76), the nonlinear phase variation $\Delta\varphi_0 = 0$.

In the picture 3.25.(b), we count manually the number of maxima, the result is 9 maxima i.e. 4 rings + 1 bright central spot (see the zoom of central spot). And in picture 3.25.(c), we count 10 maxima which represent 5 rings + 1 dark central spot. To get the nonlinear phase variation (nonlinear refractive index) in these cases we need to consider two different methods of measurement that depend on the state of the central spot.

In the first case (i.e. Fig. 3.25.(b)), the nonlinear phase variation is given by

$$\Delta\varphi_0 = 2N_{\text{ring}}\pi \quad \Rightarrow \quad \Delta\varphi_0 = 8\pi \quad (3.79)$$

The above equality is attributed to the term of interference in equation 3.75. In the case of a bright central spot, we know that the waves interfered constructively. Therefore, the term of interference should take its

maximum value, which is represented by an even number times π . Consequently, in the case of the SBN crystal we used (i.e. $L = 2$ cm), the nonlinear refractive index along the x -axis is:

$$\Delta n = (8\pi/k_0L) = 1.06 \cdot 10^{-4}$$

Using the destructive interference hypothesis, we can easily deduce the relation for the case of a dark central spot. Therefore, for the figure 3.25.(c) where we have 5 rings, the nonlinear phase is found by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\varphi_0 &= (2N_{\text{ring}} - 1)\pi \quad \Rightarrow \quad \Delta\varphi_0 = 9\pi \\ &\Rightarrow \quad \Delta n = 1.33 \cdot 10^{-4} \end{aligned} \quad (3.80)$$

We counted respectively 10 rings in figures 3.25.(d) and 3.25.(e) with a dark central spot and a bright one. This respectively gives refractive indices variation $\Delta n = 2.39 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $\Delta n = 2.66 \cdot 10^{-4}$. In the following 3 pictures 3.25.(d), (f) and (f) we notice that the number of rings saturates at 10 which in terms of the phase $\Delta\varphi_0 = 20\pi$. As discussed in subsections 3.2.5 and 3.2.4, such a saturating behaviour is expected for the SBN photorefractive crystal.

Figure 3.26: Experimental spectrum profiles (cut along k_x) for various input intensities. Black (resp. white) corresponds to the maximum (resp. minimum) spectral power which is normalised to 1 for each measurement. The widths of the profiles were artificially increased for clarity.

To highlight the saturation of the nonlinear effect in a photorefractive crystal we present in Figure 3.26 cuts along k_x with a thickness of 10 pixels for various values of the beam's intensity. Each filled stripe of the image represents the intensity distribution at which the measurement was performed. We added to the image plain stripes of 1 pixel thickness at values for which the measurement was not carried out to recover clarity in the figure and the realistic aspect of the measurement. The ordinate axis of the image represents the value of the optical intensity in $\text{mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ while its abscissa is simply the wave number k_x expressed in

mm^{-1} . Figure 3.26 reveals clearly the saturable behaviour of the photorefractive nonlinearity manifested in constant number of rings at very high values of the intensity.

Another point to precise regarding the spatial spectrum, is that for higher input intensities (Fig. 3.25.(e) and (f)), one observes a decrease of the power of the of the secondary lobes in favour of the central lobe $k_x = 0$. This behaviour can be explained through the relation of the refractive index variation in a photorefractive medium (3.60). In fact, when $I \gg I_{\text{sat}}$ the refractive index variation becomes:

$$\Delta n \approx -\frac{1}{2}n_e^3 r_{33} E_{\text{ext}} = \Delta n_{\text{max}} \Rightarrow \Delta \phi_{\text{nl}} = k_0 l \Delta n_{\text{max}} \quad (3.81)$$

This relation demonstrates that Δn does not depend anymore on the intensity of the beam implying that the medium becomes homogeneous. Therefore, no interference patterns can be observed in the far-field and one gets a clear Gaussian diffracted pattern. This behaviour has been also found in our simulations. For a Kerr nonlinearity, the numerics did not reveal such a behaviour. This indicates that it is only related to the saturable nature of the photorefractive nonlinearity.

After counting the number of rings for all sets of measurement, we get discrete values of the Δn as a function of beam's intensity. Therefore, we obtain experimental points that are displayed in figure 3.27 and 3.28.

To extract the values of the Δn_{max} and I_{sat} , we perform a fitting procedure on the measured values of the Δn using the isotropic model equation $\Delta n = \Delta n_{\text{max}} (\tilde{I}/(\tilde{I} + 1))$ (3.60). In the fitting procedure we keep Δn_{max} and I_{sat} as free parameters.

Figure 3.27: Refractive index variation along the x -axis versus the beam's intensity and the corresponding fit for each set of measurement. The external field is fixed to $1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ while the power of the white light varies from 0.36 W (blue dots) to 1.92 W (red dots). Vertical error bars are estimated looking at the cuts of the images and represent an uncertainty of one ring on the rings count at high intensity. Horizontal errors bars are smaller than the symbols.

Figure 3.27 presents the variation of the refractive index versus the intensity of the laser for a fixed value of the external field $E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$. We vary the white light power from 0.36 W (blue circles) to 1.92 W (red diamonds), their corresponding fits are solid lines with the same color of the experimental points. We thus can see that when the power of the white light is the lowest, the saturation is quickly attainable. Conversely, the more powerful the white light, the more we need higher intensities to reach the

saturation. The maximum refractive index change was measured for the three curves and was found to be nearly similar $\Delta n_{\max} = 2.6 - 3.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$. The extracted saturation intensities are $I_{\text{sat}}^{0.36} = 9 \pm 0.2 \text{ mW.cm}^2$, $I_{\text{sat}}^{0.96} = 25.7 \pm 0.9 \text{ mW.cm}^2$ and $I_{\text{sat}}^{1.92} = 74.7 \pm 3.3 \text{ mW.cm}^2$. From this measurement, one can notice that the applied external electric field E_{ext} allows to control the values of the maximum refractive index variation Δn_{\max} , since, the latter is constant because of the applied external electric field.

Figure 3.28: Refractive index variation along the x -axis versus the beam's intensity and the corresponding fit for each set of measurement. The power of the white light is fixed to 0.96 W while the applied electric field varies from $0.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ (red dots) to $1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ (green dots).

In Figure 3.28 we display as well the refractive index change as a function of the optical intensity but this time with setting fixed the white light power $P_{\text{WL}} = 0.96 \text{ W}$ and varying the external electric field from $E_{\text{ext}} = 0.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ (red diamonds) to $E_{\text{ext}} = 1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V.m}^{-1}$ (green triangles). We see clearly that the curves present different refractive indices at saturation Δn_{\max} . However, the saturation level is reached nearly at the same values of the optical intensities. Thus, we notice from this measurement that the white light source allows to fix the saturation intensity I_{sat} . The latter represents the quickness to reach the maximum refractive index change Δn_{\max} . This behaviour is expected because the power of the white light is maintained constant for this set of measurement.

The error bars of the Δn measurement in the experimental data as well as in the fitting curves are estimated through supposing an uncertainty of one ring in the procedure of rings count. The uncertainty might increase along with the increase of the input intensity because we lose power on the secondary lobes in favour of the central spot. For horizontal error bars, they are smaller than the symbol. This is because during the measurement we used to increase the intensity gradually till the observation of a new ring. That is why the uncertainty on the intensity is very small. Even though, we have taken an uncertainty interval of 10% on the horizontal axis.

We summarise in Table 3.2 the extracted values of Δn_{\max} and I_{sat} for various set of measurement.

Measurement of the Δn along the y -axis The procedure here is the same as in the previous part. Therefore, in this paragraph, we only show the results relative to the k_y direction. Particularly, the spectrum profiles along the k_y -axis and the curves of the Δn as a function of the laser's input intensity.

Table 3.2: A table summarising the extracted values of the Δn_{\max} along the x -axis and I_{sat} using a fitting procedure.

	Symbols	$ \Delta n_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$	$I_{\text{sat}} \text{ (mW.cm}^{-2}\text{)}$
Fixed E_{ext} Fig. 3.27	○	2.99 ± 0.02	9.0 ± 0.2
	△	3.03 ± 0.08	25.7 ± 0.9
	◇	2.64 ± 0.06	74.7 ± 3.3
Fixed P_{WL} Fig. 3.28	◇	1.09 ± 0.06	24.9 ± 2.2
	△	1.86 ± 0.05	23.9 ± 0.9
	○	3.03 ± 0.08	25.7 ± 0.9

Figure 3.29: Experimental spectrum profiles (cut along k_y) for various input intensities. Black (resp. white) corresponds to the maximum (resp. minimum) spectral power which is normalised to 1 for each measurement. The widths of the profiles were artificially increased for clarity.

Figure 3.29.(a) represents the stacked k_y -cuts of the spatial spectrum for various values of the intensity. As the intensity increases more rings appear on the spatial spectrum until reaching the saturation. One observes clearly that the number of rings (secondary lobes in 1-D) in k_y -cuts is less than the number of rings in k_x -cuts. This, as pointed out earlier, is attributed to the anisotropy of the medium. Typical curves of the k_y -cuts at intensities 40 mW.cm⁻² and 100 mW.cm⁻² are respectively shown in figures 3.29.(b) and 3.29.(c).

Using the past procedure of rings counting allows us to get values of the Δn along the y -axis as a function of the input intensity I . And employing the fitting function (isotropic model) on the acquired data allows us

to extract the values of the Δn_{\max} and I_{sat} . We present for different sets of measurement the refractive index variation Δn along y versus the intensity of the laser beam on figures below.

Figure 3.30: Refractive index variation along the y -axis versus the beam's intensity and the corresponding fit for each set of measurement. Panel (a) the external field is fixed to $1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ while the power of the white light varies from 0.36 W (blue dots) to 1.92 W (red dots). Panel (b) the power of the white light is fixed to 0.96 W while the applied electric field varies from $0.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ (red dots) to $1.5 \cdot 10^5 \text{ V}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ (green dots).

From figure 3.30, we can see the saturable behaviour of the Δn along the y -axis as well. Also we can see that the maximum value of the refractive index Δn_{\max} along the y -axis is smaller than the one along x direction. We display in table 3.3 a summary of the measured values of $(\Delta n_{\max}, I_{\text{sat}})$ of the SBN's crystal along the y -axis. Similarly to Δn along the x -axis, here also we considered an uncertainty of one ring when the intensity increases.

Table 3.3: A table summarising the extracted values of the Δn_{\max} along the y-axis and I_{sat} through the use of isotropic model of the photorefractive effect.

	Symbols	$ \Delta n_{\max} \times 10^{-4}$	$I_{\text{sat}} \text{ (mW.cm}^{-2}\text{)}$
Fixed E_{ext} Fig. 3.30.(a)	○	1.88 ± 0.07	8.4 ± 0.8
	△	1.65 ± 0.05	13.4 ± 1.7
	◇	1.52 ± 0.07	27.3 ± 9.2
Fixed P_{WL} Fig. 3.30.(b)	◇	0.27 ± 0.16	14.5 ± 1
	△	1.65 ± 0.05	13.4 ± 1.7
	○	1.48 ± 0.12	15.2 ± 2.5

3.4.3 Measurement of the SBN's anisotropy

Before ending this part, we would like to point out that we have performed a numerical resolution of the equations (3.25) and (3.57). This has provided qualitatively similar results of the intensity distribution at the far-field with the elliptical diffraction pattern. We display this result in Figure 3.31.(a).

To make a comparison with an isotropic medium, we display in Figure 3.31.(b) the far-field intensity distribution of a laser beam propagating into an isotropic nonlinear medium which is expected to be circular. This comparison allows us to definitely settle that the elliptic shape of the spatial spectrum is attributed to the anisotropic response of the material.

Figure 3.31: Figures of the far-field intensity distribution given by the numerics. (a) is obtained through resolving Equations (3.25) and (3.57). (b) is retrieved through solving numerically the Fresnel-Kirchhoff diffraction formula^[136].

We calculate for each set of measurement the ratio of the extracted refractive indices $\Delta n_{\max}^{(x)}/\Delta n_{\max}^{(y)}$, where $\Delta n_{\max}^{(x)}$ and $\Delta n_{\max}^{(y)}$ are respectively the nonlinear refractive indices along the x -axis and the y -axis for a each set of measurement. And we compare it with the ratio of the semi-major axis to the semi-minor axis of the elliptical spatial spectrum (distances accounted from the center of the image to the outer ring along x and y axis) averaged over 10 images of the highest optical intensity. We display in Figure 3.32 the result of the two ratios (blue circles present the ratio of refractive indices and red diamonds present the ratio of the semi-major to the semi-minor axis).

Both experimental methods for estimating the anisotropy of the crystal give approximately the same ratio which is around 1.6. The latter value is in good accordance with the literature.^[138]

As a resume, this technique allowed us to characterise and measure the nonlinear refractive index variation of the SBN crystal. Despite its anisotropy, we showed that one can measure accurately the nonlinear refractive index change of the SBN through the use of the sSPM and we showed that the isotropic approxi-

Figure 3.32: Figure of the SBN's anisotropy measurement. Blue circles are the ratio $\Delta n_{\text{max}}^{(x)}/\Delta n_{\text{max}}^{(y)}$. Error bars represent the uncertainty given by the fit procedure. Blue solid line (resp. light-blue area) is the mean value (resp. standard deviation) of data. Red diamonds: aspect ratios extracted directly from the images, averaged over the 10 images having the highest intensity. Error bars correspond to the standard deviation.

mation is valid to do so. However, one should consider the characterisation along the x , y axis or any other direction. In contrast, to study the propagation of a wave in the SBN photorefractive media, one should consider the anisotropic approach.

3.5 Summary

To summarise, in this chapter, we have briefly given the theory of nonlinear optics stressing the equation that models the propagation of a wave in a nonlinear medium. We have also given a description of the photorefractive nonlinearity based on the model of Kukhtarev. Afterwards, we presented the spatial self-phase modulation effect in a nonlinear medium and we have shown that making use of this effect allows one to characterise the medium of propagation. Finally, in the results part, we have measured the nonlinear refractive index variation induced by an optical wave as well as the anisotropy of the medium, and we have shown that for characterising the SBN crystal in $(1+1)\text{D}$ space, the sSPM is an accurate technique to do so.

Chapter 4

Superfluidity and drag-force cancellation in a fluid-of-light

C. Michel, O. Boughdad, M. Albert, P. E. Larré and M. Bellec. Superfluid motion and drag-force cancellation in a fluid of light. *Nature communications*, **9**, 2108, (2018)

We dedicate entirely this chapter to the study and the observation of superfluidity in fluids-of-light in the frame of the propagating geometry. For this purpose, we suggest in the first section to introduce a technique to identify the superfluid transition in quantum fluids. Thereafter, a similar technique is introduced in the frame of fluids-of-light. Afterwards, we will present the key parameters serving to control the superfluid transition of the fluid-of-light. Later on, we propose describing the experimental set-up used to probe the superfluid regime of light pointing out some limitations in the experiment. Finally, we will expose evidences of light superfluidity through the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light and also we will introduce the concept of the analogue drag force to demonstrate and probe the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light. To the best of our knowledge, these evidences are among the first demonstrations of light superfluidity in the propagating geometry.

4.1 Brief introduction to superfluidity

Superfluidity is the ability of a fluid to move along a capillary without exhibiting friction. Discovered in 1938 by Kapitza^[1] in Russia and independently by Allen and Misener^[2] in England, it was observed in helium gas cooled to a temperature $T \approx 2$ K. The word superfluidity was invented by Kapitza who concluded in his famous article "By analogy with superconductors, helium below the λ -point ($T \approx 2$ K) enters a special state which might be called superfluid". He was right about the analogy with superconductors, even though superconductivity⁹ was not understood as superfluidity of electron pairs before 1957.

Before the discovery of superfluidity in helium, many experiments were carried out on the latter starting from its first liquefaction by Onnes in the 1908. In 1932, McLennan noticed when cooling the helium gas below the λ -point that it stopped boiling. This result was confirmed in 1935 by Keesom and was pushed to the measurement of the heat capacity of helium in its liquid state, showing the decreasing of the heat

⁹Superconductivity is a property observed in matter that consists in the drop of the resistance of an electric material. Unlike Bosonic gases the particles of a material are Fermions. Therefore, they fulfil the Pauli exclusion principle.^[139] To obtain the electronic fluid, the particles should form bound pairs of electrons known as cooper pairs.

capacity when the temperature reaches the λ -point. This was a signature of the phase transition toward another state. In the same year, Keesom carried out a measurement of the thermal conductivity below the λ -point and found out that liquid helium conducts heat better than copper. This measurement allowed to explain why helium liquid stops boiling below the λ -point. One month after the discovery of superfluidity, John Frank Allen this time with Harry Jones discovered the so-called the "fountain effect" of the superfluid helium^[140]: when heated above a particular critical temperature T helium liquid flows out of the recipient.

In the same year, London proposed the first suggestion of a relation between superfluidity of helium and the Bose-Einstein condensation effect.^[141] He stated that liquid ^4He is a Bosonic gas obeying to the Bose-Einstein statistics. Later on, Tisza came with a brilliant idea which for him explained the fountain effect and the differences between the experiments of Kapitsa and Allen. The idea he suggested is that liquid helium below the λ -point possesses two components, a condensed fraction which has no viscosity nor entropy and the other fraction being a normal fluid with a certain viscosity and a certain entropy.^[19] Soon later in 1941, Landau suggested a theoretical explanation of helium superfluidity^[68], in which, he explained that every excited state can be seen as an ensemble of single elementary excitations. Thereafter, he introduced the two-fluid model by dividing these elementary excitations into two categories: "phonon" excitations and "roton". Until now Landau's theory is considered as an exceptional accomplishment which allows to explain the strange phenomenon of superfluidity in helium. However, Landau in his articles never clarified the relation between BECs and elementary excitations. Thanks to Bogoliubov who suggested in 1947, that a weakly interacting gas can be described as a Bose-Einstein condensate formed by "quasi-particles" and the energy spectrum of this latter is related to the phenomenon of superfluidity.^[65] Years after, Penrose and Onsager^[142-144] generalised and developed the theory of BECs.

More recently, the occurrence of superfluidity and BECs were proved in cold atoms by Ketterle et al.^[145] through the measurement of the excitations spectrum of superfluids and the measurement of the velocity at which superfluidity breaks down. Also in the optical frame, the occurrence of superfluidity was reported in both the cavity geometry^[35,40] and the propagating geometry.^[62,63]

In conclusion, superfluidity is among the outstanding phenomena of the 20th century which allowed to make a great step forward in our understanding of the physics generally, and the many-body physics particularly. Thanks to all the brilliant physicists, the physical phenomena behind the effect of superfluidity are today well understood.

4.2 Probing superfluidity using a weakly perturbative obstacle

In Chapter 2, we have introduced an intuitive criterion for the determination of the behaviour of the fluid-of-light, mentioning briefly a technique to probe the superfluid transition in quantum fluids (subsection 2.3.3). There are also a few other techniques to identify light superfluidity, like the observation of non-dissipative shock-waves in a fluid-of-light^[146] and the characterisation of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation.^[62,63] In the following section, we will shed light on the technique we used to examine the superfluid behaviour of light, and the transition from a normal fluid to a superfluid of light. To get a good insight into the technique we suggest presenting it first in the frame of quantum fluids and thereafter in the optical frame.

4.2.1 Probing superfluidity in a quantum fluid

Let us consider a tank containing a quantum fluid. As mentioned in chapter 2, one of the techniques to probe the superfluid regime in a quantum fluid is by introducing a material cylinder on top of the fluid and

study the interaction between this latter and the cylinder. That is shown in figure 4.1.

The experiment consists in moving the cylinder on top of the fluid with a velocity v_s (by referential change one can interpret the experiment as the fluid flow around the obstacle with a velocity $-v_s$) and observe the impact of the obstacle on the quantum fluid.

Figure 4.1: Illustration of the transition from a frictional to a superfluid regime in a quantum fluid. A cylindrical material is driven on top of the quantum fluid. Panel (a) presents a quantum fluid exhibiting a non-superfluid regime $v_s > c_s$. Panel (b) shows a superfluid regime of the quantum fluid $v_s < c_s$.

Figure 4.1 presents two cases of a quantum fluid, namely, dissipative and superfluid regime. Driving the cylinder on top of the ordinary fluid naturally gives rise to the appearance of surface wave modulations excited by the interaction between the fluid and the cylinder. This phenomenon is illustrated in figure 4.1.(a). In contrast, for the superfluid case, Landau's theory predicts the non-existence of this surface wave modulation while driving the obstacle (see figure 4.1.(b)). This behaviour is conditioned by a driving velocity v_s lower than the sound velocity c_s (i.e. $v_s < c_s$). While in the case of $v_s > c_s$ the superfluid behaves like a normal fluid (see chapter 2). This behaviour is displayed in figure 4.1.(a).

A similar experiment was carried out to study the drag of liquid ^4He on a negative ion moving through the fluid. Here, the obstacle is the negative ion and the quantum fluid is liquid helium at a temperature 0.35 K.^[69]

In the context of atomic Bose gases, Ketterle et al. performed an experiment to study dissipation in a BEC gas through moving a laser beam on top of the condensate.^[9] Both of these experiments found a critical

velocity above which dissipation starts to take place in the quantum fluid.

To study the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light, we will make use of a similar principle.

4.2.2 Probing superfluidity in a fluid-of-light

Basic idea to probe superfluidity in a fluid-of-light Let us suppose the presence of a fluid-of-light. It is simply a laser beam propagating in a nonlinear medium under the paraxial approximation. We illustrate in

Figure 4.2: Illustration of the fluid-of-light beam propagating in a nonlinear medium along the z -axis (panel (a)). 2D (resp. 1D) spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam panel (b) (resp. panel (c)). The diameter at $1/e^2$ measures $270 \mu\text{m}$.

figure 4.2 a fluid-of-light beam propagating along the z -axis. It has a Gaussian profile shown in 2D (resp. 1D) in figure 4.2.(b) (resp. Fig.4.2.(c)), with a diameter at $1/e^2$ measuring $270 \mu\text{m}$.

The technique we suggest to probe light superfluidity consists in inserting an obstacle in the fluid-of-light and to study the interaction between the obstacle and the fluid-of-light. The illustration of this technique in terms of fluid mechanics is similar to a vessel containing a quantum fluid on top of which a material obstacle is driven. In our experiments, we build a similar system and through the Landau criterion we will be able to investigate and probe the superfluid transition of a fluid-of-light.

It is worth mentioning that the Landau criterion is related to the strength of the obstacle. Here we consider a weakly perturbative obstacle to probe the superfluid regime.^[147]

In quantum fluids, it is not difficult to get an obstacle. Generally, it might be a material obstacle with a certain mass and a certain shape introduced into the liquid. In the next paragraph we will shed light on the nature of the obstacle we use to investigate superfluidity of a fluid-of-light.

Bessel beam as an optical obstacle From the optical point of view, an obstacle is defined as an opaque body regarding the wavelength λ_0 of the laser beam. It is actually defined as a local drop of the refractive index (negative variation of the refractive index see chapter 3).

There are many ways to induce optical defects in a material. Among these ways we cite a technique based on the lithography^[148], also other techniques based on doping the bulk with chemicals^[149], and recently the photo-inscription of optical defects using a powerful pulsed laser^[150,151] through the nonlinear

absorption of the material. All these techniques allow to induce permanent defects in the bulk. Besides this, there is also the possibility to create non-permanent obstacles by taking advantage of the nonlinear properties of the medium. The basic idea is to use the photorefractive effect described in chapter 3, to photo-induce a refractive index change Δn by propagating a shape-controlled laser beam all along the crystal. The refractive index variation in this nonlinear medium is determined by the following expression:

$$\Delta n(I) = \Delta n_{\max} \frac{I/I_{\text{sat}}}{I/I_{\text{sat}} + 1} \quad (4.1)$$

where I is the intensity of the beam. Δn_{\max} is the maximum value of the refractive index¹⁰. To get a significant negative refractive index variation, one has to direct the external electric field in such a way to get a self-defocusing regime and to increase the strength of the parameters particularly, the external field and the laser beam intensity.

Figure 4.3: Figure of a nonlinear medium with a constant defect induced along the nonlinear crystal. $\Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})$ is the local variation of the refractive index. z the distance of propagation is equivalent to the time axis t . The refractive index change measures approximately $10 \mu\text{m}$ of diameter.

The experimental challenge that arises, is to set up an optical defect with micro-metric dimensions and remaining constant along the propagation direction (z -axis). This means that we have to maintain constant the width of the laser beam all over the length of the nonlinear medium L up to 10 mm as sketched by figure 4.3. The reason for the micro-metric scale is that the width of the obstacle should be in the order of magnitude of the healing length^[147] defined in chapter 2, which for its part measures approximately $10 \mu\text{m}$. As for the constant diameter, it is of an extreme importance to maintain it constant along the distance of propagation otherwise it would be equivalent to varying it in time.

A Gaussian beam does not fulfill these conditions. For example if we take a Gaussian beam with a diameter at $1/e^2$ equals $D = 20 \mu\text{m}$, its Rayleigh length calculated $z_R = \pi D^2 / 2\lambda \approx 1 \text{ mm}$ is very small compared to the propagation distance in the nonlinear medium $L = 10 \text{ mm}$. The Rayleigh range is the distance along which the diameter of a Gaussian beam is assumed to be constant, or at maximum varies with $(\sqrt{2} - 1)D$.

¹⁰See chapter 3 for more details

To solve this issue, Bessel beams are good candidates. The latter has an amplitude described by the Bessel function usually denoted by $J_m(r)$, where r is the 2D space coordinates. In our case, we use a beam described by the first kind Bessel function $J_0(r)$. One of the important properties of the Bessel beams is that they don't undergo diffraction during their propagation along a certain distance.^[152] This makes them adequate to be used as an optical obstacle in our experiment.

One way to generate a Bessel beam is by propagating a laser through an axicon lens (conical prism).^[153] Figure 4.4 shows the process of generating a Bessel beam through an axicon. Thanks to the phase accumulated in the axicon lens, the laser beam rays at the output of the lens interferes to form a Bessel beam shape.

Figure 4.4: A sketch of laser rays propagating through an axicon lens. z_D is the distance of the existence of the Bessel beam. α is the angle of conical prism and R is the radius at $1/e^2$ of the laser beam. The Bessel beam is generated right at the output of the axicon lens.

Right at the output of the axicon lens, a Bessel beam starts to form. Its intensity is given by the formula^[153]:

$$I(r, z) = \frac{[2\pi E]^2}{\lambda} \frac{R \sin(\beta)}{\cos^2(\beta)} J_0^2\left(\frac{2\pi r \sin(\beta)}{\lambda}\right), \quad (4.2)$$

where E^2 is the incident intensity on the axicon, R is the radius at $1/e^2$ of the incident beam, $r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2}$ is the radial coordinate, α and β are angles defined by the properties of the axicon lens, they allow defining the focus depth of the axicon lens $z_D = R[\tan^{-1}(\beta) - \tan(\alpha)]$. This distance refers simply to the existence range of the Bessel beam and is highly related to the radius of the beam. The angles α and β are related by the Snell-Descartes formula, $n \sin(\alpha) = \sin(\alpha + \beta)$, where n is the refractive index of the axicon lens.

The diameter of the Bessel beam D_{ob} is defined by its first zero. As a function of the axicon characteristics it is given analytically by setting the Bessel function $J_0(2\pi r \sin(\beta)/\lambda) = 0$. Restricting the condition only to the first zero gives the diameter as a function of λ and β such as $D_{ob} = 0.76\lambda/\beta$. From this formula, one observes that for a small β (resp. high α), the diameter of the Bessel beam is large (resp. small). Therefore, its focus depth z_D is high (resp. small). This means that the Bessel beam lasts for a longer distance of propagation and vice versa.

In our experiment, we do not make use of an axicon lens to generate Bessel beams. We use instead a spatial light modulator (SLM). This latter allows to simulate the behaviour of an axicon lens by changing the phase of the beam passing through it. We show on figure 4.5 the phase mask uploaded to the SLM in

Figure 4.5: The phase mask uploaded to the SLM in order to generate a Bessel beam. The axicon lens is equivalent to the phase mask.

order to generate a Bessel beam. Notice that the axicon lens looks like the phase mask seen in the (x,y) -plane. A description of the spatial light modulator is given in appendix B.A.1.

In figure 4.6, we show the evolution of the intensity distribution of a Bessel beam in the free-space over the length of the nonlinear medium¹¹. It was generated by means of an SLM. From figure 4.6, we can see

Figure 4.6: Figure of the intensity distribution Bessel beams in the reel space and their corresponding cuts along x -axis. (a), (b) and (c) represent respectively the Bessel beams at $z = 0$ mm, $z = 5$ mm and at $z = 10$ mm of the nonlinear medium. The Bessel beam diameter measures $16 \mu\text{m}$.

¹¹Note that the effective length of propagation l_{eff} is smaller than the length of propagation in free space $l_{\text{eff}} = z/n_e$, where n_e is the refractive index of the medium.

that the Bessel beam does not change along its propagation, particularly its diameter. The measurement of the latter from the input to the output of the nonlinear medium gives $D_b = 16 \pm 1 \mu\text{m}$. This value is comparable to the value of the healing length ξ introduced in chapter 2 which is of the order of $10 \mu\text{m}$. It is worth mentioning that a weakly perturbative obstacle with a diameter less than the healing length $D_{\text{ob}} \ll \xi$ does not exhibit any interaction with the fluid-of-light. If $D_{\text{ob}} \sim \xi$ an interaction between the fluid-of-light and obstacle takes place. In this case, one can make use of the Landau criterion to identify the superfluid regime of the fluid-of-light. If $D_{\text{ob}} \gg \xi$, then a turbulent regime of the fluid-of-light is expected to occur (see chapter 5).

Now that we introduced some important characteristics of the optical obstacle, we propose in the following section to investigate the concept of light superfluidity. Therefore, the questions one might ask are: *In analogy with quantum fluids what is the equivalent of surface wave excitation in optics? And how can we characterise the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light?*

4.2.3 Diffraction of a fluid-of-light over an obstacle

Probing superfluidity in fluids of light Before we give an answer to the previous questions, we have to make sure that we can carry out the experiment illustrated in figure 4.1 in the frame of nonlinear optics.

Figure 4.7: Sketch of a fluid-of-light (red beam) propagating through a nonlinear medium. Simultaneously an obstacle is induced in the nonlinear crystal by another laser beam (green laser). The fluid-of-light is defined by a certain velocity v and a sound velocity c_s .

A propagating laser beam in a nonlinear medium fulfils all the conditions to behave like a quantum fluid (see Chapter 2). We gave an effective mass to photons through ensuring the paraxial propagation of the laser; we introduced interactions between photons thanks to the nonlinearity of the medium; we derived the expressions necessary to describe light as a fluid and finally, we showed how to introduce an optical obstacle in the nonlinear medium. Thus, all the needed ingredients are controlled in the experiment to study superfluidity in the optical frame. Concerning the control of the fluid-of-light beam, we provide later a detailed description about its control.

A sketch of the fluid-of-light beam propagation is displayed in figure 4.7. We propagate through a nonlinear self-defocusing medium (SBN crystal) a laser beam (red beam) assuming the role of the fluid-of-light. Simultaneously, we induce a local drop of the refractive index (obstacle) along the axis of propagation (z -axis) by means of the green laser beam (Bessel beam) (see figure 4.7).

According to the Landau criterion, the determination of the superfluid regime of light suggests to vary two main parameters: the transverse velocity of the fluid-of-light denoted by v and its sound velocity c_s . These parameters are controlled respectively by the gradient of the phase in the transverse plane $\nabla_{\perp} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, z)$ and the nonlinear variation of the refractive index Δn induced by the fluid-of-light, which for its part depends on the intensity of the fluid-of-light denoted by I (see chapter 3 for more details about the refractive index variation Δn).

Diffraction of a fluid-of-light To answer the previous questions about light superfluidity. We suggest to picture the consequences of the experiment sketched in figure 4.7.

In a linear medium, when a light beam strikes an obstacle, it undergoes the natural diffraction effect. In a nonlinear medium, if we are able to control the transverse velocity v and the sound velocity c_s of the fluid-of-light (see chapter 2) in such a way to obtain $v < c_s$, then we can manage to suppress the natural diffraction pattern. While in the opposite case $v > c_s$ the diffraction pattern remains present. This phenomenon is analogous in quantum fluids to the absence (existence) of surface wave modulation when driving an obstacle on top of the quantum fluid.

Therefore, we refer to as a *superfluid regime of light* the absence of the diffraction pattern when light encounters an obstacle. And as a *frictional (non-superfluid, dissipative)*³ regime the occurrence of this diffraction.

The superfluid/frictional behaviour of light in the propagating geometry has been studied numerically by I. Carusotto.^[66] He simulated the transition from a superfluid regime of light to a frictional one thanks to the variation of the strength of the nonlinearity as well as to the transverse velocity of the fluid-of-light (chap.2). Calculating the near-field intensity of the fluid-of-light beam after a certain propagation length gives the result presented in figure 4.8.

Figure 4.8: Simulation of the transition from a superfluid regime (panel (c)) of a dissipative regimes (panels (b) and (a)) in fluids of light^[66]

³Note that the words dissipative and frictional do not mean the loss or the absorption in the nonlinear medium. Here, we use this terms to refer to the analogies between hydrodynamics and nonlinear optics.

Figure 4.8 reveals clearly a superfluid character of light displayed in the picture 4.8.(a). Here, the fluid-of-light flows from left to right as indicated by the white arrow. The dark point on the middle marks the position of the obstacle. In this figure, one observes similarly to quantum fluids for a transverse velocity $v < c_s$, that the fluid-of-light does not exhibit any diffraction pattern at the output of the nonlinear medium. On the contrary, in the opposite limit $v > c_s$ (i.e. fig. 4.8.(b)) and $v \gg c_s$ (i.e. 4.8.(c)), the beam undergoes diffraction because of its interaction with the obstacle (non-superfluid regime).

Figure 4.9: Figure of superfluidity/frictional transition in a semi-conductor microcavity system (polariton). The yellow arrow indicates the direction of the fluid-of-light flow.^[40] The pictures I, II and III are respectively the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light in the frictional, transitional and superfluid regimes. Images IV, V and VI represent the intensity distribution in the (k_x, k_y) space.

Experimentally, this behaviour was previously reported in cavity systems (see chapter 2.2.1 for a few details on these systems).^[35,40] Figure 4.9 displays the measured intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light (polariton gas) flowing from up to down. One observes in Fig.4.9.I the occurrence of the diffraction pattern in the vicinity the obstacle (non-superfluid regime). A transitional regime is depicted in 4.9.II and the superfluid regime of polaritons is shown in panel 4.9.III manifested in the disappearance of the diffraction pattern. Right below are represented the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light in the far-field representation. The superfluid regime of polaritons is manifested in the shrinkage (Fig. 4.9.V) and the collapse (Fig.4.9.VI) of the scattering ring.

4.2.4 Optical parameters to probe the superfluid transition

In the preceding section, we have provided a definition of light superfluidity; we have also presented the intensity distribution of a superfluid light past an obstacle. In this section, we propose to introduce the key parameters allowing to monitor the behaviour of the fluid-of-light.

According to the Landau criterion, it is the comparison between the velocity v of the fluid-of-light and its sound velocity c_s which allows to examine the transition to superfluidity. We have established in Chapter 2 the expressions of the sound velocity for a fluid-of-light. We have pointed out that the speed of sound depends substantially on the nonlinearity of the medium. Therefore, making use of a nonlinear photorefractive medium and in the case of kerr-like type regime (i.e. $I \ll I_{\text{sat}}$), we showed that the sound velocity of the fluid-of-light is expressed as:

$$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{|\Delta n(I)|}{n_e}}, \quad (4.3)$$

where n_e is the bulk refractive index along the extraordinary axis (see chapter 3). The variation of the refractive index $\Delta n(I)$ in the case of Kerr-like regime induced by the fluid-of-light beam linearly polarised along the c -axis is given by:

$$\Delta n(I) \approx -(1/2)n_e^3 r_{33} E_{\text{ext}} \frac{I}{I_{\text{sat}}}, \quad (4.4)$$

where I is the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam, r_{33} , I_{sat} and E_{ext} are respectively the electro-optic coefficient, the saturation intensity and the external field applied by the electrodes on the sides of the nonlinear crystal c -axis. These quantities are fully described in chapter 3. However, it is worth reminding that the saturation intensity I_{sat} is controlled by means of an incoherent light shone onto the photorefractive crystal. Fixing the amount of power of the incoherent light allows to control accurately the saturation intensity and keep it constant, which is the case in our measurements of light superfluidity.

According to equation (4.4) and to the study presented in chapter 3, the variation of the refractive index $\Delta n(I)$ induced by the fluid-of-light intensity ranges from 0 to 2.4×10^{-4} . Thus, the corresponding sound velocity ranges from 0 to 8×10^{-3} . We remind that c_s is a dimensionless quantity as explained in chapter 2.

Figure 4.10: Variation of the refractive index and of the speed of sound versus the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam I . The refractive index change exhibits clearly a saturable behaviour. The grey box represents the accessible experimental values.

We display in figure 4.10 the curves of the Δn and c_s as a function of the fluid-of-light intensity I . We observe on the figure that Δn saturates at a certain value of the fluid-of-light intensity. That is an expected behaviour for the photorefractive nonlinearity (see chapter 3). Let us explain this figure clearly, as pointed out in chapter 2, we cannot define a speed of sound when the index of refraction saturates. That is why we represent $c_s(I)$ to a certain value corresponding to the limit of the Kerr-like regime. The grey box in the figure represents the accessible values in the experiment and corresponds to a Kerr-like regime of the nonlinearity. While the blue box corresponds to the saturated regime of the photorefractive nonlinearity.

Let us define now the velocity of the fluid-of-light. Physically, it corresponds to the transverse velocity of the laser beam (according to chap. 2). It is given by:

$$v_s(\mathbf{r}, z) = (1/n_e k_0) \nabla_{\perp} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, z) \quad (4.5)$$

The fluid-of-light beam has a Gaussian shape considered very large regarding the width of the obstacle. Therefore, it is assumed to be a plane wave in the vicinity of the obstacle. Additionally, the propagation of the light beam is done along the z -axis with an angle within the (z, x) -plane. Hence, the wave vector \mathbf{k} of the laser beam possesses only two components along z and x axes ($\mathbf{k}_y = \mathbf{0}$). Therefore, the phase of the beam $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, z)$ is expressed as follows (see figure 4.11):

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}, z) = \varphi(\mathbf{x}, z) = \mathbf{k}_x \cdot \mathbf{x} + \mathbf{k}_z \cdot z \quad (4.6)$$

Figure 4.11: A 2D geometric representation of a plane wave propagating in the (z, x) plan panel(a). \mathbf{k} is the wave vector and \mathbf{k}_x (resp. \mathbf{k}_z) are its projections along x (resp. z).

Figure 4.11 illustrates the propagation of a plane wave with an angle of incidence θ_{in} with respect to the propagation axis z . Using the expression of the phase gradient (eq. (4.5)), the transverse velocity of the laser beam becomes:

$$v = \frac{1}{n_e k_0} k_x \quad (4.7)$$

It can be written for a plane wave under the assumption of the paraxial propagation as :

$$v = \frac{\sin \theta_{in}}{n_e} \approx \frac{\theta_{in}}{n_e} \quad (4.8)$$

Note that the velocity of the fluid-of-light is a dimensionless quantity as explained in chapter 2. Depending on the experimental conditions, the angle of incidence θ_{in} ranges from 0 to 25 mrad.

In conclusion, the fluid-of-light velocity v is controlled by the angle of incidence of the laser and the sound velocity is controlled via the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. To mediate the transition between the superfluid/frictional regime of light, we vary the ratio v/c_s through the angle of incidence θ_{in} and the intensity of the beam I . We express the ratio v/c_s (also called the Mach number) as follows:

$$\frac{v}{c_s} = \theta_{\text{in}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_e \Delta n(I)}} \quad (4.9)$$

From the above expression, one notices that the Mach number v/c_s varies differently when changing the angle or changing the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. The experimentally accessible range of the ratio v/c_s is defined from 0 to ≈ 6 . It is important to mention that the transition from the frictional to the superfluid regime should normally occur at $v/c_s \approx 1$. And since the ratio v/c_s ranges from 0 to 6, then we surely expect to visualise the superfluid transition.

So far, we have presented a technique to identify the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light and we showed how to probe the superfluid transition through controlling the velocity v and the sound velocity c_s of the fluid-of-light. Before we expose the results of light superfluidity, we suggest in the next subsection presenting the experimental set-up pointing as well its limitations.

4.2.5 Experimental set-up

Experimental set-up In this paragraph we give a brief description of the experimental set-up used to investigate the superfluid behaviour of light. However, for a full description we refer the reader to appendix B.A.1.

The nonlinear medium consists in a $5 \times 5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ strontium barium niobate (SBN:61) photorefractive crystal additionally doped with cerium 0.01% to enhance its photoconductivity^[154] albeit it induces linear absorption (3.2 dB.cm^{-1}).

Making use of a spatial light modulator, we produce a diffraction-free Bessel beam ($\lambda_{\text{ob}} = 523 \text{ nm}$, $I_{\text{ob}} = 7.6$

Figure 4.12: Sketch of the experimental set-up used to investigate the superfluid behaviour of light. A red CW laser beam is emitted from a He-Ne laser and plays the role of the fluid-of-light beam. Its rotation is controlled by the wavefront shaping module. A green beam is emitted from a solid-state laser assuming the role of the obstacle. Both beams are detected using an sCMOS camera.

$\text{W.cm}^{-2} \gg I_{\text{sat}}$), green path in Fig. 4.12. The latter creates the obstacle with a radius of $16 \mu\text{m}$ (comparable

to the healing length of the system $\xi = 10 \mu\text{m}$). The propagation of the obstacle beam into the crystal induces a local drop $\Delta n(I_{\text{ob}}) = -2.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$ in the refractive index. A second laser ($\lambda_f = 633 \text{ nm}$, red path in Fig. 4.12) delivers a Gaussian beam whose radius is extended to $270 \mu\text{m}$ and which corresponds to the fluid-of-light beam. Both laser beams are linearly-polarized along the extraordinary axis to maximize the photorefractive effect. We vary the flow velocity v by changing the input angle θ_{in} of the fluid-of-light beam with respect to the propagation axis z (see Fig. 4.12). The accessible range, tuned by rotating a mirror imaged at the input of the crystal via a telescope, goes from $\theta_{\text{in}} 0$ to $\pm 25 \text{ mrad}$, corresponding to v ranging from $v = 0$ to $v = \pm 1.05 \cdot 10^{-2}$. The sound velocity c_s is controlled by the input intensity of the beam which can be tuned from $I = 0$ to $350 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ via a half-waveplate and a polariser. The maximum value for c_s is $6.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$. For the detection part, a $\times 20$ microscope objective and an sCMOS camera allow to get the spatial distribution of the near-field intensity of the beams at the output of the crystal.

Limitations of the propagating geometry experiment The experiment of the propagating geometry for the study of light superfluidity presents plenty of positive points discussed previously. However, it also suffers from few limitations that we discuss in this paragraph.

Among the limitations we faced in the experiment is the propagation distance z . Since we have a crystal length of 10 mm , the time flow of the fluid-of-light is limited $t = (n_e/c)z$. This restricts the observation at the high time flow of the fluid-of-light. For example, studying vortex dynamics at a particularly higher time flow might be unachievable. Therefore, for this purpose, we need to have higher propagating lengths, or we need to develop a feedback technique to reinject the preceding output of the medium.^[61] However, this technique is limited to few feedbacks.

Another limiting quantity is the angle of incidence of the fluid-of-light beam. In the experiment we have noticed that there is an angle of incidence θ_{in} (fluid velocity v) above which the interaction between the fluid-of-light and the obstacle does not take place. The reasons for this are on the one hand, the flow velocity becomes high in such a way that the fluid-of-light flows rapidly and does not feel the presence of the obstacle. On the other hand, fluid-of-light systems in the propagating geometry are considered in the frame of the paraxial approximation, which deals with small angles of incidence.

One more limiting point in the experiment is the obstacle beam (Bessel). As stressed earlier, the obstacle is photo-induced through the nonlinear effect thanks to the self-defocusing regime of the photorefractive medium. The reason for which we choose a Bessel beam was mentioned previously in this chapter, since this latter follows a Bessel function with secondary lobes (rings in 2D space). These lobes in the highly perturbative regime are also photo-induced in the crystal making them as undesirable obstacles for the fluid-of-light. This problem does not take place in the weakly perturbative regime of the obstacle (for probing light superfluidity) because the power of the beam is sufficiently low such that only the principal lobe is photo-induced in the crystal. We will present later in Chapter 5 this issue because we consider a strong defect.

4.3 Results and discussion

So far, we have provided the necessary tools to probe and visualise the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light. In this section, we first expose the results of the superfluid transition through the observation of the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam. Thereafter, we tackle in this section the concept of

the optical analogue drag-force.

Let us remind that the key parameter allowing the control of the superfluid transition is the ratio v/c_s , which as explained earlier is controlled via the angle of incidence and the intensity of the fluid-of-light.

4.3.1 Diffraction suppression in the intensity distribution

The fluid-of-light beam propagates in the nonlinear crystal within the presence of the obstacle. We present in the following figures the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light in the near-field and its cut along the x -axis above each picture. In these sets of measurement, we vary the sound velocity in the fluid-of-light beam from $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $8 \cdot 10^{-3}$, while its angle of incidence θ_{in} varies from 3 mrad to 23 mrad. This allows the Mach number v/c_s to range from 0.15 to 4.8.

One way to probe light superfluidity is by maintaining a fixed velocity of the fluid-of-light v and varying its sound velocity c_s . Figure 4.13 is obtained for a velocity fixed at $v = 4.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and a sound velocity of the fluid-of-light ranging from $2 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $8 \cdot 10^{-3}$. This defines an interval of the Mach number from 0.52 to 2.1.

Figure 4.13: Figure of the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light visualised in the near-field (crystal's output) for various values of the ratio v/c_s . Here the velocity of the fluid-of-light is fixed at $v = 4.23 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the fluid-of-light intensity is variable. We represent above each figure its corresponding normalised intensity along the x -axis. The white arrow indicates the direction of the flow. The white crosses on the middle mark the position of the obstacle.

From intensity distributions of figure 4.13, one observes clearly on panels 4.13.(a) and 4.13.(b) a superfluid behaviour of the fluid-of-light manifested in the absence of the diffraction pattern upstream of the

obstacle. The position of this latter is indicated by a white cross in all the pictures. The x -cuts of the fluid-of-light intensity distribution are plotted above to display the symmetry of the spatial intensity in the vicinity of the obstacle. Thus, a symmetrical intensity distribution is revealed by the panels (a) and (b) of the figure.

Decreasing the intensity I of the fluid-of-light beam (i.e. increasing v/c_s) results in the creation of an asymmetry in the x -cuts and the beginning of the diffraction pattern formation upstream of the obstacle. That is depicted in Fig. 4.13.(c). It represents the transition between the superfluid regime and the frictional one. If we keep increasing the ratio v/c_s a clear diffraction pattern forms upstream of the obstacle and the corresponding x -cuts become totally asymmetric. This is what we have defined previously as the frictional regime of the fluid-of-light. This behaviour is displayed on figures 4.13(d)-(h). Notice on the pictures that the breakdown of the superfluid regime occurs below the value $v/c_s \approx 1$ predicted previously by the Landau criterion (see chapter 2). This behaviour in our system is attributed to two factors, the first one is the obstacle which is not a point-like object^[147], and the second factor is the linear absorption induced by the medium (SBN crystal).

Figure 4.14: Figure of the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light visualised in the near-field (crystal's output) for various values of the ratio v/c_s . Here the sound velocity of the fluid-of-light is fixed at $c_s = 8 \cdot 10^{-3}$, the fluid-of-light velocity is variable.

Another way to probe the fluid-of-light behaviour is by maintaining the sound velocity c_s constant and varying the flow velocity v . This set of measurement (Fig. 4.14) was obtained for $c_s = 8 \cdot 10^{-3}$ and a velocity varying from $1.68 \cdot 10^{-3}$ to $10.92 \cdot 10^{-3}$, allowing the Mach number v/c_s to range from 0.21 to 1.36. We display in figure 4.14 the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light and the corresponding x -cuts. The

first three images (i.e. 4.14(a)-(c)) display a clear superfluid behaviour, while the set of images 4.14(d)-(h) present a frictional behaviour of the fluid-of-light.

Notice that the period of the diffraction pattern increases when approaching the superfluid transition and the minimum measured period gives an idea about the value of the healing length of the system ξ . In figure 4.14.(f) (i.e. $I = 150 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$), the measured period is $8 \mu\text{m}$ which is close to the calculated value of $\xi(150) = 7.03 \mu\text{m}$ (see figure 4.15). However, one should not mix these two distinct quantities. In this measurement, we kept the sound velocity c_s invariant, this means that the healing length is invariant as well. However, the period of the diffraction pattern increases clearly when the fluid-of-light is near the superfluid transition.

In order to have an idea about the healing length of the system, we present in figure 4.15 the variation of ξ as a function of the intensity I of the fluid-of-light beam by considering the parameters of the experiment. In our set of measurement, the healing length ranges from 6 to $\approx 20 \mu\text{m}$ and declines with the increase of the beam's intensity. A further study aiming to measure experimentally the healing length ξ is presented in chapter 5.

Figure 4.15: Theoretical variation of the healing length ξ versus the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. The value 7.03 corresponds to a healing length calculated for the value of $I = 150 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$

As a resume to the previous set of measurements, the behaviour of the fluid-of-light has been studied through the observation of its intensity distribution. And we have seen that the breakdown of superfluidity occurs nearly at 0.6 where the diffraction pattern starts forming in the vicinity of the obstacle. The observation of the near-field spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light gives a good qualitative way to probe the superfluidity transition. However, in order to be more quantitative, we also managed to study the so-called optical analogue of the drag-force experienced by the obstacle. Therefore, in the next section, we suggest defining the concept of the optical drag-force. And thereafter an experimental study based on this force is presented.

4.4 Optical drag force

We mean by the drag-force in fluid mechanics a resistance force created on the walls of an object, that acts conversely to the motion of the fluid flow (or the motion of the object inside the fluid). If a fluid flows in a

tank, in which we introduce an obstacle we notice, depending on the flow velocity and the geometry of the obstacle, that this latter experiences a force leading to a mechanical deformation of the object because of its friction with the surrounding fluid. The expression of the drag force in fluid mechanics depends on the type of the flow (Laminar or turbulent flows); it is given for a laminar flow by:

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 A C_D, \quad (4.10)$$

where ρ is the density of the fluid, v is the relative speed of the obstacle, C_D is the drag coefficient depending on the fluid viscosity as well as v itself. And A is the cross section between the fluid and the obstacle.

The vanishing drag force between an object and the surrounding fluid remains among the strongest signatures of superfluidity. This property has been studied in genuine systems (liquid helium).^[69] However, few investigated this feature in analogue systems. In quantum fluids a great majority of works focused on the influence of the obstacle on the fluid by studying the density modulation taking place at the surface of the fluid. The influence of the superfluid (atomic Bose gas) on the obstacle was theoretically investigated^[147,155–157], where they have studied the motion of a point-like obstacle on top of a BEC. By solving the GPE, they have calculated the drag force taking place at the supersonic regime of the quantum fluid. Also, experimentally a study of a Bose-gas superfluidity using a moving obstacle was reported.^[158] However, a direct measurement of the drag-force experienced by the obstacle was not investigated.

Figure 4.16: Figure of an obstacle immersed in a nonlinear liquid. The fluid-of-light beam propagates through the nonlinear medium. l_z , l_x and χ_s are respectively the length, the thickness and the susceptibility of the solid obstacle. $\zeta(z, y)$ is the bending of the obstacle. From^[159]

By analogy with quantum fluids, we can define an optical quantity analogous to the hydrodynamical definition of the drag-force. This was investigated theoretically^[160–162] in the frame of the polaritonic systems. Concerning the propagating geometry, the first suggestion to measure the drag-force was reported in 2015.^[159] The idea is to introduce a material obstacle of a certain permittivity in a nonlinear liquid, to send the fluid-of-light beam into the nonlinear medium and thus to measure the mechanical deformation of the obstacle induced by radiation pressure^[163] with respect to the ratio v/c_s . Figure 4.16 extracted from^[159] illustrates the bending of the material obstacle induced by the laser beam propagating into the nonlinear medium with a fixed incidence angle.

According to^[159], we can define the optical analogue drag-force as a quantity proportional to the difference of the fluid-of-light intensity upstream I_- and downstream I_+ of the obstacle. It is expressed by the following relation:

$$F \propto |I_+ - I_-| \quad (4.11)$$

In order to relate the optical drag-force (4.11) to superfluidity, an intuitive simplified interpretation can be considered. In fact, in the superfluid regime light is expected to propagate without exhibiting a disturbance upstream of the obstacle. This means in terms of the optical drag-force that the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam has a symmetric distribution around the obstacle. Hence, the intensities upstream and downstream of the obstacle are nearly equal $I_+ \approx I_-$. Whereas, in the non-superfluid regime, an asymmetry in the intensity distribution takes place. This is expressed by $I_+ \neq I_-$.

The suggested idea for measuring the optical drag-force^[159] considers a physical object inserted in the medium. Therefore, a displacement exhibited by the obstacle involves only the radiation pressure^[164,165] exerted by the fluid-of-light. The experiment we suggest for tracking light superfluidity consists in a non-physical obstacle (light induced obstacle). Thus, a radiation pressure force can not apply by the fluid-of-light in this case. We detail this situation in next section.

4.4.1 Optical drag force - the shape of the fluid-of-light and the displacement of the obstacle

The optical drag-force calculation Being the difference of the fluid-of-light's intensity upstream and downstream of the obstacle, the optical drag force denoted by $F \propto I_+ - I_-$ appears to be analogous to the dielectric force experienced by a material obstacle^[159] in a nonlinear medium. This force seems to be closely analogous to the drag force applied by a flowing BEC on a material obstacle. Therefore, in our system we make use of this quantity to study the superfluid transition in a fluid-of-light.

Figure 4.17: Illustration of the integration area to measure the intensity of the fluid-of-light upstream I_- and downstream the obstacle I_+ . The integration areas is chosen to be of the order of the healing length ξ .

To illustrate the procedure of extracting the optical analogue drag force, we represent in figure 4.17 the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam at the output of the nonlinear medium. The position of the obstacle is indicated by the middle dark circle. We calculate I_+ , (I_-) respectively, by integrating the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light downstream (upstream) (bright regions) of the obstacle as shown by the figure. The integration area is chosen to be in the order of the healing length ξ .

Figure 4.18: x -cuts of the fluid-of-light beam intensity distribution in the superfluid (resp. frictional) represented in (a) (resp. (b)). In the superfluid regime I_+ and I_- are approximately equal, while in the frictional regime $I_- > I_+$. The dark grey box indicates the position of the obstacle within the 1D intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam.

To get an insight into the drag-force, we represent respectively in figures 4.18(a) and (b) the typical x -cuts of the spatial intensity distributions of pictures 4.13.(a) and (h), where the fluid-of-light exhibits a superfluid behaviour on 4.13.(a) and a frictional regime on 4.13.(f).

In Fig. 4.18.(a) the fluid-of-light is a superfluid. One easily observes on this figure that the intensity distribution is symmetric around the obstacle. Therefore, the calculation of I_+ and I_- gives approximately close values $I_+ \approx I_-$. Hence, the optical analogue drag-force in this situation is roughly equal to zero ($F = I_+ - I_- \approx 0$). In figure 4.18.(b), one can see that the intensity distribution is not symmetric around the obstacle. Therefore, the calculation of the drag force gives directly a quantity that differs from zero ($|I_+ - I_-| > 0$). In this situation, the fluid-of-light exerts a drag-force on the obstacle.

So far, we have presented a method to calculate the optical drag-force from the images of the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light. However, we have not yet investigated the consequences of the optical drag-force on the obstacle. This is the goal of the next paragraph.

Displacement of the obstacle as a consequence of the drag-force and the shape of the fluid-of-light

A remarkable consequence of the intensity distribution asymmetry is the possibility to observe a concrete displacement of the obstacle (Bessel beam). Since the latter is an optically induced obstacle, it is expected to undergo a displacement when the drag-force differs from zero. From the optical point of view, we attribute this displacement in the supersonic regime to the intensity modulation around the obstacle (see figure 4.18.(b), which leads to a local modification of the refractive index thanks to the nonlinearity of the medium. The obstacle being an optically induced defect, is sensitive to the local modulation of the refractive index and exhibits a tendency to move to higher refractive indices, corresponding to lower intensity regions of the

fluid-of-light beam, thanks to the self-defocusing effect. In the subsonic regime, the intensity modulation does not take place. This means that the local refractive index modulation due to the diffraction pattern does not take place (see Fig. 4.18.(a)). Hence, no displacement is expected from the obstacle.

Figure 4.19: Figure of the normalised refractive index variation induced by a Gaussian beam shape versus the x coordinate.

However, one should remember that the fluid-of-light has a Gaussian shape. Therefore, in the non-saturating regime (i.e. Kerr-type nonlinearity), the refractive index change induced by the fluid-of-light has also a Gaussian shape (see figure 4.19). This characteristic might induce an additional displacement of the obstacle, if the position of the latter is not placed at the center of the Gaussian potential $\Delta n(I)$, where I is the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. To resume, the expected displacement of the obstacle has two origins:

- first, the *intensity modulation of the fluid-of-light surrounding the obstacle* due to the frictional/superfluid regimes. In this case, we say that the displacement of the obstacle is due solely to the **drag-force**.
- second, the *Gaussian shape of the fluid-of-light*. In this case, we say that the displacement of the obstacle is due to the **Gaussian potential induced by the fluid-of-light**. This displacement is an unwanted effect, which should be avoided.

We illustrate these effects in Fig. 4.20. The latter shows that the total displacement exhibited by the obstacle (Fig. 4.20.(a)) is the sum of the displacements induced by the drag-force (Fig. 4.20.(c)) and by the Gaussian potential denoted by $\Delta n(I)$ (Fig. 4.20.(b)). To understand why we have the contribution of the Gaussian potential, we suggest to picture the experiment of light superfluidity (Fig. 4.21).

One should know that introducing an angle on the fluid-of-light leads to the transverse translation of the potential (Δn induced by the fluid-of-light) along the propagation into the nonlinear medium, as depicted by Fig. 4.21.(b) and (c). We illustrate on figures 4.21.(d)-(e) the process of the supplemental displacement of the obstacle due solely to the Gaussian potential. Figure 4.21.(d) displays the position of the obstacle (grey box) within the surrounding potential. When the obstacle is centered on the Gaussian potential, no

Figure 4.20: Illustration of the processes responsible for the displacement of the obstacle. Panel (a) represents the obstacle’s displacement process due to frictional/superfluid regimes + Gaussian beam shape. Panel (b) is the displacement process due only to the Gaussian and panel (c) is the displacement due only to the frictional/superfluid regimes.

Figure 4.21: Figure of the fluid-of-light and the Bessel beams. The figure displays the position of the obstacle regarding the fluid-of-light from the input to the output of the crystal when the fluid-of-light is shifted.

displacement takes place. This is because the local variation of the refractive index in the vicinity of the obstacle is homogeneous ($\Delta n(x^+) = \Delta n(x^-)$). In contrast, when the obstacle is not centered on the Gaussian

potential (i.e. Figs. 4.21.(e) and (f)), then it starts to feel the inhomogeneity of the surrounding potential ($\Delta n(x^+) > \Delta n(x^-)$), leading to the transverse displacement of the obstacle into the regions of higher refractive index.

Notice that this displacement has nothing to do with the superfluid/frictional regimes of the fluid-of-light. This means that this displacement occurs even though the fluid-of-light beam does not interact with the obstacle. This is an important point which allows us to characterise independently the displacement of the obstacle due only to the Gaussian potential. This can be achieved through propagating linearly the obstacle beam (Bessel beam) in such a way that no refractive index variation is induced by the obstacle beam $\Delta n(I_{\text{ob}}) \approx 0$, where I_{ob} is the intensity of the obstacle beam.

To study the superfluid transition of the fluid-of-light using the obstacle's displacement, we should be able to extract the displacement associated only to the drag-force. For this purpose, we should characterise solely the effect of the Gaussian potential on the obstacle. That is the goal of later paragraphs. Before doing so, we suggest in the next paragraph to model using the Ehrenfest theorem, the displacement of the optical obstacle propagating linearly into the medium and in the presence of a Gaussian potential.

4.4.2 Displacement of the obstacle in a Gaussian potential

Optical analogue of the Ehrenfest theorem The Ehrenfest theorem relates the expectation value of a force $F = -dV/dx$ applied on massive particle moving in a scalar potential to the time derivative of the expectation values of the position x and momentum p .^[166]

$$m \frac{d}{dt} \langle x \rangle = \langle p \rangle, \quad \frac{d}{dt} \langle p \rangle = - \left\langle \frac{\partial}{\partial x} V(x) \right\rangle \quad (4.12)$$

The equation that describes the motion of a massive particle as a function of time in a potential is the time-dependent Schrödinger equation. It is given by:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi = - \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \Delta \psi + V(x,t) \psi \quad (4.13)$$

ψ is the wave function of the particle and Δ is the transverse Laplacian operator. The Hamiltonian of this system is expressed by $H = p^2/2m + V(x,t)$.

To express the optical analogue of the Ehrenfest theorem, we should recall the propagation equation of a laser beam into a nonlinear medium. However, here we have two beams (the fluid-of-light and the obstacle beam) propagating in the nonlinear medium. Therefore the equation of propagation of the obstacle beam can be expressed as follows:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} E_{\text{ob}} = - \frac{1}{2n_e k_{\text{ob}}} \nabla^2 E_{\text{ob}} - k_{\text{ob}} [\Delta n(I) + \Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})] E_{\text{ob}}, \quad (4.14)$$

where k_{ob} is the wave number of the light beam responsible for the obstacle, $\Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})$ is the nonlinear refractive index induced by the obstacle beam, $I_{\text{ob}} = |E_{\text{ob}}|^2$ being the intensity of the obstacle light beam and $\Delta n(I)$ is the potential induced by the fluid-of-light beam. In analogy with the time-dependent Schrödinger equation, one can express the Hamiltonian of the nonlinear wave equation (4.14) in the following form:

$$H(x, k_{\perp}, z) = \frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2n_e k_{\text{ob}}} - k_{\text{ob}} [\Delta n(I) + \Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})], \quad (4.15)$$

where k_{\perp} is the transverse momentum of the obstacle beam. Denoting by $\langle x \rangle = \int x I_{\text{ob}} \cdot dx$ the position of the obstacle's beam centroid, and using equation (4.12), the optical analogue of the Ehrenfest theorem can be expressed as follows:

$$(n_e k_{\text{ob}}) \frac{d}{dz} \langle x \rangle = \langle k_{\perp} \rangle \quad (4.16)$$

$$\frac{d}{dz} \langle k_{\perp} \rangle = \left\langle k_{\text{ob}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Delta n(I) + \Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})] \right\rangle, \quad (4.17)$$

These equations lead to one equation expressing the motion of the obstacle's beam centroid position as a function of the potential (i.e. the refractive index change):

$$(n_e) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \langle x \rangle = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Delta n(I) + \Delta n(I_{\text{ob}})] \quad (4.18)$$

One can see that this equation comprises the potential induced by the fluid-of-light beam as well as the potential created by the obstacle beam itself. The second one can be neglected because as we said before, the propagation of the obstacle beam is linear in that specific study, and thus $\Delta n(I_{\text{ob}}) \approx 0$. Therefore, we can simplify the previous equation:

$$(n_e) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} \langle x \rangle = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} [\Delta n(I)]. \quad (4.19)$$

So far, we have derived an optical version of the Ehrenfest theorem that allows to predict the position of the obstacle beam in a certain potential. In the next paragraph we suggest to experimentally characterise the obstacle's beam displacement in the fluid-of-light assumed to be at rest $v = 0$ (i.e. $\theta_{\text{in}} = 0$).

Displacement of the obstacle beam in a fluid-of-light at rest This measurement consists in propagating a Bessel beam (obstacle) linearly in such a way that no variation of the refractive index is induced in the crystal. Simultaneously, we propagate the fluid-of-light beam responsible for the potential $\Delta n(I)$. We consider the fluid to be at rest $v = 0$, so its angle of incidence is zero $\theta_{\text{in}} = 0$. Therefore, the procedure to characterise the displacement, is by translating the potential beam (fluid) in the transverse plane (x -axis) without changing its incidence angle, and study the induced obstacle beam displacement at the output of the medium.

Assuming that the linear absorption in the medium is negligible (i.e. $\Delta n(I)$ is independent of z), the integration of equation (4.19) over the propagation length z yields to:

$$\langle x(z) \rangle - x_0 = \frac{1}{2n_e} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Delta n(I) \right] z^2, \quad (4.20)$$

where x_0 is the initial position of the obstacle beam. Equation (4.20) allows to predict the position of the obstacle in the potential $\Delta n(I)$ as a function of the propagation length in the nonlinear medium.

The Gaussian beam considered has a diameter of $270 \mu\text{m}$ at half-width $1/e^2$. Its intensity varies from 44 mW.cm^{-2} to 349 mW.cm^{-2} . The displacement of the obstacle beam is measured at the output of the nonlinear crystal relatively to its initial position x_0 (at the input of the crystal) within the fluid-of-light beam. The position along the crystal is denoted by $\langle x(z) \rangle$ and the relative transverse displacement regarding the

Figure 4.22: Illustration of the obstacle's displacement because of the Gaussian potential. Panel a. When the obstacle beam is in the center of the Gaussian potential no displacement is expected. Panel b. The obstacle beam is placed at $200 \mu\text{m}$ the measured displacement d at the output of the crystal is of the order of $207.8 \mu\text{m}$. Panel c. the obstacle is placed in $-200 \mu\text{m}$.

initial position is expressed by $d(z) = \langle x(z) \rangle - x_0$ (see figure 4.22). In this figure, we illustrate the process of the obstacle's displacement as a function of the Gaussian potential.

In figure 4.22.(a), the obstacle is placed at the center of the fluid-of-light, in this case the obstacle beam does not shift along the propagation into the medium. Placing the obstacle in the left side Fig. 4.22.(b) (resp. right side Fig. 4.22.(b)) of the Gaussian potential induces a shift of the obstacle. As explained earlier, this shift can be calculated using equation (4.20), and we write $d(z) = \langle x(z) \rangle - x_0$. The displacement at the output is practically measured, such as $d = d(z = L)$, where L is the length of the nonlinear medium.

The measurement of the transverse displacement d as a function of the initial position x_0 is displayed in figure 4.23. In this figure we plot the deviation of the obstacle beam as a function of its initial position within the Gaussian potential $\Delta n(I)$. For an initial position of the obstacle beam $x_0 = 200 \mu\text{m}$ and an intensity of the fluid-of-light $I = 175 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ the measured deviation at the output of the crystal $d = 7.8 \mu\text{m}$. A

similar displacement is exhibited in the opposite direction ($-x$). The maximum displacement measured $d_{\max} \approx \pm 11.5 \mu\text{m}$ was for a fluid-of-light intensity $I = 349 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ and an obstacle's initial position $x_0 = \pm 200 \mu\text{m}$. One easily observes that the measured displacement d depends on the intensity of the fluid-of-light I . This is an expected behaviour. In fact, in the non-saturating regime, as the intensity increases, the $\Delta n(I)$ increases as well. Thus, according to (4.20) the displacement at the output of the medium increases.

Figure 4.23: The transverse displacement of the obstacle in fluid-of-light (Gaussian beam) at rest $\theta_{\text{in}} = 0$. The measured displacement at the output of the crystal d of the obstacle versus its initial x_s . In a Gaussian potential of a radius at $1/e^2$ of $270 \mu\text{m}$. The round dots represent the experimental measured displacement and the solid lines are the fit procedure allowing to extract the saturation intensity $I_{\text{sat}} = 380 \pm 50 \text{ W.cm}^{-2}$, and the refractive index variation $\Delta n_{\max} \approx 2.5 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

Notice that every curve of this figure has the shape of a Gaussian derivative distribution. This result is in good agreement with the equation (4.20). In fact, for a fixed value of z the displacement of the obstacle is defined as the derivative of the nonlinear refractive index change which for its part has Gaussian shape in the non-saturated regime of nonlinearity.

This measurement allowed us to extract the values of Δn_{\max} and I_{sat} . To do so, we perform a fitting procedure on the measured values of the displacement d using the model of the photorefractive nonlinearity in the non-saturated regime. Therefore the fitting function can be expressed as follows:

$$|d(x, z = L)| = \frac{2I_0}{n_e \omega_0^2} \frac{\Delta n_{\max}}{I_{\text{sat}}} x e^{-2x^2/\omega_0^2}, \quad (4.21)$$

where, I_0 is the intensity of fluid-of-light at the peak of the Gaussian profile, ω_0 is the width of the bell shape intensity distribution. The other parameters were described in detail in chapter 3. The only free parameters we have are Δn_{\max} and I_{sat} . Therefore, the extracted values are: $I_{\text{sat}} = 380 \pm 50 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ and $\Delta n_{\max} = 2.5 \pm 0.4 \cdot 10^{-4}$. Hence, the sound velocity c_s at the peak intensity can then be deduced $c_s = 7.2 \times 10^{-3}$.

To resume, we have presented in this paragraph a characterisation of the obstacle's behaviour within the Gaussian potential (i.e. fluid-of-light). However, in order not to be confused, let us recall the goal of

the whole section. As we said before, we want to study light superfluidity through the measurement of the obstacle's displacement induced by the fluid-of-light. Nevertheless, this displacement was due also to the form of the fluid-of-light which represents an undesirable displacement. Therefore, to extract the obstacle's displacement associated only to the frictional/superfluid regime, we were ought to study the undesirable displacement. In the next subsection, we present the procedure we used to extract the net displacement of the obstacle associated to the frictional/superfluid regime of the fluid-of-light.

4.4.3 Extraction of the displacement due to the superfluid/frictional regimes

The previous characterisation (i.e. Fig. 4.23) enables us to extract the net displacement associated only to the drag-force. This can be done by subtracting the measurement of the displacement due only to the Gaussian potential from the measurement of the displacement in the frictional/superfluid regimes (where the impact of the diffraction pattern is as well included). We illustrate in figure 4.24 the subtraction procedure.

In figure 4.24.(a) we represent the cut along the x -axis of the fluid-of-light's intensity distribution in the frictional regime. The blue rectangle in the middle represents the obstacle's corresponding displacement between the input and the output of the crystal. Figure 4.24.(b) represents the displacement of the obstacle with the same initial condition (i.e. angle of incidence of the fluid-of-light θ_{in}) but considered without any influence from the obstacle beam on the fluid-of-light. The subtraction of these two effects results in the figure 4.24.(c) showing the net displacement caused only by the effect of the drag-force.

To clarify this procedure, we assume that we introduce a certain angle on the fluid-of-light, its associated x -cut intensity distribution is represented in 4.24.(a). In these conditions, we measure a certain shift at the output of the medium, we denote it by D (see figure 4.24.(a)). Afterwards, thanks to the characterisation of the displacement due only to the Gaussian potential (i.e. fig 4.23), we measure as well a shift d of the obstacle. Therefore, to eventually extract the value of the displacement due solely to the drag-force (superfluid/frictional regime i.e. fig 4.24.(c)), we subtract d from D . This procedure was done for various values of intensity of the fluid ranging from 44 mW.cm^{-2} to 349 mW.cm^{-2} . Finally, the resulting displacement $D - d$ is to be correlated with the drag-force extracted from the images of the fluid-of-light beam intensity distribution.

Figure 4.24: Illustration of the subtraction procedure to extract the net displacement of the obstacle. The panels represent the cut of the intensity distribution along x -axis. Panel (a) displays the profile of the fluid-of-light on top of which the obstacle propagates non-linearly. The blue rectangle illustrates the obstacle's displacement. Panel (b) represents the fluid-of-light profile in the case of an obstacle propagating linearly (fluid unperturbed). The orange rectangle shows the obstacle and its displacement induced by the shape of the fluid-of-light beam (Gaussian). Panel (c) displays the difference between the profiles (a) and (b) the net displacement of the obstacle is represented by the green rectangle.

4.4.4 Experimental results and discussion

We present in the figures below the results of the drag-force and the corresponding obstacle's displacement for various values of the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. In this set of measurement, the Mach number v/c_s ranges from -0.41 to 4.1 . It is worth mentioning that in this manuscript we do not present the displacement corresponding to the negative values of the ratio v/c_s . This is because of the cavity effects taking place in the crystal. These cavity effects blur the measurements of the drag-force as well as the extracted displacement of the obstacle. For more information, please refer to the appendix B.B. In the left panels of each figure, we represent the normalised drag-force for a fixed intensity of the fluid-of-light beam I (speed of sound c_s) as a function of the ratio v/c_s . As we explained earlier, it is simply the difference between the intensities upstream and downstream of the obstacle. The right panels of each figure display the measured displacement of the obstacle associated with the drag-force as a function of the ratio v/c_s .

Figure 4.25: Figure of the drag-force and the obstacle's displacement versus the Mach number v/c_s for a probe intensity fixed at 44 mW.cm^{-2} . Panel a. represents the drag-force calculated by subtracting the intensity upstream and downstream of the obstacle. Panel b. is the results of the corresponding displacement. the grey box is the error bar of the obstacle's displacement.

Figure 4.25 shows through the measurement of the drag-force that the the fluid-of-light exhibits a superfluid behaviour when the ratio v/c_s is less than 0.2. This is explained by the local symmetry of the intensity distribution around the obstacle. One observes that the drag force for the first three points is roughly equal to zero (i.e. $F = |I_+ - I_-| \approx 0$). In contrast, when $v/c_s \geq 0.2$, the drag-force starts to take a non-zero value. Therefore, the fluid-of-light exhibits a frictional regime in this interval. Independently of the drag-force, the measurement of the obstacle's displacement for a Mach number $v/c_s \leq 0.2$ gives approximately a zero value (i.e. $\langle x \rangle = 0$). This result fits well the drag-force previously calculated. As v/c_s increases, a concrete displacement of the obstacle is recorded reaching a maximum value of $1.8 \mu\text{m}$. This result demonstrates that in this region the fluid-of-light is not superfluid. In this set of measurement, the superfluid interval is very narrow in such a way that we hardly see it on the first three points. In figure 4.25, one sees clearly that all curves drop to zero values when the ratio v/c_s is high. One should not confuse this with the superfluid behaviour. In fact, this regime takes place because the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light becomes homogeneous in the vicinity of the obstacle. This behaviour is attributed to two things, first the obstacle has not a Dirac-like form. And second, the velocity of the fluid-of-light becomes so high in such a way that the obstacle is not anymore seen by the fluid-of-light. On figure 4.25.(b), we plot the displacement of the obstacle along the y -axis (grey box curve). We clearly see that the obstacle's displacement along this axis is below 0.3. This curve defines also the uncertainty of the obstacle's displacement along the x -axis.

The measurements of the drag-force and the obstacle's displacement were also carried out for input intensities equal to $I = 175 \text{ mW.cm}^2$, $I = 262 \text{ mW.cm}^2$ and $I = 349 \text{ mW.cm}^2$. They are displayed in figure 4.26. Unlike the previous set of measurements where the superfluid regime takes place in a narrow interval of v/c_s , here we see clearly that the superfluid regime of the fluid-of-light takes place in a larger interval

Figure 4.26: Figure of the drag-force and the displacement for various values of the fluid-of-light intensity. The transition superfluid/frictional regimes occurs at $v/c_s \leq [0.5 - 0.6]$.

$v/c_s \leq [0.5 - 0.6]$. This result is demonstrated through the calculation of the drag-force as well as the measurement of the obstacle's displacement. Both of which have zero values for $v/c_s \leq [0.5 - 0.6]$. As v/c_s increases, one observes clearly that the fluid-of-light exhibits a non-superfluid behaviour manifested in the appearance of the drag-force and the displacement of the obstacle. Notice that in figures 4.26.(e) and (f) (i.e. $I = 349 \text{ mW.cm}^2$), the measured displacement and the drag force are practically negligible. This is because the fluid-of-light's intensity is too high and becomes homogeneous in the vicinity of the obstacle. Therefore, the displacement of this later and the drag-force become very small. Another point to clarify is the occurrence of the plateau in the measured obstacle's displacement around the value $\langle x \rangle = 0.5 \mu\text{m}$ (see figures 4.26.(b), (d) and (f)). To understand why the plateau appears, one has to follow the propagation of the fluid-of-light beam inside the bulk and record the intensity distribution at different distances of propagation $z_1 = 2 \text{ mm}$, $z_2 = 4 \text{ mm} \dots z_2 = 10 \text{ mm}$. Experimentally, it is impossible to perform this measurement since the laws of ray refraction are no more linear. Therefore we suggest proceeding numerically for visualising the intensity distribution inside the bulk of the crystal. We display in figure 4.27 the 2D spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light encountering an obstacle at different propagation lengths along the nonlinear medium.

The simulation were carried out at an incidence angle $\theta_{\text{in}} = 5$ mrad for two extreme intensities of the fluid-of-light $I = 349 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ (i.e. $v/c_s = 0.3$) and $I = 44 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ (i.e. $v/c_s = 1$). The occurrence of the plateau at higher intensities of the fluid-of-light (figures 4.26.(b), (d) and (f)) is attributed to the transient regime taking place at early stages of the propagation. In this transient regime, the fluid-of-light is not superfluid yet. This is shown in the figure 4.27 b, at $z = 4$ mm and $z = 5$ mm. Therefore an asymmetric intensity distribution of the fluid takes place at these distances of propagation inducing a local refractive index modification, hence, a residual transverse displacement takes place even though a superfluid regime is attained at a distance $z = 10$ mm.

Figure 4.27: Figure of the evolution of the fluid-of-light's intensity distribution. Each of the images corresponds to a snapshot of the intensity distribution of the fluid at various distances of propagation. The pictures size was reduced to $50 \times 50 \mu\text{m}$ Panel a. $I = 44 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ and panel b. $I = 349 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$.

As a resume of the results, we have on the one hand studied the property of superfluidity in a fluid-of-light in the propagating geometry through the direct observation of its 2D spatial intensity distribution. We have seen the breakdown of superfluidity manifested in the appearance of the diffraction pattern upstream of the obstacle. On the other hand, we have demonstrated through the independent measurement of the optical analogue drag-force as well as the measurement of the obstacle's corresponding displacement that

these two quantities drop down to zero when the fluid-of-light exhibits a superfluid behaviour. This can be considered as a strong signature of the superfluid behaviour of light.

4.5 Summary

To conclude, we have introduced in this chapter a technique to investigate the superfluid behaviour of light, we have seen in analogy with quantum fluids that light superfluidity is defined as the absence of the diffraction pattern of the fluid-of-light when this latter encounters an obstacle, stressing the parameters that control the flow of the fluid-of-light, namely, the flow velocity v and the density of the fluid-of-light ρ controlled respectively through the angle of incidence θ_{in} and the intensity of the laser beam. Finally, we have exposed a few results that demonstrate the occurrence of the superfluid regime of a fluid-of-light.

Chapter 5

Vortex observation in a fluid-of-light

We dedicate this chapter to a preliminary study and observation of optical vortices in a self-defocusing photorefractive medium. In the first section, we provide an introduction to optical vortices and we expose some techniques used to generate beams with orbital angular momenta (optical vortex beams). Afterwards, we present a description of optical vortices based on the analogy with quantum fluids. Thereafter, a hydrodynamical approach to observe optical vortices is given, pointing out the physical mechanism responsible for their generation. Finally, we present and discuss the preliminary results about optical vortex shedding in the fluid-of-light. We precise that this chapter presents only a preliminary study of optical vortex generation in fluids-of-light and has not to be the subject of a complete study such as the other parts of this work.

5.1 Introduction

The study of superfluidity in quantum fluids as well as in fluids-of-light is strongly related to the concept of vortices, since the latter represent a peculiar solution of the Gross-Pitaevskii and the wave equations. Vortices were majorly studied within the frame of hydrodynamic physics. They are regions of space in which the phase of the wave function is singular. Hence, its amplitude drops to zero. In these regions, the density of the fluid revolves around an axis. The first elaboration of a phase singularity in hydrodynamics was done in the 1830s by Whewell^[167], where he studied ocean tides. Vortices can be found in many systems with different scales starting from whirlpools in classical fluids to quantised vortices in quantum fluids and quantised lines of magnetic flux in superconductors. Vortices in classical fluids are created thanks to viscosity. On the contrary, in quantum fluids, viscosity drops to zero, therefore, a vortex solution in this system takes another form. In fact, their circulation is quantised with a coefficient of \hbar/m .^[168] This property emanates directly from the irrotationality condition in superfluids.^[169]

Vortices exist as well in optics, they are also defined as waves with phase singularities^[170] in which the energy flow revolves with a higher velocity around an axis giving rise to zero intensity in the vortex core region. Optical vortices look like ring beams when they are projected on a flat surface. They possess the same properties as vortices in quantum fluids, in particular, quantised circulations and topological charges.^[171] The active field that studies optical vortices is known as singular optics. Nowadays, optical vortices start to find some interesting applications in fundamental and applied physics. Among these applications there is the increase of the optical data storage^[172], the establishment of optical chips-boards interconnects^[173], also the achievement of a free-space communication.^[174,175] Recently, the transmission of orbital angular momentum of light through free-space has shown a great capability of carrying information with good robustness over a distance of 143 km.^[176] Optical vortices are useful for trapping particles

thanks to their capability of generating reconfigurable patterns of complex intensity^[177], and the ability of guiding light through waveguides created by an optical vortex beam.^[178–181] Another interesting application of optical vortices is the possibility to increase the bitrate (capacity of data transfer in a communication system), thanks to the orthogonality property between different topological charges, optical vortex beams with different topological charges cannot interfere.^[182] More recently, optical vortex beams have shown a good accuracy to encode quantum information by structuring the spin and the orbital angular momenta of the light beam.^[183]

The study of the dynamics of optical vortices is such of a great importance knowing the existing similarities between optics and quantum fluids (BECs). They generally play a crucial role in physics, for example, the occurrence of the Berezinskii-Kosterlitz-Thouless (BKT) phase transition in quantum fluids and in a photonic lattice^[184–186] in the 2-dimensional model marked by the formation of vortex pairs with opposite topological charges. Optical vortices can also be transferred into polariton fluids-of-light to study quantised vortex dynamics.^[187]

5.1.1 General techniques of generating optical vortices

In this subsection, we give a brief summary about the commonly used techniques to generate optical vortices. According to the literature, vortices in optics can be generated using many techniques we cite the most widespread ones:

- The **computer-generated holography (CGH)**. It is a digital method to generate holographic patterns of interference. These generated patterns are printed onto a mask or film and are therefore illuminated by the laser beam to finally get an optical vortex beam^[188].
- The **spiral phase plates**. It might be the simplest method for producing a vortex beam. The principle is to propagate a Gaussian beam into an optical device "spiral phase plat" of refractive index n .^[189] The obtained intensity distribution at the output has a rotating angular momentum.
- The **mode conversion** technique. Starting from a Hermite-Gaussian beam modes, one can generate an optical vortex beam through passing the Hermite-Gaussian beam into a cylindrical pair of lenses. This latter introduces a phase shift on the beam resulting in a Laguerre-Gauss beam (optical vortex) a more detailed description can be found in.^[190,191] It worth mentioning that Hermite-Gauss beams can easily be generated through the laser cavity by placing crossed wires inside this latter.

These techniques used to generate beams carrying orbital angular momentum are well established and are independent of the fluid-of-light context. Conversely, in our work, we consider a purely hydrodynamical approach to generate and to investigate optical vortices behaviour. Therefore, our study is not incorporated within the previous techniques.

5.2 Review of optical vortices

The possibility of light to carry an angular momentum regarding its propagation axis has always been asked even in eras before Maxwell's theory of electromagnetism. In 1909, Poynting predicted that light carrying an elliptic polarisation could apply a rotational force on a body, he also gave an analogy between a circularly polarised light beam and a rotating body.^[192] This prediction was thereafter verified experimentally in 1936 by Beth^[193]. Afterwards, the development of the electromagnetic theory gave possibilities to investigate

light energy flows, and to define the concept of orbital angular momentum^[194,195] which is the crucial physical quantity for investigating optical vortices. Thereafter, a first calculation of the angular momentum of a Laguerre-Gauss beam^[196] was carried out by Allen and co-workers^[170] who showed that a rotating wavefront is similar to a circularly polarised beam.

5.2.1 Optical vortices description

The angular momentum of a light beam comprises two main physical quantities referred to as spin angular momentum and orbital angular momentum. The first quantity is directly related to the polarisation of the laser beam. This latter is said to have a spin angular momentum if the electromagnetic field of the laser rotates around the axis of propagation. The second quantity is related to the rotation of the beam's wavefront resulting in a change of its intensity distribution.

To describe the concept of an optical vortex let us remind that the wave function of a laser beam can be written as a complex quantity (function). For the sake of simplicity, we consider this complex wave function to be scalar and we denote it by $\psi(\mathbf{r}, t)$. An optical vortex is defined as the drop of the amplitude's wave function. Therefore, one can write the wave function associated to a vortex beam as follows:

$$\psi(\mathbf{r}, t) = \rho(\mathbf{r}, t)e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)} = \rho(\mathbf{r}, t)e^{im\theta}, \quad (5.1)$$

where $\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is amplitude of the wave function, $\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)$ is its phase, \mathbf{r} being the radial coordinate, θ is the azimuthal angle of the wavefront and m is called the topological charge.

The topological charge (sometimes called the winding number) of the zero-intensity (dislocation) can be calculated through the following expression:

$$m = \frac{1}{2\pi} \oint \nabla \varphi(\mathbf{r}, t) dr \quad (5.2)$$

This expression represents the circulation of the phase gradient around the dislocation. It is an integer number since the phase is a multiple of 2π . This arises from the single valued condition of the wave function. The topological charge m allows us to access to the orbital angular momentum of the optical vortex.

In figure 5.1 upper row is displayed the intensity distribution of an optical vortex beam for various topological charge values m . It is also shown respectively the corresponding phase-front and the helical wavefront in the middle and lower rows of the figure. As shown in the figure, a beam carrying an angular momentum has a doughnut-like intensity profile and its wavefront revolves around the axis of propagation of the beam.

It is worth mentioning that a vortex beam carrying higher order dislocations $|m| > 1$ suffers from the topological instability and generally decays into a single-charge vortices $|m| = 1$. However, it was demonstrated within the frame of quantum fluids that higher order vortices might last longer.^[198] Similarly, in nonlinear optics it was shown that multiple-charge vortices can survive for a relatively longer distance.^[199] To get a better insight into optical vortex beams, we suggest in the next paragraph to briefly describe the transverse behaviour of optical vortices in linear and nonlinear media.

Behaviour of optical vortices The transverse dynamics of an optical vortex depend on the medium of propagation of the beam carrying the vortex.^[200] In linear medium, (e.g. air) a doughnut-like beam undergoes the linear diffraction effect resulting in the transverse spread of the vortex core. This behaviour makes

Figure 5.1: Figures of the light intensity distributions carrying an orbital angular momentum. The upper row represents the intensity distribution of an optical vortex, the middle row is the phase of the optical vortex and the lower row displays the wavefront rotation of the wave. The number m corresponds to the topological charge of the optical vortex. Adapted from^[197]

the vortex disappear after a certain distance of propagation. Figure 5.2 presents the propagation of a vortex beam into a linear medium. The distance of propagation z is normalised to the diffraction distance of the system.

Figure 5.2: The evolution of the intensity distribution of an optical vortex beam in a linear medium. z represents the distance of propagation, it is normalised by the diffraction length of the system. In a linear medium the optical vortex beam undergoes the effect of linear diffraction resulting in the spread of the optical vortex. Adapted from^[201]

In a nonlinear medium, the dynamics of optical vortices is significantly different. Thanks to the nonlinearity the natural linear diffraction might be counterbalanced resulting in a more stable vortex. However, the sign of the nonlinearity Δn plays a crucial role on the transverse dynamics of the dislocations. In a self-focusing nonlinearity $\Delta n(I) > 0$, vortices do not survive longer and are not stable. In fact, in the self-focusing regime, the competing effects of diffraction and the nonlinearity foster the appearance of bright solitons instead of dark ones. Therefore, within this regime, a beam with an initial dislocation might decay into trains of bright optical solitons because of the modulational instability^[201,202] (see figure 5.3).

In the self-defocusing regime, the dynamics of optical vortices are manifestly distinct from the self-focusing regime. The self-defocusing nonlinearity does not support the establishment of bright solitons. However, thanks to the negative refractive index change, the medium fosters the appearance of dark-solitons. Therefore, a possibility to get a stable vortex structure can be considered. We usually refer to

Figure 5.3: The intensity distribution evolution of an optical vortex beam in a self-focusing nonlinear medium. The numerical study shows that along with the propagation the optical vortex decays into bright solitons. The quantity z represents the axis of propagation of the laser beam; it is normalised by the nonlinear length z_{nl} of the medium. Adapted from.^[201]

vortices in a self-defocusing media to as *optical vortex solitons*. We present in figure 5.4 a propagation of a laser beam carrying an angular momentum in a self-defocusing nonlinear medium.

Figure 5.4: The intensity distribution evolution of an optical vortex beam in a self-defocusing nonlinear medium. In this nonlinear medium the vortex structure is more stable. z is the axis of propagation normalised to z_{nl} Adapted from^[201]

The observation and the study of optical vortices in a self-defocusing nonlinearity have been the subject of a many works. To cite a few, we refer to the work of Swartzlander^[203] where they investigated optical vortex solitons pair in a Kerr-type nonlinear medium. Also, Mamaev and co-workers reported an experimental study of the propagation, the decay and the interaction of optical vortex solitons in an anisotropic photorefractive medium.^[58,59] Furthermore, Segev and co-workers^[204] also investigated optical vortices in a photorefractive medium. All these studies consider optical vortex beams at the initial condition, which means pregenerated vortices at the entrance of the nonlinear medium.

From a different perspective, Vocke and co-workers^[205] reported the nucleation of optical vortices in the frame of fluids-of-light. Here, the laser beam does not possess an initial orbital angular momentum. The generation of optical vortices was also reported in polaritonic systems.^[43,206,207] In our study of optical dislocations, we focus on the case of the self-defocusing nonlinearity in the propagating geometry and we consider the case of a fluid-of-light which initially does not possess optical singularities. Therefore, optical vortices are generated during the propagation of the fluid-of-light beam through the nonlinear medium. In the next paragraph, we suggest to give a description of optical dislocations in the fluids-of-light frame.

Description of optical vortices in a fluid-of-light To describe the properties of optical vortices in the context of fluids-of-light, we invoke the description given in Chapter 2. We remind the equation that describes the evolution of a laser beam (fluid-of-light) in a nonlinear medium:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} A(r, z) = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 A(r, z) + k_0 \Delta n(I) A(r, z). \quad (5.3)$$

It is worth expressing this equation in the dimensionless form. To simplify, let us consider a Kerr-type nonlinear medium (i.e. $\Delta n = n_2 I$). And let us denote by A_∞ (resp. I_∞) the amplitude (resp. the intensity) of the wave in the region far from the vortex. It is important to note that the field $A(r, z)$ varies slowly in the transverse plane over distances of the order of the healing length ξ . Therefore, performing the change of variable $A \rightarrow A' = A/A_\infty$ in the equation (5.3), gives the following equation:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial Z} A'(R, Z) = -\frac{1}{4\xi_\infty^2} \nabla_\perp^2 A'(R, Z) + n_0 |A'|^2 A'(R, Z), \quad (5.4)$$

where Z is the normalised distance of propagation and R is the normalised radial coordinates. They are expressed as follows:

$$Z = \frac{z}{z_{\text{nl}}} \quad \text{and} \quad R = \frac{r}{\xi_\infty}, \quad (5.5)$$

where z_{nl} is often referred to as the nonlinear length and ξ_∞ is the healing length given in previous chapters but here defined in regions far from the vortex core where the density of the fluid-of-light is considered to be homogeneous. They are defined by the following expressions:

$$z_{\text{nl}} = \frac{n_0}{k_0 n_2 I_\infty} \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_\infty = \frac{1}{k_0 n_0} \sqrt{\frac{n_0}{n_2 I_\infty}}. \quad (5.6)$$

A solution to the equation (5.4) in the form of a vortex wave function can be considered using Madelung's transformation. $A'(x, y) = \sqrt{\rho(x, y, z)} e^{i\varphi(x, y)} = \sqrt{\rho(x, y, z)} e^{im\theta}$. Making use of the circular symmetry of the system, we write the Madelung transformation in the cylindrical coordinates as follows:

$$A'(R, \theta, Z) = \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta, Z)} e^{im\theta} \quad (5.7)$$

The wave envelop A' cancels when $\rho = 0$. In this region, the circulation of the velocity i.e. $\nabla\varphi(R, Z)$ is proportional to 2π . Now, substituting the vortex wave function (5.7) in the equation of propagation (5.4) results in the equation of the vortex wave function given in the cylindrical coordinates and at a certain fixed distance z as follows:

$$\frac{d^2}{dR^2} \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{d}{dR} \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)} - \frac{m^2}{R^2} \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)} + 4n_0 |\rho| \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)} = 0 \quad (5.8)$$

The above expression is the equation that describes the shape of the optical vortex. It can be solved numerically. However, knowing that the vortex wave function satisfies the following boundary conditions $\rho(R \rightarrow 0) = 0$ and $\rho(R \rightarrow \infty) = 1$, we can directly establish the asymptotic form of the solution near zero ($R = 0$) and near infinity ($R \rightarrow \infty$) and we write:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\rho(R)} &\approx aR^{|m|} & \text{when } R \rightarrow 0 \\ \sqrt{\rho(R)} &\approx 1 - \frac{m^2}{2R^2} & \text{when } R \rightarrow \infty \end{aligned} \quad (5.9)$$

We give in figure 5.5 the plots of the vortex amplitude shape $\sqrt{\rho(R)}$ for two different values of the topological charge m . The figure shows that the amplitude shape of the vortex expands when the topological charge increases.

Figure 5.5: Figure of vortex profiles in the 1-dimensional space versus the normalised radial coordinate R in the self-defocusing nonlinearity (5.9). Solid line (resp. dotted line) represents the shape of the vortex for $m = 1$ (resp. $m = 2$). An increase of the topological charge induces an expansion in the vortex core. Adapted from.^[12]

It is important to note that the radius of the vortex should be compared to the healing length of the system ξ . Notice that the healing length in regions far from the vortex ξ_∞ is different from the healing length of the system. This latter takes into account the inhomogeneities of the intensity distribution of the fluid-light. Let us demonstrate why the radius of the vortex is comparable to ξ . In fact, to find the radius of the vortex in a fluid-of-light, one should determine the cross over between the two asymptotic regimes namely, $R \rightarrow 0$ and $R \rightarrow \infty$. That is determined by equalising the nonlinear term to the kinetic energy term of the equation (5.8) and this yields:

$$\frac{m^2}{R^2} \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)} = 2n_0 |\rho| \sqrt{\rho(R, \theta)}. \quad (5.10)$$

From equation (5.10) one easily establishes the expression of the vortex radius $r_v = R/\xi_\infty$ knowing that $|\rho(R, Z)| = |I(R, Z)/I_\infty|$. Therefore, the expression of the vortex radius is given as follows:

$$r_v = \frac{m}{2k_0 n_0^{3/2}} \sqrt{\frac{n_0}{n_2 I(r, z)}} = \frac{m}{4n_0^{1/2}} \xi \sim m\xi \quad (5.11)$$

This equation shows that the radius of the vortex has the same order of magnitude of the healing length of the system ξ . Notice that the radius of the vortex grows with the order of the dislocation m . Since the healing length ξ declines with the increase of the density of the fluid-of-light, then also the radius of the vortex is expected to decrease with the increase of the density $I(r, z)$.

We present in figure 5.6 the evolution of the vortex radius r_v versus the intensity of the beam I . We can see that the radius of the vortex declines with as the square root of the intensity.

Let us now establish the expression of the tangential rotation velocity of the optical vortex that we denote by \mathbf{v} . We know from preceding chapters that the transverse velocity of the fluid-of-light is given by:

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{1}{n_0 k_0} \nabla_\perp \varphi(r, \theta, z) \quad (5.12)$$

Where $\varphi(r, \theta, z)$ is the phase of the optical field. In the vortex region, we know that $\varphi = m\theta$. Therefore, the transverse gradient of the phase is expressed as a function of the radial coordinate by $\nabla_\perp \varphi(r, \theta, z) =$

Figure 5.6: Figure of the vortex core radius r_v evolution versus the intensity of the fluid-of-light I . The vortex core decreases as the square root of the intensity.

$(m/r)\mathbf{e}_r$. Consequently, the rotation velocity of the vortex is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{v} = \frac{1}{n_0 k_0} \frac{m}{r} \mathbf{e}_r = v \mathbf{e}_r \quad (5.13)$$

From this expression one sees clearly that the rotation velocity of the vortex in fluids-of-light v is inversely proportional to the radial coordinate r . This produces an infinite angular velocity in the center of the vortex ($v(r=0) \rightarrow \infty$). This behaviour is radically different from the usual classical law that governs the rotation of a rigid-body or a classical fluid.

Figure 5.7: Geometrical representation of the circulation of the vortex. The tangential velocity v is represented on the circumference of the vortex. $d\mathbf{l}$ is the variation of the circumference of the vortex, it is oriented along the tangential direction \mathbf{e}_θ and r, θ are respectively the radial and azimuthal coordinates.

From equation (5.13), one easily establishes the expression of the circulation of a vortex in fluids-of-light (see 5.7). It is quantised in units of $1/n_0 k_0$:

$$\Gamma_v = \oint_0^L \mathbf{v} \cdot d\mathbf{l} = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{1}{n_0 k_0} \frac{m}{r} r d\theta = 2m\pi \frac{1}{n_0 k_0} \quad (5.14)$$

In the next subsection, we present the optical configuration to generate vortices in a fluid-of-light.

5.3 Optical vortex generation in a fluid-of-light and experimental set-up

5.3.1 Vortex generation in a fluid-of-light

In this subsection, we describe the hydrodynamical approach we employed to study optical vortices in a fluid-of-light beam. For this purpose, we follow the pioneering theoretical work of T. Frisch and co-workers^[44], where they numerically studied the flow around an obstacle of a system governed by the nonlinear Schrödinger equation and they have reported the emission of vortical structures when the flow velocity reaches a critical velocity.

The configuration we used to investigate optical vortices is similar to the configuration presented in Chapter 4 for the study of superfluidity. It consists in propagating a laser beam in the presence of an obstacle through a nonlinear medium. However, in the previous configuration, we have used a weakly perturbative obstacle (weak intensity with a circularly shaped obstacle). We have briefly mentioned in Chapter 4 that the shape and the strength of the obstacle play a crucial role in determining the behaviour of the fluid-of-light around the obstacle, pointing out that the vortex generation regime might be observed for higher strength and diameter of the obstacle. Therefore, the aim of this preliminary study is to observe the regime of optical vortex shedding when we change the characteristics of the obstacle.

Figure 5.8: Illustration of the principle to probe optical singularities in fluids-of-light. A fluid-of-light beam (green beam) propagates into the SBN crystal within the presence of an optical defect (red beam). An angle is being introduced on the fluid-of-light to provide it with a velocity v . The axis z is the propagation direction of the beam. The c -axis of the crystal is oriented along the x -axis

Let us quickly introduce the principle and remind the key quantities to control the behaviour of the fluid-of-light. We display in the figure 5.8 the propagation of the fluid-of-light around an obstacle into a photorefractive nonlinear medium. Here, we repeat the same configuration of Chapter 4 but this time we vary the diameter D_{ob} and the power P_{ob} of the obstacle.

The green beam plays the role of the fluid-of-light. Its velocity $v = (1/n_e) \sin(\theta_{in})$ is controlled by the angle of incidence θ_{in} of the laser beam and its critical velocity $c_s = \sqrt{\Delta n(I_f)/n_e}$ is monitored through its intensity I_f , where n_e is the index of refraction along the extraordinary axis of the crystal. As for the obstacle, it is induced by another laser beam (red beam). Thanks to the techniques of wavefront shaping, we have a good control on the diameter of the obstacle beam D_{ob} .

5.3.2 Experimental set-up

In the experimental set-up depicted in figure 5.9, we have interchanged the roles of the laser beams for the simple reason of the provided power by the red light. The latter is a He-Ne Laser that supplies a maximum power of 3 mW. In contrast the green beam goes to a maximum power of 300 mW. In addition to this, we set up a Mach-Zehnder interferometer to access the phase of the fluid-of-light. A reference beam interferes with the fluid-of-light beam at the output of the crystal as displayed by figure 5.9.

Figure 5.9: Sketch of the experimental set-up for investigating optical vortices. The green light plays the role fluid-of-light beam and the red one is the obstacle. A Mach-Zehnder interferometer is added to access the phase of the fluid-of-light beam. The sCMOS camera allows to measure the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light as well as its phase.

We use as a nonlinear medium a 20 mm long SBN:61 crystal. The reason for this change is the following: the observation of vortex nucleation in quantum fluids-of-light requires a larger distance of propagation z into the nonlinear medium (see chapters 2 and 4).

5.3.3 Physical mechanism of optical vortex pairs nucleation

In this subsection, we expose the physical mechanism responsible for generating vortex/anti-vortex pairs in a fluid-of-light encountering an obstacle.

Figure 5.10: Illustration of the physical mechanism responsible for vortex/anti-vortex pair. The fluid-of-light is illustrated by the wave modulation upstream of the obstacle. \mathbf{v}_0 is the initial velocity of the fluid-of-light. P_1 and P_2 are the pole point of the obstacle. \mathbf{v}_{P_1} and \mathbf{v}_{P_2} are respectively the velocities at the poles of the obstacle.

Let us assume a flow of a fluid-of-light around an circular obstacle (see figure 5.10). The initial flow velocity is equal to \mathbf{v}_0 . Figure 5.10 shows the process of generating vortex/anti-vortex pair through an obstacle. The points P_1 and P_2 are the pole points of the circular obstacle. The theory that predicts the occurrence of a vortical flow in the fluid-of-light (or a quantum fluid) is the Landau criterion. To understand the mechanism, one should recall the hydrodynamics equations of the fluid-of-light seen in Chapter 2. We assume a homogeneous distribution of the fluid-of-light (resp. of a quantum fluid). Therefore, the quantum pressure can be neglected and the Euler equations read:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho(\mathbf{r}, t) + \nabla_{\perp} \cdot [\rho(\mathbf{r}, t) \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r}, t)] = 0, \quad (5.15)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{v} + \rho (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla_{\perp}) \mathbf{v} + \nabla_{\perp} P = 0, \quad (5.16)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = \nabla_{\perp} \varphi$ is the velocity of the fluid oriented along the x -axis, φ being the phase of the fluid-of-light, ρ is its density and P is the pressure term defined by the nonlinearity. Assuming the following boundary condition $\mathbf{v}(r \rightarrow \infty, z) = \nabla_{\perp} \varphi = \mathbf{v}_0$ and that the density of the fluid-of-light is constant along the flow. This means in the context of nonlinear optics that the laser beam does not undergo absorption along the axis of propagation (i.e. z -axis). Therefore, the first L.H.S term of the continuity equation (eq. (5.15)) is equal to zero (i.e. $\partial \rho / \partial t = 0$). Hence, the continuity equation reads:

$$\nabla_{\perp}^2 \varphi(r, \theta, t) = 0 \quad (5.17)$$

Now we want to express the velocity at the points P_1 and P_2 . The solution of eq. (5.17) in the considered boundary conditions can be expressed as follows^[22,26,208]:

$$\varphi(r, \theta) = |\mathbf{v}_0| \cos(\theta) \left[r + \frac{r_0^2}{r} \right], \quad (5.18)$$

where r and θ are the polar coordinates and r_0 is the radius of the obstacle. Expressing the velocity \mathbf{v} at the points P_1 and P_2 (i.e. $\theta = \pm\pi/2$ and $r = r_0$) yields:

$$|\mathbf{v}_{P_1}| = |\mathbf{v}_{P_2}| \approx 2|\mathbf{v}_0| \quad (5.19)$$

The velocity v at points P_1 and P_2 is approximately two times the initial velocity of the fluid. Note that for an inviscid idealised fluid the velocity at the poles of the obstacle is expected to be equal to $2v_0$. Taking into account of eq. (5.19), for $v_0 = 0.5c_s$, the velocity at the poles of the obstacle $v_{P_1} = v_{P_2} \approx c_s$. Therefore, the Landau criterion applied locally at P_1 and P_2 predicts the existence of excitations if $[v_{P_1}, v_{P_2}] \geq c_s$. These excitations take the form of pairs of vortices with opposite circulations (see figures 5.11 and 5.12).

Figure 5.11: figure of vortex pair in a quantum fluid. Panel (a) (resp. panel (b)) presents the experimental (resp. numerical data) images of the quantum fluid density. A vortex/anti-vortex are emitted (left extreme image), they evolve in the direction of the flow until they annihilate (right extreme image). Adapted from^[209]

In the context of quantum fluids, the generation of vortex/anti-vortex pairs through an obstacle was theoretically and experimentally investigated.^[209–211] We display in figure 5.11.(a) (resp. 5.11.(b)) the experimental (resp. theoretical) observation of vortex pairs in a quantum fluid. One observes clearly the propagation of vortex pairs generated (from left) until their annihilation (to right).

In the frame of fluids-of-light, the generation of optical vortex pairs through an obstacle was reported in the polaritonic configuration.^[21,212] In the propagating geometry, Khamis and co-workers reported the numerical observation of optical vortices through an obstacle^[49] in a photorefractive nonlinearity, also I. Carusotto in his work^[66] reported a numerical observation of optical vortices (see fig. 5.12). In this latter, the velocity of the fluid-of-light v was fixed at 0.034, while its intensity varies. In terms of the Mach number v/c_s varies from 2.66 (fig. 5.12.(a)) to 0.77 (fig. 5.12.(c)).

One observes on the 3 images the nucleation of optical vortices in a fluid-of-light. Depending on the Mach number v/c_s one might observe various number of vortex pairs.

5.4 Preliminary results and discussion

In this part, we present preliminary experimental results relative to the observation of optical vortices in the fluid-of-light. We remind that we send through a self-defocusing photorefractive medium (SBN crystal) a laser beam encountering an obstacle. The diameter at $1/e^2$ of the fluid-of-light beam measures $D_f = 680 \mu\text{m}$. We display respectively in figure 5.13.(a) and 5.13.(b) the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light and its cut along the x -axis.

Figure 5.12: Numerical simulation of optical vortex generation in a fluid-of-light within the frame of the propagating geometry. Pictures (a), (b) and (c) are the intensity distributions of the fluid-of-light beam. They have respectively a Mach number of 2.66, 1.33 and 0.77. Vortex/anti-vortex are nucleated from the obstacle evolving in the direction of the flow. Adapted from^[66]

Figure 5.13: Figure of the fluid-of-light beam profile (a) and its cut along the x -axis (b). The radius at $1/e^2$ measures $340 \mu\text{m}$.

To identify the occurrence interval of the vortex shedding regime in the fluid-of-light as a function of the obstacle characteristics, we first performed measurements for various values of the obstacle's diameter D_{ob} . Thereafter, we fixed the diameter of the obstacle to explore the possible different regimes exhibited by the fluid-of-light. To make a comparison, we remind that in the quest for superfluidity the obstacle we have used, had respectively a diameter and a power of $D_{\text{ob}} = 15 \mu\text{m}$ and $P_{\text{ob}} = 8 \mu\text{W}$. Let us precise that in our measurements, we have investigated the vortex shedding regime for a Bessel obstacle first and for a Gaussian potential after. The reason for this is clarified later. Both of which are presented in this section.

It is important to stress that the vortex nucleation regime is expected to take place at a velocity near the transition superfluid/dissipative of the fluid-of-light where, as stated in the preceding subsection, the initial velocity v of the fluid-of-light should be at least greater than $0.5c_s$. However, this threshold might change depending on the strength of the obstacle. According to our previous measurements the transition occurs in the vicinity of a ratio $v/c_s = 0.6$. That is why in our measurements we focused mainly on ratios near $v/c_s = [0.5, 0.6, 0.7]$.

5.4.1 Potential induced by a Bessel beam

In the first set of measurements, we fixed the diameter of the obstacle at $35 \mu\text{m}$ and its power at $35 \mu\text{W}$. The obstacle has a Bessel shape. We present in figure 5.14 the intensity distribution of the obstacle as well as its cut along the x -axis.

Figure 5.14: Figure of the obstacle intensity distribution (a) and its cut along the x -axis (b).

Figure 5.15: Figure of the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light (upper and middle rows) and its interferograms (lower panel) for various values of the Mach number v/c_s . The measurement was carried out for an obstacle diameter of $D_{\text{ob}} \approx 35$. The ratio v/c_s varies from 0.6 to 1.7. This ratio was only varied through the angle of incidence of the fluid-of-light beam θ_{in} (i.e. velocity v). The phase distortion that occurs results from the higher power of the obstacle.

In figure 5.15, we display the intensity distributions of the fluid-of-light encountering an obstacle (upper row), their zoom in the region of the obstacle (middle row) and their interferograms (lower row). As expected, we can see the formation of the diffraction pattern downstream of the obstacle witnessing the

occurrence of the frictional regime of the fluid-of-light.

Using this obstacle (i.e. $D_{\text{ob}} \approx 35 \mu\text{m}$ and $P_{\text{ob}} = 35 \mu\text{W}$), we do not report any observation of a vortex pair emission. That is demonstrated on the interferogram 5.15.(e)-(h), showing that a clear fork structure does not take place, hence, no phase dislocation is reported. However, we clearly observe on the interferograms the occurrence of a phase distortion in the obstacle's position. This apparently comes from the obstacle, which is considered as a strong one.

To resume, the use of this obstacle diameter did not allow us to see a vortex shedding regime. Therefore, we propose in the next set of measurement to increase the diameter of the obstacle.

Figure 5.16: Spatial intensity distribution (resp. interferogram) of the fluid-of-light beam. The diameter of the obstacle taken for this measurement is $D_{\text{ob}} \approx 65$. A vortex pair is emitted from the obstacle (images (a) and (b)). Pictures (c) and (d) do not reveal vortex pair nucleation. The enclosed circles annotate the regions where the intensity drops but do not correspond to a vortex structure.

In this set of measurement (i.e. figure 5.16), we fix the obstacle's diameter at $D_{\text{ob}} = 65 \mu\text{m}$ and we keep its power fixed at $P_{\text{ob}} = 35 \mu\text{W}$. Also we vary the Mach number v/c_s of the fluid-of-light from 0.5 to 1.6. We present the results associated with these conditions in figure 5.16.

One observes the nucleation of a vortex-antivortex pair upstream of the obstacle in figures 5.16.(a) and (b). Their interferograms display clear forks in the interference pattern corresponding to dark spots in the intensity distribution. This represents an accurate signature of the presence of optical vortices. Using the interference patterns, one can see that the vortices rotate in difference directions showing that their topological charges possess opposite signs. We annotate their rotation directions using curved arrows on figures 5.16.(e) and (f). In addition to the vortex pair observation, figure 5.16.(b) shows the occurrence of a "dark line" downstream of vortices. This according to^[49,66] might be a dark soliton that decays into vortices.

In figures 5.16.(c) and 5.16.(d), we do not report any emission of vortex pair. However, one sees on figures

5.16.(g) and 5.16.(h) the distortion of the fluid-of-light phase attributed to the strength of the obstacle. We also added on pictures 5.16.(b), (c) and (d) some enclosed circles (dotted lines) to clarify that the drop of the intensity in these enclosed regions might come from the ring structure of the Bessel beam that also behave as an obstacle regarding the fluid-of-light.

Note that in the two past measurements the ratio v/c_s was changed only through the variation of the incidence angle of the laser beam (i.e. the velocity of the fluid-of-light). This allowed us to identify the occurrence interval of the vortex nucleation. Therefore, to explore more in depth the regime of vortex emission, we propose in the next set of measurement to use similar obstacle strength and diameter but instead of varying the fluid-of-light velocity we vary its density I_f (i.e. the critical velocity c_s).

Figure 5.17 displays the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam for various values of the ratio v/c_s ranging from 0.4 to 1.8. The interferogram of each figure is displayed below. We observe in all the pictures the emission of one vortex pair manifested in forks formation in the interferograms. Increasing the ratio v/c_s makes the vortices evolve in the direction of the fluid-of-light flow. One observes as well that the vortex inter-space gets larger with the increase of the Mach number. Also in figures 5.17.(d) and 5.17.(e) we observe the occurrence of a dark line which, as we said before, might be a dark soliton. The intensity drops in the form of arcs that show up on figures 5.17.(d) and 5.17.(e) are not vortices.

Figure 5.17: The spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light (upper and middle rows) and the corresponding interferogram (lower row). The ratio v/c_s is controlled through the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. The diameter of the obstacle was fixed to $65 \mu\text{m}$. Images from (a) to (j) measure $160 \mu\text{m}$. A vortex/anti-vortex pair is emitted from the obstacle. The rotation directions of the vortices are chosen arbitrarily to show the counter rotating direction of the vortices.

In this set of measurement, the ratio was controlled solely by the intensity of the fluid-of-light I_f . Therefore, it is possible to get a measurement of the vortex diameter D_v as function of the intensity of the

fluid-of-light beam. Qualitatively, figure 5.17 tells that the increase of the intensity I_f (i.e. decrease of v/c_s) makes the diameter of the vortices decline. This is because the vortex diameter in a fluid-of-light is of the order of the healing length ξ , which itself decreases with the square root of the intensity.

Figure 5.18: Cuts along the y -axis of the vortex intensity distribution in a fluid-of-light. The solid line plot (resp. dotted line) represents the vortex shape at an intensity of the fluid-of-light beam equals to 8.2 mW.cm^{-2} (resp. 24.7 mW.cm^{-2}).

We present in figure 5.18 an example of the measurement of the vortex diameter for the typical intensities of 8.2 mW.cm^{-2} and 24.7 mW.cm^{-2} . We measure the diameter of the vortex at half maximum of (FWHM) of the vortex profile intensity. The typical extracted diameters for intensities $I_f = 8.2 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ and $I_f = 24.7 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$ are respectively $D_v = 11 \mu\text{m}$ and $D_v = 8 \mu\text{m}$ (see figure 5.18).

Performing the measurement of the vortex diameter for different values of the intensity of the beam allows to obtain the evolution of the vortex diameter versus the density of the fluid-of-light. That is shown in figure 5.19. This latter presents a logarithmic scale representation (i.e. 5.19.(a)) to show the slope of the experimental data. We plot also $3\xi/2$ to make a comparison between the diameter of the vortex and the healing length. The coefficient $3/2$ is chosen in such a way to approach the value of x_i to the measured diameter of the vortex. It depends significantly on the choice of the diameter measurement. From the figure, one notices that the vortex diameter has a similar behaviour of ξ . This result is expected, since D_v is proportional to ξ (see equation (5.11)).

The parameters we used in order to plot $3\xi/2$ are those of the experiment, namely the intensity I_f and the Δn of the photorefractive nonlinearity. We display as well in figure 5.19.(b) the plot of the vortex diameter and $3\xi/2$ in the normal scale. We precise that the error bar considered in the diameter measurement is 2 pixels on the left side and on the right side of the vortex core.

5.4.2 Potential induced by a Gaussian beam

In the previous measurements, we have considered an obstacle having a Bessel profile, and as we pointed out earlier, the increase in the power of the Bessel makes its concentric rings play the role of secondary obstacles and induce local drops in the fluid-of-light beam intensity. Therefore, we believe that it is interesting to investigate the vortex shedding regime using a Gaussian obstacle. In contrast, the use of a Gaussian beam

Figure 5.19: Experimental Measurement of the vortex diameter versus the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam (grey dots). The plot of $3\xi/2$ as a function of the intensity. The parameters used to plot $3\xi/2$ are the ones used in the experiment. Panel (a) (resp. panel (b)) is the logarithmic (resp. normal) scale representation.

profile does not allow to achieve obstacles with $60 \mu\text{m}$ of a fixed diameter along a propagation distance of 2 cm. Therefore, we raised the diameter of the obstacle.

We suggest here to maintain all the parameters associated with the fluid-of-light fixed. Namely, its intensity at $177 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$ and its velocity at $v = 3.8$, this gives a Mach number equals to 0.35. We fix as well the diameter of the obstacle $D_{\text{ob}} = 120 \mu\text{m}$ and we suggest to vary only its power. These conditions allows us to investigate the impact of the obstacle's strength on the vortex generation in the fluid-of-light.

Figure 5.20 displays the intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light evolution around an obstacle as a function of the strength of the optical obstacle. The strength of the obstacle is controlled by its power P_{ob} as shown on the pictures. We illustrate its position by the white cross on the images. Figure 5.20.(a) shows the beginning of the vortex pair shedding manifested in the formation of the fork structure on the interferogram 5.20.(f). An increase of the obstacle's power makes the vortex pair separate from one another as shown in Fig.5.20.(b) and evolve in the direction of the flow. On figures 5.20.(c) and 5.20.(d) one sees the nucleation of two vortex pairs highlighted by the fork structures on the corresponding interferograms. And in the last image 5.20.(e) three vortex pair are nucleated from the obstacle. Their orientation and localisation are indicated on the figures.

We plot in figure 5.21 the number of the nucleated vortex pairs as a function of the obstacle's strength P_{ob} .

It shows that the number of vortex pairs increases with the intensity of the fluid-of-light beam. This result is expected, since the behaviour of the fluid-of-light depends significantly on the characteristics of the obstacle. The vertical grey boxes on the figure delimit the horizontal error bars. They are defined as the regions in which the measurement were not carried out. Therefore, one cannot be sure at which intensity new vortex pairs appear.

To sum up, all these results present only a preliminary study of optical vortices observation in a fluid-

of-light. At the moment, a more systematic work is being made on this subject.

Figure 5.20: Figure of the intensity distributions of the fluid-of-light (upper and middle rows) and its interferograms (lower panel) for various values of the obstacle strength P_{ob} . The ratio v/c_s of the fluid-of-light was fixed to 0.6. The power of the obstacle P_{ob} was varied from $16 \mu\text{W}$ to $240 \mu\text{W}$. The white cross on the images of the upper row marks the position of the obstacle.

Figure 5.21: number of nucleated vortex pair versus the power of the optical obstacle. The diameter of the obstacle is fixed at $120 \mu\text{m}$. The grey bars on the figure represent the horizontal error bars.

5.5 Chapter 4 summary and perspectives

We have presented in this chapter a preliminary study and an experimental observation of vortex shedding in a fluid-of-light flowing around an obstacle. We have derived the equation that describes the shape of the vortex in a fluid-of-light pointing out that the vortex core has the same order of magnitude of the system's healing length ξ . Also in this chapter, we showed that the vortex revolving velocity is quantised in $1/n_0k_0$ and we gave the physical mechanism that explains the optical vortex nucleation in a fluid-of-light. Finally, in the results part, we presented the intensity distribution of a fluid-of-light with vortex/anti-vortex pairs. We showed through the measurement of the vortex diameter that this latter declines with the square root of the fluid-of-light density. Last, we have presented a study of the vortex pair number as a function of the obstacle's strength. As perspectives of this chapter, one can emphasise multiplying the number of obstacles and expect to generate multiple vortex/anti-vortex pairs and dark solitons. These structures might interact with each other and yield a turbulent regime of a fluid-of-light. The turbulence in quantum fluids and in fluids-of-light is called quantum turbulence and it occurs when a system comprises many interacting quantised vortices. At the moment, a more systematic study on our experiment is being made by multiplying the number of obstacles. A first observation of the so-called snake instability was observed in our system and further work aiming to investigate the quantum turbulence in the fluid-of-light is a part of our perspectives.

Chapter 6

Conclusion and perspectives

Broadly speaking, we have presented in this thesis an experimental study of some hydrodynamical concepts transposed into the field of nonlinear optics. In chapter 2, we have described the two optical systems capable of simulating hydrodynamical features. We have seen that the concept of a fluid-of-light is premised upon the establishment of effective interactions between photons on the one hand, and assigning photons an effective mass on the other hand. In the propagating geometry, the nonlinear optical susceptibility of the material offers the possibility to tune effective interactions between photons, while the effective mass is guaranteed by the paraxial approximation.

In the self-defocusing regime, the intensity of a laser beam is assimilated to a density of a fluid, the propagation distance of the laser beam is considered as the time evolution of the fluid-of-light. The concept of the fluid-of-light velocity is introduced through the gradient of the laser beam's phase and finally, the nonlinear refractive index defines the sound velocity in the fluid-of-light. The formalism allowing to retrieve this analogy is the Madelung transformation. Additionally, the Bogoliubov dispersion relation witnessing a possible superfluid state, is derived through the analysis of a perturbation evolving on top of the fluid-of-light.

The investigation of the hydrodynamical features of light requires a very good understanding and mastering of the nonlinearity type exhibited by the medium. This has been the objective of chapter 3. Along this chapter, we have presented a simple technique to measure the nonlinear refractive index of our medium. This technique relies on the effect of spatial self-phase modulation (sSPM) which for its part arises in media presenting an intensity-dependent refractive index. The sSPM effect modifies the phase of the propagating Gaussian profile in a manner that the spatial spectrum expands. Thus giving birth to a diffraction pattern as a result to an interference of waves with a similar transverse wavenumber. A rigorous analysis of the diffraction pattern enables one to determine the behaviour of the nonlinear refractive index change, thanks to the connection between the accumulated phase and the refractive index of the medium.

In chapter 4, the superfluid behaviour of light is investigated with the help of the Landau criterion. The latter establishes a condition for the generation of an elementary excitation in a quantum fluid (frictional regime) through the comparison of the flow velocity and the sound velocity of a fluid-of-light. The basic idea was to study the flow of a fluid-of-light past an obstacle. It was shown through the observation of the fluid-of-light density the occurrence of a superfluid regime characterised by the absence of the diffraction cone in the vicinity of the obstacle. Moreover, we extracted a direct optical analogue of the drag-force exerted by the fluid-of-light on the obstacle and we measured the corresponding displacement. As a result, both quantities drop to zero in the superfluid regime of the fluid-of-light. Another hydrodynamical feature of the fluid-of-light is the possibility to observe vortical structures. In chapter 5, we reported a preliminary experimental observation of vortex pair shedding due to the interaction between the fluid-of-light and a strong obstacle. When twice the flow velocity of the fluid-of-light at the poles of the obstacle exceeds the sound velocity,

then excitations in the form of a vortex pair with opposite circulations are created. In addition to this, a measurement of the vortex diameter as a function of the fluid-of-light density has revealed that the vortex diameter declines as the square root of the fluid-of-light density. Also, we have studied the impact of the obstacle's strength on the vortex emission regime. This has shown that, the stronger the obstacle, the more vortex pairs are emitted.

In spite of the experimental study we have carried out during the past three years, future directions and perspectives are still to be investigated in the frame of fluids-of-light.

Thanks to photo-inscription techniques in nonlinear media, the study of superfluidity in complex environments is thus possible and can be investigated in our set-up. Such complex media can hold obstacles (optical defects) with different shapes (i.e. triangular) and different strengths. In addition to obstacles, they also can hold waveguides. This complexity will allow the investigation of the interplay between the superfluid regime of the fluid-of-light and localisation effects. Another effect to investigate is the quantum turbulence phenomenon. The latter takes place when a large number of vortex/anti-vortex pairs as well as dark solitons are interacting. Using our set-up we can increase the number of obstacles and generate many vortex/antivortex pairs to observe and investigate the quantum turbulent regime^[210]. Another interesting feature possible to characterise in our system, is the Casimir force^[213]. The latter consists in the appearance of an attracting force between two material plates placed in vacuum. This is because of the fluctuations of the quantised electromagnetic field. In the context of the propagating geometry, these fluctuations can be triggered through the fluid-of-light beam. As for the material plates, they can be mimicked through photo-inducing refractive index drops (optical plates). A concrete displacement of these optical plates can be measured and may demonstrate the existence of the optical Casimir force in the fluid-of-light frame. There are some other phenomena to investigate in our set-up like the BKT transition^[185] characterised by the generation of vortex/antivortex pair between the superfluid and frictional regime, as well as the effect of the spin-orbit coupling^[214] on the behaviour of the fluid-of-light.

Appendix A

Fluids-of-light in the propagating geometry

Appendix A.A Derivation of the light's hydrodynamical equations

In this paragraph we fully derive the hydrodynamical description of a light beam propagating in a nonlinear medium. We give the refractive index change in its generic form $\Delta n(I)$. To get the hydrodynamical equations of light, we should inject the Madelung transformation in the nonlinear wave equation (2.3). For the sake of simplicity, we assume that the Madelung transformation is written as follows:

$$A(\mathbf{r}, t) = \sqrt{\rho(\mathbf{r}, t)} e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)} = U(\mathbf{r}, t) e^{i\varphi(\mathbf{r}, t)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In order not to clutter the demonstration we suggest omitting the variables \mathbf{r} and t (or z). However, we should keep in mind that the phase and amplitude depend on these variables. Therefore, we write the wave equation as follows:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} U e^{i\varphi} = -\frac{1}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 U e^{i\varphi} + k_0 \Delta n(I) U e^{i\varphi} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

The L.H.S term can be calculated as follows:

$$i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} U e^{i\varphi} = i e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} U - U e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \varphi \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Let us now calculate the term $\nabla_{\perp}^2 U e^{i\varphi}$. to do so, we use the Cartesian coordinates system. We know that in these coordinates $\nabla_{\perp}^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$. Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} U e^{i\varphi} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U + i U e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi \right] = e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} U + 2i e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi \\ &\quad + i U e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \varphi - U e^{i\varphi} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi \right]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

With respect to y :

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} U e^{i\varphi} &= \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left[e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} U + i U e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \right] = e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} U + 2i e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial y} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \\ &\quad + i U e^{i\varphi} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \varphi - U e^{i\varphi} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \right]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Thus, the term $(1/2k_0n_0)\nabla_{\perp}^2 U e^{i\varphi}$ can be expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2k_0n_0}\nabla_{\perp}^2 U e^{i\varphi} &= \frac{e^{i\varphi}}{2k_0n_0} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} U - U \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi \right]^2 + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} U - U \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \right]^2 \right] \\ &+ \frac{ie^{i\varphi}}{2k_0n_0} \left[2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi + U \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \varphi + 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi + U \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \varphi \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Now, separating the imaginary part and the reel parts of the equations (A.3) and (A.6). And using eq. (A.2), simplifying by $e^{i\varphi}$, the imaginary part yields:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} U + \frac{1}{2k_0n_0} \left[U \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right] \varphi + 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi + 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial y} U \times \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \right] = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Lets assume that $v = (1/k_0n_0)\nabla_{\perp} \varphi$, $v_x = (1/k_0n_0)(\partial\varphi/\partial x)$ and $v_y = (1/k_0n_0)(\partial\varphi/\partial y)$. Therefore, equation (A.7) becomes:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} U + \frac{1}{2} U \nabla_{\perp} v + v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} U + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} U \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Knowing that $(\partial U/\partial z) = (1/2\sqrt{\rho})(\partial\rho/\partial z)$, equation A.8 takes the following form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \rho + \rho \nabla_{\perp} v + v_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \rho + v_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \rho = 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Hence, the above equation can simplify to:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \rho + \rho \nabla_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla_{\perp} \rho = 0 \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Replacing the space coordinate with time, equation A.10 is the continuity equation of a fluid:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho + \nabla_{\perp} \cdot (\rho \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Let us now develop the reel part of the equation (A.2). Considering only the reel parts of the equations (A.3) and (A.6) and simplifying $e^{i\varphi}$, we get:

$$-U \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \varphi + \frac{1}{2k_0n_0} \left[\left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right] U - U \left(\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \varphi \right]^2 + \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial y} \varphi \right]^2 \right) \right] - k_0 \Delta n(I) U = 0 \quad (\text{A.12})$$

Using the expressions v_x and v_y we simplify the expression (A.12):

$$-U \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \varphi + \frac{1}{2k_0n_0} \left[\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2} \right] U - U \frac{k_0n_0}{2} (v_x^2 + v_y^2) - k_0 \Delta n(I) U = 0 \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Knowing that $v^2 = v_x^2 + v_y^2$, multiplying equation (A.13) by $1/U$ as well as replacing U by $\sqrt{\rho}$ and z by t we obtain:

$$\frac{1}{n_0} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \varphi + \frac{1}{2} k_0 v^2 + k_0 \frac{\Delta n(I)}{n_0} - \frac{1}{2k_0n_0^2} \frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

To find the equation of momentum conservation for a fluid-of-light (2.14), we apply the transverse gradient operator on the equation (A.14) and we multiply it by ρ

$$\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial t} v + \frac{1}{2} \rho \nabla_{\perp} v^2 + \rho \nabla_{\perp} \frac{\Delta n(I)}{n_0} - \frac{\rho}{2k_0^2 n_0^2} \nabla_{\perp} \frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.15})$$

For a Kerr-type nonlinearity (i.e. $\Delta n(I) = n_2 I$), we can express the above equation as follows:

$$\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial t} v + \frac{1}{2} \rho \nabla_{\perp} v^2 + \rho \nabla_{\perp} P - \frac{\rho}{2k_0^2 n_0^2} \nabla_{\perp} \frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2 \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{\rho}} = 0, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where $P = (n_2 I^2 / 2n_0)$ is the pressure term. The above equation is the momentum conservation equation besides the quantum pressure term. Note that for the Kerr-like regime of the photorefractive nonlinearity, the nonlinear refractive index is given by: $\Delta n(I) = \frac{\Delta n_{\max}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I$. Therefore, the expression of the pressure yields: $P = (\Delta n_{\max} I^2 / 2n_0 I_{\text{sat}})$. And the equation of the momentum conservation remains the same.

Appendix A.B Derivation of the Bogoliubov dispersion relation for a fluid-of-light

In this subsection, we suggest to derive the Bogoliubov dispersion relation (2.31). We have specified earlier that we should consider a perturbation on the top of the fluid-of-light and study the evolution of this perturbation. Therefore, we inject the expression of the fluid-of-light in addition to the perturbation in the equation of propagation (2.3).

We remind that the expression of the perturbation is the following:

$$A(r, z) = \sqrt{I_0} e^{-i\phi z} + [u(r) e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r) e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The term I is the intensity of the fluid-of-light, we assume that it is constant, ϕ is the phase accumulated by the fluid-of-light through the propagation in the nonlinear medium assumed here to be a Kerr-type medium, $u(r)$ and $v(r)$ are the amplitudes of the perturbation. \mathbf{k}_z is the wave vector of the perturbation.

The L.H.S term of the propagation equation is expressed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} i \frac{\partial}{\partial z} A(r, z) &= [k_z u(r) e^{-ik_z z} - k_z v^*(r) e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} \\ &+ [\phi u(r) e^{-ik_z z} + \phi v^*(r) e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z}, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.18})$$

the term of diffraction can be calculated:

$$-\frac{1}{k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 A(r, z) = -\frac{e^{-ik_z z}}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 u(r) - \frac{e^{ik_z z}}{2k_0 n_0} \nabla_{\perp}^2 v^*(r) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

And we calculate the term of the nonlinearity $k_0 n_2 |A(r, z)|^2 A(r, z)$. First we suggest to calculate the term $|A(r, z)|^2$:

$$\begin{aligned} |A(r, z)|^2 &= A(r, z) A^*(r, z) = \left[\sqrt{I_0} e^{-i\phi z} + [u(r) e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r) e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} \right] \\ &\times \left[\sqrt{I_0} e^{i\phi z} + [u^*(r) e^{ik_z z} + v(r) e^{-ik_z z}] e^{i\phi z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

$$|A(r, z)|^2 = I_0 + \sqrt{I_0} [u^*(r)e^{ik_z z} + v(r)e^{-ik_z z}] + \sqrt{I_0} [u(r)e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r)e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} + \mathcal{O}(u^2(r) + v^2(r) + u(r)v(r)), \quad (\text{A.21})$$

with respect to the first order terms (i.e. $u(r)$ and $v(r)$) the second order ones (i.e. $u^2(r)$, $v^2(r)$ and $u(r)v(r)$) are negligible. This is because we have a small perturbation. That is why in the last equation we wrote $\mathcal{O}(u^2(r) + v^2(r) + u(r)v(r))$.

Let us now calculate the term $k_0 n_2 |A(r, z)|^2 A(r, z)$, we multiply eq.(A.21) by eq.(A.17):

$$k_0 n_2 |A(r, z)|^2 A(r, z) = k_0 n_2 \sqrt{I_0^3} e^{-i\phi z} + 2I_0 [u(r)e^{-ik_z z} + v^*(r)e^{ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} + k_0 n_2 I_0 [u^*(r)e^{ik_z z} + v(r)e^{-ik_z z}] e^{-i\phi z} + \mathcal{O}(u^2(r) + v^2(r) + u(r)v(r)) \quad (\text{A.22})$$

Collecting all the terms evolving in $e^{ik_z z}$ and $e^{-ik_z z}$ of the equations (A.18) and (A.22), and eliminating the term $e^{i\phi z}$, we get the following equations. for the term $e^{-ik_z z}$:

$$k_z u(r) = \left[-\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} - \phi + 2k_0 n_2 I_0 \right] u(r) + k_0 n_2 I_0 v(r) \quad (\text{A.23})$$

Taking the complex conjugate of the equation resulting from the term $e^{ik_z z}$ yields:

$$-k_z v(r) = \left[-\frac{\nabla_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} - \phi + 2k_0 n_2 I_0 \right] v(r) + k_0 n_2 I_0 u(r) \quad (\text{A.24})$$

Equations (A.23) and (A.24) are the Bogoliubov equations. They can be solved numerically. However, we can solve them analytically, in the case of a perturbation having the form of the plane wave $u(r) = u_0 e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{r}}$ and $v(r) = v_0 e^{i\mathbf{k}_{\perp} \cdot \mathbf{r}}$. And knowing that the accumulated phase ϕ is equal to the nonlinear phase $\phi_{nl} = k_0 n_2 I_0$ then the Bogoliubov equations become:

$$k_z u_0 = -\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} u_0 + k_0 n_0 I_0 (u_0 + v_0) \quad (\text{A.25})$$

$$-k_z v_0 = -\frac{k_{\perp}^2}{2k_0 n_0} v_0 + k_0 n_0 I_0 (u_0 + v_0) \quad (\text{A.26})$$

The system of equation (A.25) and (A.26) is easily solvable by eliminating u_0 and v_0 . And one directly gets the Bogoliubov dispersion relation:

$$k_z = \sqrt{\frac{k_{\perp}^4}{4k_0^2 n_0^2} - \frac{n_2 I k_{\perp}^2}{n_0}} \quad (\text{A.27})$$

Therefore, for a photorefractive medium and in the case of a Kerr-like nonlinearity (i.e. $\Delta n(I) = \frac{\Delta n_{\max}}{I_{\text{sat}}} I$), the Bogoliubov dispersion relation can be expressed as follows:

$$k_z = \sqrt{\frac{k_{\perp}^4}{4k_0^2 n_0^2} - \frac{\Delta n_{\max} I k_{\perp}^2}{n_0 I_{\text{sat}}}} \quad (\text{A.28})$$

Appendix A.C The Madelung transformation for a quantum fluid

Given a non-uniform interacting Bose-gas near the absolute zero temperature $T \approx 0$ K, the many-body operator $\hat{\psi}$ can be replaced with a classical field wave function ψ . This is analogous to the electromagnetic limit of the quantum electrodynamics in the case of a large number of photons at the same state. The Gross-Pitaevskii equation was derived by Gross and Pitaevskii in 1961. It plays the same role as Maxwell's equations in electromagnetism. It is given by^[12] :

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi(r,t)}{\partial t} = \left(-\frac{\hbar}{2m} \nabla^2 + V_{ext}(r) + g|\psi(r,t)|^2 \right) \psi(r,t) \quad (\text{A.29})$$

Where $\psi(r,t)$ is the wave function describing the condensate, V_{ext} is an external potential applied on the condensate and $g = 4\pi\hbar a_s/m$ is the interaction coefficient, it depends on the scattering length of two interacting bosons a_s .

From eq. (A.29) one can easily retrieve the continuity equation by multiplying by $\psi^*(r,t)$ ^[12].

$$\frac{\partial n(r,t)}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{j}(r,t) = 0 \quad (\text{A.30})$$

$\mathbf{j}(r,t) = n(r,t)(\hbar/m)\nabla s(r,t)$ is the current density of the condensate, where the density of the condensate is written in the form:

$$\psi(r,t) = \sqrt{n(r,t)} e^{is(r,t)} \quad (\text{A.31})$$

This allows to define the velocity of the condensate flow as:

$$\mathbf{v}_s = \frac{\hbar}{m} \nabla s(r,t) \quad (\text{A.32})$$

Injecting the expression of $\psi(r,t)$ in the GPE allows to obtain the momentum conservation equation of the fluid :

$$\hbar \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}_s}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2} m \nabla v_s^2 + \nabla (V_{ext} + gn) - \frac{\hbar}{2m} \nabla \left(\frac{\nabla^2 \sqrt{n}}{\sqrt{n}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A.33})$$

The R.H.S term is the quantum pressure. Equations (A.30) and (A.33) are equivalent to the Euler's equations found in hydrodynamics physics.

Appendix A.D Bogoliubov dispersion relation in quantum fluids

This section was radically written on the basis of the remarkable book of Pitaevskii and Stringari.^[215]

A.D.1 Bogoliubov theory for weakly interacting Bose gas - ground state energy

It is known that an ideal Bose gas at the condensation temperature T_c has an infinite compressibility which is not the case for a non-ideal Bose gas. Therefore, we should admit that interactions between particles change the properties of the gas. For a dilute gas, where the range of interatomic force r_0 is smaller than

the average distance between particles, we have to take into account only of pairs of interacting particles.

Let us consider the presence of the condensate in a Bose gas. This implies that the linear momentum of particles satisfies the following condition $p(r_0/\hbar) \ll 1$. As a consequence to this, the scattering amplitude of two interacting particles is completely independent of the energy and the scattering angle of the particles. Therefore the interaction potential of the pairs can be considered as a function of an effective potential V_{eff} . The Hamiltonian of this system is given

$$\hat{H} = \sum \frac{p^2}{2m} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_p + \frac{1}{2V} \sum V_q \hat{a}_{p_1+q}^\dagger \hat{a}_{p_2-q}^\dagger \hat{a}_{p_1} \hat{a}_{p_2} \quad (\text{A.34})$$

Where \hat{a}_p and \hat{a}_p^\dagger are respectively the creation and the annihilation operator of the particle with momenta p , the 2nd R.H.S term represents the interaction term between two particles of momenta p_1 and p_2 , $V_q = \int V(r) e^{-iqr/\hbar} dr$ is the Fourier transform of the interaction potential between two particles and V is the volume occupied by the gas. It is difficult to solve this system by considering the microscopic potential V_q . According to what we said earlier about a dilute gas, we can replace the microscopic potential $V(q)$ by an effective one V_{eff} . Therefore we can define for small momenta values, the interaction potential of the system by $V_0 = \int V_{\text{eff}}.dr$. Since the current fluid is a weakly interacting Bose gas, the potential is considered to be small for all distances between particles. This allows to have an accurate lowest order approximation.

Knowing that for a dilute gas the occupation number of atoms for energy states other than $p = 0$ is not null but it is small. Thus, we can neglect in the Hamiltonian all the terms with a linear momentum $p \neq 0$. And then using the expression of the condensate, $\hat{a}_0 \approx \sqrt{N_0} \approx N$ in the Hamiltonian (A.34), where N is the number of atoms of the gas and N_0 is the number of atoms occupying the lowest energy state. One gets the expression for the lowest energy state.

$$E_0 = \frac{N^2 V_0}{2V} = \frac{1}{2} N n g \quad (\text{A.35})$$

Where V_0 obtained for the first approximation is $V_0 = 4\pi\hbar^2 a/m$, a is called the scattering length of particles.

From the equation (A.35), one can derive the pressure of this Bose gas $P = -\frac{\partial E_0}{\partial V} = gn^2/2$. On the contrary to an ideal gas, the weakly interacting Bose gas has a finite pressure P as well as a finite compressibility $\frac{\partial n}{\partial P} = \frac{1}{gn}$. Using the relation between sound velocity and the pressure in classical hydrodynamics $\frac{\partial n}{\partial P} = \frac{1}{mc_s^2}$, one finds an important expression relating the speed of sound c_s and the nonlinear interaction potential g .

$$c_s = \sqrt{\frac{gn}{m}} \quad (\text{A.36})$$

A.D.2 Excitation spectrum - Higher order approximation

The lowest energy state E_0 in the previous paragraph was obtained by considering only the lowest order operators $\hat{a}_p, \hat{a}_p^\dagger$. Now in the Hamiltonian of the system, we consider the 2nd order (quadratic) terms we can write it in the following form:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{H} = & \frac{V_0}{2V} \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_0 \hat{a}_0 + \sum_{p=0} \frac{p^2}{2m} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_p + \frac{V_0}{2V} \sum_{p \neq 0} 4 \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_0 \hat{a}_p \\ & + \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_{-p}^\dagger \hat{a}_0 \hat{a}_0 + \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_p \hat{a}_{-p} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.37})$$

As for the scattering length a , we can express it to the second order as a function of the potential V_0 , $a = (m/4\pi\hbar^2)(V_0 - (V_0^2/V) \sum_{p \neq 0} (m/p^2))$. Thus, the interaction potential V_0 can be expressed as follows:

$$V_0 = g \left(1 + \frac{g}{V} \sum_{p \neq 0} \frac{m}{p^2} \right) \quad (\text{A.38})$$

If we carry out the previous procedure $\hat{a}_0 = \sqrt{N}$ on the expression of the Hamiltonian (A.37) and if we take into account the normalization expression $\sum_p \hat{a}_0^\dagger \hat{a}_0 = N$, one finds a simple expression of the Hamiltonian.

$$\hat{H} = g \frac{N^2}{2V} + \sum \frac{p^2}{2m} \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_p + \frac{1}{2} gn \sum_{p \neq 0} \left(2 \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_p + \hat{a}_p^\dagger \hat{a}_{-p}^\dagger + \hat{a}_p \hat{a}_{-p} + \frac{mgn}{p^2} \right) \quad (\text{A.39})$$

The current Hamiltonian (A.39) can be diagonalised using the Bogoliubov transformation

$$\hat{a}_p = u_p \hat{b}_p + v_{-p}^* \hat{b}_{-p} \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{a}_p^\dagger = u_p^* \hat{b}_p^\dagger + v_{-p} \hat{b}_{-p}^\dagger. \quad (\text{A.40})$$

This transformation defines a new set of operators, \hat{b}_p and \hat{b}_p^\dagger , called the Bogoliubov operators. u_p and v_p are simple coefficients chosen in a way to cancel all the non-diagonal terms of the Hamiltonian. Thereafter the resulting expression of the diagonalized Hamiltonian can be written in the basis of operators $\hat{b}_p, \hat{b}_p^\dagger$ as:

$$\hat{H} = E_0 + \sum \varepsilon(p) \hat{b}_p^\dagger \hat{b}_p \quad (\text{A.41})$$

With, E_0 is the lowest energy state given by :

$$E_0 = g \frac{N^2}{2V} + \sum_{p \neq 0} \left(\varepsilon(p) - gn - \frac{p^2}{2m} + \frac{m(gn)^2}{p^2} \right) \quad (\text{A.42})$$

And $\varepsilon(p)$ is the Bogoliubov dispersion relation. It is expressed by the following relation:

$$\varepsilon(p) = \sqrt{\frac{gn}{m} p^2 + \left(\frac{p^2}{2m} \right)^2} \quad (\text{A.43})$$

The equation (A.41) allows to interpret the system of weakly interacting particles in a Bose gas, as a system of non-interacting quasi-particles of energy $\varepsilon(p)$ and creation, (annihilation) operators $\hat{b}_p^\dagger, (\hat{b}_p)$.

We represent in figure A.1 the Bogoliubov dispersion relation of a quantum fluid.

Figure A.1: Figure of the dispersion relation $\varepsilon(p)$ of the elementary excitations versus the linear momentum p . \hbar/ξ represents the limit of the transition between the free particle-like and phonon-like regimes^[215].

A.D.3 Small amplitude oscillations - Bogoliubov dispersion relation

The goal in this paragraph is to derive the Bogoliubov dispersion under the assumption of the small-amplitude oscillation. To do so, we have to introduce a small perturbation on the system and then we will see how this perturbation evolves on top of the fluid.

Let us suppose a fluid at condensation temperature T_c . The wave function $\psi_0(r, t)$ of this condensate in the absence of perturbation (equilibrium state) is written:

$$\psi_0(r, t) = \sqrt{n(r)} e^{-i\mu t/\hbar} \quad (\text{A.44})$$

Where $n(r)$ is the density of the condensate in the equilibrium state, μ is the chemical potential.

Now, if we suppose the existence of the perturbation, we can write the condensate wave function in the following form:

$$\psi(r, t) = \psi_0(r, t) + \delta\psi(r, t) \quad (\text{A.45})$$

The solutions we are looking for are of the following form:

$$\delta\psi(r, t) = (u(r)e^{-i\omega t} - v^*(r)e^{i\omega t})e^{-i\mu t/\hbar} \quad (\text{A.46})$$

The functions u , v are respectively similar to the functions u_p , v_p in the Bogoliubov transformation (A.40) for non-ideal atomic Bose gas. If we consider a uniform Bose gas, its density $n(r)$ does not depend on r (space coordinates) nor on the chemical potential μ is equal to gn . Injecting the wave function of the non-equilibrium state (A.45) in the GPE (A.29) we get a set of differential equations of u and v :

$$\begin{aligned} \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\Delta^2 + gn - \hbar\omega \right] u(r) - gn.v(r) &= 0 \\ \left[-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m}\Delta^2 + gn - \hbar\omega \right] v(r) - gn.u(r) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.47})$$

We can take $u(r) = e^{iq \cdot r}$ and $v(r) = e^{iq \cdot r}$ because of the invariance in the translation of the Bose gas. Finally, if we insert $u(r)$ and $v(r)$ in the equation (A.47) we get the Bogoliubov dispersion relation for the quantum fluid:

$$(\hbar\omega)^2 = \left(\frac{\hbar^2 q^2}{2m}\right)^2 + \frac{\hbar^2 q^2}{m} gn \quad (\text{A.48})$$

Appendix B

Experiment and techniques

Appendix B.A Experimental set-up - experimental control of the parameters

B.A.1 Experimental set-up

A sketch of the experimental set-up is depicted in figure B.1. Qualitatively it consists in two laser beams propagating through the nonlinear crystal.

Two beams are emitted green (red) respectively from a solid-state laser (He-Ne Laser). The green (red) beam plays the role of the fluid-of-light (obstacle) in the frame of quantum fluids. The probe beam (green) having a diameter $D_f = 2$ mm passes through a telescope to enlarge its diameter for the purpose of maximising the efficiency of the wavefront shaping. We control its power through the couple half-wave plate $\lambda/2$ and a linear polariser. This latter allows to fix the polarisation of the beam chosen in here to be horizontally oriented optimised for the SLM and the DMD. We use a polarising beam splitter to pick up a reference beam (local oscillator). The origin beam passes through a spatial light modulator (SLM). This latter permits a good control of the beam wave-front through changing the phase of the laser beam (we will detail the functioning of the SLM later). Here we make use of the SLM to change the incidence angle of the probe beam. As stressed before we need to vary the angle of the probe beam to change the fluid-of-light velocity $v = \theta_{in}/n_e$.

We image the facet of the SLM at the input of the nonlinear crystal through a system of two 4f lenses ($\{l_{g3}, l_{g4}\}, \{l_{g5}, l_{g6}\}$). The digital micro-mirror device (DMD) placed at the Fourier space serves as a spatial filter allowing to pick the adequate propagation mode of the fluid-of-light beam. We image as well the facet of the DMD using a 4f system of lenses ($\{l_{g4}, l_{g7}\}$). The probe beam is thus sent to the nonlinear crystal. The system of 4f lenses ensures as well the adequate diameter of the fluid-of-light beam. The focal distances of the lenses l_{g3}, l_{g4}, l_{g5} and l_{g6} are respectively $f_{g3} = 200$ mm, $f_{g4} = 150$ mm, $f_{g5} = 500$ mm and $f_{g6} = 100$ mm. The probe beam has a diameter at $1/e^2$ of $D_f = 270$ μ m at the input (output) of the crystal.

Simultaneously we expand the diameter of the pump (red) beam using a telescope to enhance the efficiency of the wave front shaping. We also control its power by the pair of half-wave plate $\lambda/2$ and a linear polariser. Similarly to the probe beam the polarisation direction is oriented along the horizontal axis because of the SLM (the liquid crystal molecules of the SLM are oriented horizontally). Afterward, the

pump beam passes through the SLM to generate a Bessel serving as the obstacle. The DMD serves as well for the pump beam as spatial filter. We make use of two 4f to image the facet of the SLM at the input of the crystal and to reduce the diameter of the obstacle D_{ob} beam measured ($D_{\text{ob}} \approx 15 \mu\text{m}$) at the input and the output of the crystal. The focal distances of l_{r3} , l_{r4} , l_{r5} and l_{r6} are respectively $f_{r3} = 250 \text{ mm}$, $f_{r4} = 200 \text{ mm}$, $f_{r5} = 300 \text{ mm}$ and $f_{r6} = 100 \text{ mm}$. We use two CMOS cameras to visualise the output of the nonlinear crystal in the near and far-fields.

The phase of the fluid-of-light beam at the output of the crystal is accessible by interfering with the local oscillator. This latter is coupled into a single mode (SMF). The diameter of the local oscillator at the output of the fiber is equal to 1.5 mm , it is then reduced to $500 \mu\text{m}$ using a telescope ($\{l_{g10}, l_{g11}\}$) with focal distances respectively equal to $f_{g10} = 300 \text{ mm}$, $f_{g11} = 100 \text{ mm}$. The power of the local oscillator and its polarisation are controlled through the half-wave plate and a linear polariser to optimise its interference with the fluid-of-light beam.

The nonlinear medium consists in a $5 \times 5 \times 10 \text{ mm}^3$ Strontium Barium Niobate (SBN:61) photorefractive crystal doped with cerium (0.02%) to enhance its photoconductivity albeit it induces linear absorption (3.2 dB.cm^{-1}).

The 4f system ($\{l_1, l_2\}$) allows us to translate the image of the crystal's output to avoid cluttering the set-up. We then use a microscopic objective to visualise the output facet of the crystal.

We precise that this experimental set-up presents a few interesting features, thanks to the SLM, the DMD and to the other optical devices. The most important characteristic is the possibility to invert the roles of the fluid-of-light and the DMD just by changing the masks used by the SLM and the DMD. Another important feature is its automatic control of the physical parameters, particularly, the intensity and the angle of incidence of the fluid-of-light laser beam.

Figure B.1: Figure of the experimental set-up. Two laser beams are wave-front shaped and then led to propagate simultaneously in the nonlinear crystal. The green laser beam plays the role of the fluid-of-light and the red beam assumes the role of the obstacle. A visualisation set-up allows to access to the near-field as well as the far-field through the use of two cameras.

B.A.2 The spatial light modulator (SLM)

Introduction to SLM A spatial light modulator is a device that allows to spatially modulate a beam of light. They provide a complete spatial control of the beam through the modulation of its phase, amplitude, or both. They are widely used in video projector devices. SLMs are screens containing liquid crystals (state of matter that possess physical properties of both solids and liquids). A pixel of the SLM's screen measures approximately $10 \times 10 \mu\text{m}^2$ containing liquid crystals. Therefore, the precision of the modulation by the SLM is limited by the size of the pixel. The molecules of the liquid crystals have a rod shape presenting birefringence properties controllable by the electrical voltage. The modulation of the amplitude or the phase of the beam is achieved thanks to the controllable birefringence of the liquid crystals. There are two types of liquid crystals, nematic in which the positional arrangement of the molecules is random and smectic liquid crystals that are positionally well ordered in one direction (see figure B.2).

Figure B.2: Figure of the molecular distribution of liquid crystals. The nematic distribution is represented in the left panel showing a disordered arrangement of the molecules. The smectic in the right side displays an ordered arrangement.

The SLM we used is a phase modulator that has a physical screen measuring 15×12 with a resolution of 1280×1024 . The spatially modulated signal is accessible after its reflexion on the SLM's screen. We control each pixel by a CMOS Backplane and a controller via a visual communication (DVI signal) with a computer. Thus, for controlling the orientation of the liquid crystal molecules, we need to upload phase images to the SLM. Each pixel can modulate the phase from 0 to 2π . We would like to point out that enlarging the beam hitting the screen of the SLM allows to have an efficient spatial modulation because we increase the number of pixels serving for the modulation. This is the reason for which we enlarge the diameters of the fluid-of-light and the Bessel beams before the SLM. Let us show the phase only functioning of the SLM.

We have said earlier that the molecules of the liquid crystal have a rod shape presenting a different refractive indices along the two principal directions. We denote by n_e and n_o respectively the indices of refraction along the extraordinary and ordinary axis of the molecules. Generally, the refractive index along the extraordinary axis is larger the refractive index of the ordinary axis (i.e. $n_e > n_o$). Therefore, the maximum phase acquired by a wave propagating through the liquid crystal is given as follows:

$$\varphi_{lc} = k_0 d (n_e - n_o), \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where k_0 is the wave number of the laser beam propagating through the SLM and d is the thickness of the liquid crystal along the axis of propagation assumed here to be the z -axis.

To get a phase only modulation of the SLM, we have adjust the polarisation of the laser beam illuminating the liquid crystal, in fact, let us suppose a laser beam with an electric field defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{E}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} E_x \\ E_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The Jones matrix of a transmissive spatial light modulator is given as follows:

$$\mathbf{T}_{\text{lc}} = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Denoting by \mathbf{E}_2 the electric field at the output of the spatial light modulator (see figure B.3), it is calculated as follows:

$$\mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{E}_1^T \mathbf{T}_{\text{lc}} = \begin{bmatrix} E_x e^{-i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} \\ E_y e^{i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Therefore, to have a phase only modulation, one should fix the polarisation of the input field \mathbf{E}_1 at one of the directions x -axis or y -axis. we chose the direction of the extraordinary axis to have a maximum phase modulation and we write the output field in this case as follows:

$$\mathbf{E}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} E_x e^{-i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{E}_1 e^{-i\varphi_{\text{lc}}} \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Thereafter, changing φ_{lc} allows to obtain a wavefront shaped beam.

Figure B.3: Illustration of the propagation of a wave through a spatial light modulator

As earlier said, we use the SLM to change the angle of incidence of the fluid-of-light beam and to create a Bessel beam for the obstacle. To do so, we divide the screen of the SLM by uploading two distinct phase masks (for the fluid-of-light and for the Bessel).

Concerning the fluid beam we use a blazed phase mask. We know from the theory of diffraction that we can change the angle of incidence of the laser beam using a blazed grating dielectrics through changing its periodicity (see figure B.4).

Figure B.4: Figure of blazed grating material. A laser beam hits the grating and undergoes a reflection. The angle of reflection is controlled by the period of the grating denoted by d .

At the output of the gratings, we will at least have three modes propagating in different directions called diffraction modes (modes $\{0, 1, -1\}$). The mode $m = 0$ does not change its direction of propagation (it has the same direction of the incident beam). So we will use both the modes 1 and -1 . The value of the angles at the output of a blazed grating for the modes 1 and -1 satisfies the following condition:

$$\sin(\beta_m) = \frac{m\lambda_0}{d} - \sin(\alpha) \quad (\text{B.6})$$

Where m corresponds to the mode of diffraction. Therefore the variation of the angle β_m depends on the periodicity of the blazed grating. The phase mask type we upload to the SLM and the corresponding intensity distribution of the chosen mode are displayed in figure B.5:

Figure B.5: Figure the mask uploaded to the SLM in the left side and the resulting intensity distribution blurred by the interference of diffraction modes. Here the DMD has no contribution.

The main problem we faced using this technique is the disturbing interference occurring on the beam in the near-field B.5. This is because at the facet of the SLM (input of the crystal since we image the facet at the input of medium), the modes are sufficiently close to yield an interference pattern. It is at this stage

that the role of the DMD is important. Placed at the Fourier space of the SLM, the DMD allows to filter the disturbing modes generated by the blazed grating. The type of the mask uploaded to the DMD is displayed in figure B.6.

Figure B.6: Masks uploaded to the SLM and the DMD illustrated in the left part of the figure. On the right side we represent the intensity distribution of the fluid of light in the near-field. The phase mask of the SLM allows to change the angle of the fluid-of-light. The DMD mask allows to pick the adequate mode through the white circle.

Concerning the pump beam (obstacle) the phase masks we used are shown in the figure below. They give a complete control of the Bessel beam, namely, its radius and its angle of incidence at the expense of the distance of propagation of the Bessel beam (focus depth z_D).

B.7 shows the phase masks uploaded to the spatial light modulator in order to generate Bessel beam shapes. By controlling the phase mask we can change the diameter of the Bessel beam. Bessel beams with larger diameter last for a long distance of propagation compared to lower Bessel diameter beams. According to our measurement, Bessel beams in figures (a), (b) and (c) last respectively for distances 2 cm, 3.5 cm and 4.5 cm.

B.A.3 The digital micromirror device (DMD)

The DMD is an electrical device that comprises a controller and a screen made up of highly reflective micro-mirrors. It is considered a micro-electrical-mechanical system (MEMS) that has an electrical input and an optical output. Each micro-mirror represents a pixel of the screen controllable with an electrical signal. Alike the SLM, this device is also used in digital video projectors and allows a spatial modulation of light through its intensity or its phase. Similarly to the SLM, we can upload images to the screen of the DMD to command the rotations of the micro-mirrors; Hence, a deflection of the laser beam occurs.

Figure B.7: Figure of phase masks uploaded to the SLM for generating a Bessel beam. The corresponding intensity distributions of the Bessel are displayed on the right side. As shown in the figure we can increase the diameter of the Bessel through controlling the phase masks. D_b are the measured diameters of each Bessel beam on the figure.

The device we used has a screen width 16 mm of diagonal length and a resolution of 1920×1080 comprising over two million micro-mirrors. Each micro-mirror measures $7.56 \mu\text{m}$ of length (width) and can perform a rotation of 12° in two different directions (see figure B.9).

To properly describe the DMD system, one needs to refer to the diffraction theory, since it is a screen

made up of millions of micro-mirrors. In addition to this, the micro-mirrors of the DMD are slightly tilted, therefore, one needs to adjust the angle of incidence to fulfil the blazing condition. In this paragraph, we do not derive this. However, for whom who are interested in the blazing condition of the DMD we cite the work of S. Popoff^[216]. We model the DMD by a transmittance coefficient denoted by T_{DMD} . Our employment of the DMD is limited to only a binary amplitude modulator. Therefore, the global output electric field can be written as a function of the input field as follows (see figure B.8):

$$E_{\text{out}} = T_{\text{DMD}}E_{\text{in}}, \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where T_{DMD} has binary values 0 and 1, E_{in} and E_{out} are respectively the input output electric field.

Figure B.8: illustration of the DMD screen transmittance

The reason for which we used a DMD instead of an SLM (as an amplitude modulator) is the rate of extinction. As we pointed out earlier, we need to filter the unwanted modes induced by the blazed grating at the output of the SLM to suppress the interference in the beam. Using the amplitude SLM we cannot achieve this because of the low extinction rate of the SLM, while the DMD allows to reach approximately a rate of extinction of $r_e = 40 \text{ dB}$.

The mask we upload to the DMD to carry out a spatial filtering is shown in the figure B.10. The white pattern corresponds to 12° (pixel value = 1) while the black one corresponds to -12° (pixel value = 0).

Figure B.9: Figure of the DMD screen. Each micromirror pitch can carry out a rotation of 12° in both directions (CW, CCW) enabling a deflection of the laser beam.

B.A.4 Determination of the white light power

In this subsection we give the experimental procedure we used to measure the power of the white illuminating our nonlinear crystal. As explained in chapter 3, the white light is used to control the saturation intensity of the nonlinear crystal in order to monitor its nonlinear refractive index. Therefore, it is of a crucial importance to have a measurable quantity referring to the saturation intensity I_{sat} .

We precise that the incoherent light is generated from a Halogen lamp equipped with reflector to guide the generated incoherent light. This lamp is controlled through the voltage applied across which can be varied continuously from 0 to 5 V. Therefore, the only parameter that we know is the applied voltage.

Figure B.10: Figure of the facet of the DMD displaying the diffraction modes of the laser beam in the Fourier space (after applying a blazed grating phase mask). The upper part of each panel displays the corresponding mask uploaded to the DMD. Panel a. shows the result of a completely white mask, all the modes pass. Panel b. shows only the central spot picked by the white pitch. Panel c. displays the filtering process of the central spot.

The measure of the white light power is a tricky job to carry out because the incoherent light possesses a very large spectrum and the power might vary with respect to the frequency of the spectrum. In our experiment, we considered that the lamp is a black-body^[217] that has a certain temperature T when the voltage is applied. The temperature of the lamp is specified in the notice of the lamp. Therefore, using Wien's displacement law we can calculate the wavelength at which the intensity per unit wavelength of the radiation is at maximum λ_{\max} , according to Wein's law we write:

$$\lambda_{\max} = \frac{b}{T}, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

where $b = 2.897771955 \cdot 10^{-3}$ mK is known as Wien's displacement constant and T is the temperature of the body. Wien's displacement law shows how the spectrum of black-body radiation at any temperature is related to the spectrum at any other temperature.

The lamp we used goes to a temperature of $T = 3400$ K. Therefore, the wavelength at which the intensity is maximal is $\lambda_{\max} = 852$ nm.

Now, after calculating λ_{\max} , it should be easy to measure the white light power at this wavelength. The experimental measured values of the white light power versus the applied voltage across the lamp is shown

on figure B.11.

Figure B.11: Measured white light power versus the applied voltage across the lamp

In our measurement of medium's characterisation, we used three different applied voltage i.e. $V = [2, 3, 4]$ V. which correspond respectively to white light powers of $P_{wl} = [0.36, 0.96, 1.92]$ W. To sum up, although it is not rigorously correct, this technique allowed us to have a measurable physical quantity to control the saturation intensity of our nonlinear medium.

Appendix B.B Negative velocities measurements artifacts

As we said before in the footnote of the subsection 4.4.4, we do not present results relative to negative velocities. That is because for the simple reason of the cavity effects arising in this interval of measurement. The cavity effects arise from the reflections occurring inside the crystal on the surface between the bulk and the air. They manifest themselves as a large scale interference in the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam (see figure B.13.(a)).

To avoid the cavity effects, we slightly tilt the crystal with an angle θ_0 with respect to the propagation axis z . We illustrate in figure B.12 a tilted crystal with various signs of the fluid-of-light velocities (i.e. incidence angle θ_{in}).

As one can see, when θ_{in} approaches θ_0 , that is shown in B.12, the reflected amount of light by the faces of the crystal interferes with the probe beam (fluid-of-light). In the other case $\theta_{in} > 0$, the reflected amount of light by the faces of the crystal does not interfere with the fluid-of-light beam. The large scale interference makes it generally difficult to study the fluid-of-light in this conditions. That is why we focused mainly on the case where $\theta_{in} > 0$. However, in the case of $\theta_{in} < 0$ we have also recorded a displacement of obstacle in the negative direction $-\mathbf{x}$. We display in figures B.13.(b) and B.13.(c) respectively the displacement of the obstacle in the negative direction along the x -axis and the y -axis.

Note that this set of measurement cannot be compared to the results we presented in section 4.4.4. This is because the negative set of measurement were carried out in different conditions, particularly, the imaging

Figure B.12: illustration of the experimental configuration in order to get rid of the cavity effects. In the case of positive angles $\theta_{in} > 0$ (top row), the cavity effect was overcome thanks to the inclination of the crystal. In the negative angles case $\theta_{in} < 0$ (bottom row), a large scale interference pattern takes place.

Figure B.13: Negative angle illustration. (a) the spatial intensity distribution of the fluid-of-light beam at the output of the crystal, The measurement is done at $I_f = 262 \text{ mW.cm}^{-2}$. (b) The displacement of the obstacle at the output of the crystal along the x -axis. (c) The measurement of the displacement along the y direction. This measurement defined the uncertainty of the obstacle displacement.

objective was $4\times$ instead of $20\times$. However, one can qualitatively see that a similar behaviour is exhibited by the fluid-of-light and by the obstacle as well.

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